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4. Summary

This report presents research conducted under Task 2.2 of Work Package 2, focused on the role of warning systems as a significant tool used in Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR). Warning systems bring together a wide range of stakeholders, using different warning types, communication channels, and cutting across sectoral and disciplinary silos, to generate effective decisions and actions. The research carried out focused on multi-hazard warning systems (MHWS) used in DRR to integrate short to long term preparedness, prevention, mitigation, response, and recovery. Recent evidence suggests that multi-hazard risks (e.g., cascading, compounding, and consecutive hazards) are becoming more frequent across Europe. The HuT project addresses the growing challenges posed by climate extreme and multi-hazard risks, including floods, storms, forest fires, droughts, heatwaves, and landslides.

The complexities of climate extremes and multi-hazard risks present new challenges in managing and communicating risks to different users, especially in regions heavily dependent on tourism. The Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030 and subsequent Early Warnings for All initiative underline the need for a multi-hazard and multisectoral approach to warnings and risk management that are integrated. While there have been some advancements in multi-hazard approaches, a critical gap remains in systemic understanding on implementing effective MHWS across scales and users. This research fills this critical gap by examining the state of the art of DRR and warning systems in five demonstrator sites and the extent to which multi-hazard risks are integrated between local, regional, and national systems with a specific focus on stakeholder roles and perspectives.

The specific case studies presented in this study showcase long-term multi-hazard experiences, including in Switzerland, Iceland, Spain, Italy, and the UK. Using qualitative social scientific methods, comprising over six weeks of fieldwork, this study examined how national, regional, and local MHWS operate in each DEM site, the barriers and challenges stakeholders face in implementation, and how these can be overcome to communicate risks effectively. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with stakeholders from multiple perspectives and across different sectors, including national and local government, emergency authorities, weather and meteorological services, hazard specialists, scientists, private sector, community and civil society, volunteer and public organisations to fully understand the key actors, decision-making processes, and interactions across scales within the DRR/warning system (see table 1). The research was conducted under UCL research ethics approval as well as EU guidelines and was participatory in nature with DEMs as the main contacts and partners throughout the research process.

Research has shown that for early warning systems (EWS) to be effective there is a need to better understand the role of social and behavioural processes, including decision-making, communication, and interaction between actors and across scales (Fearnley 2011). Decision-makers working to manage disaster risks and extreme weather events must navigate complex and interconnected challenges that require novel approaches to enable effective coordination, communication, and collaboration. This report integrates expertise from social and behavioural sciences to provide recommendations on effective multi-hazard risk management and warning communication strategies and provides practical insights on implementing multi-sectoral MHWS that can be tailored and adapted across contexts reaching multiple users.

This report is structured with an introduction and overview of European warning and risk management systems. It provides a brief literature review and outlines the methodology used to examine the five demonstrator sites. In each DEM section, a detailed overview and historical background of the risk/hazard management and warning system is given, followed by a summary

of the governance structure. The next section outlines the multi-hazard warning system and how it is operated at the national, regional, and local level. A summary of key actors and agencies involved in the warning chain, including in forecasting, observation, risk assessment, monitoring, issuing warnings, communicating warnings, and response is presented. Specific information is presented on how actors across scales work together, communicate, and interact across the warning sequence and chain of responsibility. Detailed information is also provided on decision-making, warning design, and the different warnings that are issued for multiple hazards. The next section highlights strengths and good practices in each case as well as challenges and gaps that remain. Recommendations and guidance based on the analysis is provided for how to enhance the MHEWS to better address the changing climatic conditions. A summary of where practices could be shared to help enhance warnings across the DEMS and areas for collaboration are provided. Finally, summative reflections on communicating multi-hazard warnings and risk management strategies are discussed.

Table 1: Summary of Research Conducted

	DEM 2 Val d'Aran, Spain	DEM 3 Lattari, Italy	DEM 6 E Fjords, Iceland	DEM 9 Dorset, UK	DEM 10 Bern, Switzerland
Number of Interviews	15	22	22	24	15
Visited Locations	Barcelona, Vielha, Baqueira, Arties, Casau, Fos, Cierp-Gaud	Naples, Sorrento, Salerno, Amalfi, Atrani	Reykjavík, Seydisfjordur, Neskaupstadur,	Dorset, Weymouth, West Bay, Poole, Nottingham, Exeter	Bern, Steffisburg, Thun
Stakeholders Interviewed	Cartographic and Geological Institute of Catalonia (ICGC), Meteorological Service of Catalonia (SMC), Civil Protection, Regional and municipal offices, Research and scientific institutes, Public and community organisations, Private sector	Italian National Department for Civil Protection (DPC), Centro Funzionale Regione Campani, Red Cross, Municipal offices, Scientists, Fire services, Volunteer organisations	Icelandic Meteorological Office (IMO), Department of Civil Protection and Emergency Management (NCIP), Iceland Search and Rescue (ICE-SAR), Red Cross, Municipal offices, Austurbru, Skaffell Austurlands, Scientists, Residents	British Geological Survey (BGS), UK MET Office, Flood Forecasting Centre (FFC), Environment Agency (EA), Civil Contingency Advisors (CCA), Local Councils, RNLI, Voluntary & Public organisations	Federal Office for the Environment (FOEN), LAINAT, MeteoSwiss, Cantonal Office for Civil Defence, Cantonal Office for Water and Waste, Regional Offices, Municipal Offices, Local Natural Hazard Advisors(LNHA), Fire services Residents, Private sector
Meetings & Events	Visits to: Avalanche Center (Centre de Lauegi D'Aran), Val d'Aran emergency center control room, Plan d'Arem dam, 2013 flood event sites	Meetings/ events: Civil Protection Open Day, Volcano Flegrei Exercise "Exe Flegrei 2024" Visit to: Civil Defense Emergency Operation Centre	Visits to: IMO's Hazard monitoring room, DCPEM (NCIP), Neskaupstadur Police Station, Site of 2020 landslides	Meetings/ events: Dorset Coast Forum Conference Visits to: weather station, landslide sites	Visits to: Mobiliar Lab, Zugl River and flood sites, warning and flood protection site

5. Introduction

Early warning systems, defined as “an integrated system of hazard monitoring, forecasting and prediction, disaster risk assessment, communication and preparedness activities systems and processes that enables individuals, communities, governments, businesses and others to take timely action to reduce disaster risks in advance of hazardous events,” have long been recognised as one of the most important tools for effective disaster risk reduction and risk communication (UN 2016: 17). However, the management and warning of multi-hazard risks has become a pre-eminent pressing need. Recent evidence suggests that multi-hazard risks and their interrelationships (e.g., cascading, compounding, and consecutive hazards) are becoming more frequent across Europe. Natural hazards and climate-related extremes affected millions of people across the EU and caused economic losses of €738 billion between 1980 and 2023 and €59 billion in 2021 and €52 billion in 2022 (EEA 2024). The five countries included in this study, Switzerland, Iceland, Spain, Italy, and the UK face multi-hazard risks, including hydrometeorological, geophysical, and climate-related, in addition to other risks. These complex risks emphasise the need to move from single-hazard-focused to multi-hazard risk management and warning systems (Trogrlić et al. 2024; Navarro et al. 2023).

In recent years, international agreements and policy initiatives, such as the United Nations Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction and the Early Warnings for All initiative have highlighted the need for further research and development of effective, people-centred multi-hazard warning systems as well as comprehensive approaches to disaster risk management (DRM). However, while there has been some progress made in developing multi-hazard warning systems (MHWS), significant gaps remain in the implementation of these systems (Rokhideh et al. 2025). Moreover, cross-sectoral, cross-agency, and transdisciplinary coordination necessary to manage and deal with cascading, compounding, and consecutive risks still pose a challenge to effective MHWS in many countries (Tupper and Fearnley 2023). Fostering greater collaboration, coordination, and knowledge-sharing across sectors and between local, regional, and national scales will provide more effective responses to multi-hazard risks (Taylor and Rokhideh 2024).

This study focused on the role of warning systems as a significant tool used in DRR to integrate short to long term preparedness, responses, recovery, and mitigation. Warnings systems bring together a wide range of stakeholders, using different warning types, communication methods, and cutting across sectoral and disciplinary silos, to generate effective decisions and actions. This research examined three main domains of inquiry:

1. Decision-making processes by key stakeholders: integrating behavioural sciences to aid warning effectiveness, e.g., different iconographies and designs of systems.
2. Multi-scale warnings: elements involving society, bottom-up approaches and community-based warnings, integration with top-down regional or national government or international warnings systems.
3. Multi-directional warning communication: how to involve the public and key stakeholders; how to embed warnings into the fabric of society.

6. Multi-Hazard Warning Systems in the European Context

This report explores how MHWS are being implemented across the European context by examining good practices, challenges, and lessons learned in practice from the DEMs. Recent evidence suggests that multi-hazard risks (e.g., cascading, compounding, and consecutive hazards) and climate extremes are becoming more frequent and impactful across Europe (Bednar-Friedl et al. 2022; Trogrlić et al. 2024). Natural hazards and climate extremes affected millions of people in the EU, causing economic losses of €738 billion between 1980 and 2023 (EEA 2024). Europe is expected to face even more major impacts from a changing climate over the coming decades with challenges encompassing but not limited to sea-level rise, coastal flooding, and coastal erosion (Laino and Iglesias 2024; Kreibich et al. 2014). There have been a wealth of impact studies conducted at the European level examining a single specific weather or climate risk, including as fluvial floods (Rojas et al. 2012; Alfieri et al. 2015), coastal floods (Nicholls and Klein 2005; Hinkel et al. 2010), heat waves (Fischer and Schär 2010; Russo et al. 2015; Christidis et al. 2015), storms (Nikulin et al. 2011; Outten and Esau 2013) and wildfires (Bedia et al. 2013; Migliavacca et al. 2013). However, while it is increasingly recognised that hazards and their impacts often overlap in space and time, necessitating a more systemic approach to address these risks (Šakić Trogrlić et al., 2022, Ward et al., 2022, Hochrainer-Stigler et al., 2023, Kreibich et al., 2022), there has been a dearth of research focusing on the management of multi-hazard risks, especially with regards to integrating all aspects of the disaster risk management cycle (DRM) and the warning value chain (see below).

Following numerous calls for multi-hazard approaches to disaster risk reduction, a definition of MHWS was established for the first time in the international policy context:

Multi-hazard early warning systems address several hazards and/or impacts of similar or different type in contexts where hazardous events may occur alone, simultaneously, cascadingly or cumulatively over time, and taking into account the potential interrelated effects. A multi-hazard early warning system with the ability to warn of one or more hazards increases the efficiency and consistency of warnings through coordinated and compatible mechanisms and capacities, involving multiple disciplines for updated and accurate hazards identification and monitoring for multiple hazards (UN 2016:17).

This definition and novel approach calls for a coherent and systemic approach that requires coordination at multiple governance and management levels (national, regional, and local). MHWS considers four interrelated elements (pillars) (see Fig. 1a and b) that address the phases of the DRM/warning value chain, including risk assessment and disaster education, preparedness, detection and monitoring, warning communication and dissemination, and response. To be effective, MHWS need to i) be designed to detect different hazards that may occur alone, simultaneously, or cascade (multi-hazard criteria), ii) cover the entire range, from hazard detection to action, which includes providing understandable and actionable warning messages (“end-to-end” criteria) and iii) designed with people in mind, to empower them to act on time and in an appropriate manner to reduce potential harm according to people-centred criteria (UNDRR, 2023).

Disaster risk knowledge
Systematically collect data and undertake risk assessments

- Are the hazards and the vulnerabilities well known by the communities?
- What are the patterns and trends in these factors?
- Are risk maps and data widely available?

Detection, observations, monitoring, analysis and forecasting of hazards
Develop hazard monitoring and early warning services

- Are the right parameters being monitored?
- Is there a sound scientific basis for making forecasts?
- Can accurate and timely warnings be generated?

Preparedness and response capabilities
Build national and community response capabilities

- Are response plans up to date and tested?
- Are local capacities and knowledge made use of?
- Are people prepared and ready to react to warnings?

Warning dissemination and communication
Communicate risk information and early warnings

- Do warnings reach all of those at risk?
- Are the risks and warnings understood?
- Is the warning information clear and usable?

Figure 1a and 1b: The MHEWS Four Interconnected pillars (Source: WMO, 2022).

The warning value chain, developed by the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) and High Impact Weather Project (HIWeather) follows a similar approach, underlining the importance of the links and flows between the different phases or “valleys” of work (Golding et al. 2019, see figure 2). The links in the value chain symbolize the interactions between the actors or agencies (Ebert et al. 2024). There have been some limitations raised with this approach with regard to the overreliance and privileged focus given to National Meteorological and Hydrological Services (NMHSs) as a key actor of the value chain, especially since in multi-hazard risk landscapes there are a multitude of actors that provide important services at different levels and thus should be incorporated and integrated as equal partners in the warning system (Rokhideh et al. 2025). In the case of Italy, for example, the key actor in the warning system is civil protection while Switzerland’s warning governance structure includes a multitude of agencies and departments beyond the NMHS.

Figure 2: Warning Value Chain depicting outputs, exchanges (bridges), and links between actors in the system (Source: Golding et al. 2019).

Nevertheless, this research builds on the important work of the warning value chain and key scholarship on multi-risk governance and critical links within the early warning system (Scolobig et al. 2017; Garcia and Fearnley 2012).

Following Garcia and Fearnley (2012), early warning systems (EWS), in this research, are seen as extensive systems that integrate different components of disaster risk reduction to communicate risks to populations and to reduce negative impacts. Historically, research has focused on the individual components or subsystems of EWSs, such as forecasting, hazard monitoring, risk assessment, and warning dissemination. However, analyses of natural hazards indicate that, in most cases, the processes that link individual components of EWS fail, rather than the components themselves (Garcia and Fearnley 2012). That is why coordination and integration between the components or links are paramount, especially for communicating timely and actionable warnings to the public. The recent flood disaster in DEM1 Valencia underscored this point whereby the lack of national and regional coordination and collaboration led to the failure of communicating AEMET’s warnings prior to the flood event (see Deliverable 5.7 for more information). Timely and effective warnings, mitigation, and response were further hampered by political and institutional differences between national, regional, and local entities.

The warning value chain elaborates that links in the chain can be described as flows, such as the communication and exchange of data, knowledge, resources and relations among actors, agencies, and sectors. Flows can be internal and external to an organisation and relations among actors govern the flow of information and outputs. It is therefore vital to clarify the roles and responsibilities associated with each actor and agency so that the system can operate in a coherent and coordinated manner to ensure the effectiveness of the flow (Garcia and Fearnley, 2012; Potter et al., 2021). This, however, can prove very challenging in practice.

A study on eleven European countries by Scolobig and colleagues (2017) further elaborates on this, noting that institutional barriers posed the greatest challenge to adopting multi-risk approaches, as institutional risk frameworks and management primarily remain single-risk centered. In other words, authorities are rarely officially responsible for the management of cascading effects of hazards and furthermore institutional mandates limit their reach and scope.

Drawing on these developments, this research forefronts multi-risk management and governance, focusing on the links and interactions between agencies through multiple scales, including their coordination, communication, and collaboration. In this way, we aim to move beyond technocratic understandings of EWS and provide critical insights on how to enhance multi-sectoral and multi-hazard approaches throughout all phases of the warning value chain/DRM cycle in diverse contexts.

With regards to warning communication, we draw on literature on the state of the art of warning communication developed through the Warning Response Model and further advanced by impact-based approaches (Mileti and Sorensen 1990; Potter et al. 2018; Fearnley and Beaven 2018). Based on these developments, five main elements are identified as necessary for designing effective warning messages:

1. Information about the hazard, its characteristics, and impacts
2. The location and population at risk
3. The message source
4. Protective action guidance
5. The time to act or time the message expires (have been found to increase the likelihood that individuals will take protective action)
6. Resources or links to for further information

MHWS in the European Context

At the EU level, there have been several initiatives and policy strategies advocating for multi-hazard warning systems and all of society approaches. The European Disaster Risk Reduction Strategy Roadmap 2021-2030, recognising that risks are increasingly complex and require early-warning and preparedness systems, identified “investing in accessible multi-hazard early-warning systems” as one of its four action areas (EFDRR 2021: 5). Regional programmes such as Copernicus and multiple Horizon Europe projects, including the HuT are providing innovative research for inclusive MHWS and disaster risk reduction tools for a disaster-resilient Europe.

Cross-border collaboration is necessary to address the MHEWS needs across Europe. The EU Civil Protection Mechanism (UCPM) is partly responding to these needs through facilitation of enhanced forecasting and emergency assistance between the Member States (MS) and the ten participating countries (ECHO, 2025a). The UCPM was established in 2001 to strengthen civil protection cooperation in disaster risk prevention, preparedness and response coordinated by the

Emergency Response Coordination Centre (ERCC) (ibid.). The ERCC monitors the hazard events with the assistance of the EU's early warning and information systems provided through the Copernicus Programme and provides early assessments of the disaster events to the UCPM members (ECHO, 2025b).

To enhance direct and rapid communication of warnings and emergencies, the Directive (EU) 2018/1972 establishing the European Electronic Communications Code (EECC) introduces an objective, that has been effective since December 2020, that Member States will set up a public warning system to send alerts to citizens on their mobile phones in the event of a natural disaster or other major emergency in their area. The EU supports the member states in the task by providing, through the Copernicus Programme, Emergency Management Services consisting of mapping and early warnings components (CEMS, 2024).

7. Methodology

The research design was developed as part of Work Package 2, Task 2.2 led by UCL. UCL and the lead researcher developed the research design, methodology, and analysis with support from the University of Helsinki and five DEM partners in Spain, Italy, Iceland, UK, and Switzerland (see table 2 and figure 3). A multi-step research process was designed to ensure systematic research was carried out across all DEM sites whilst data collection tools were flexible to adapt to each context. A qualitative research approach was taken with methods that included desk and policy review, stakeholder mapping, ethnographic observations, and semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders, comprising of decision-makers, local government representatives, emergency authorities, weather and hazard specialists, scientists, and community members; a summary of the research steps is outlined in figure 4. Prior to data collection, a thorough ethical review application was completed and submitted for approval to UCL Ethics Board along with risk assessments. The research approach was participatory in nature with DEM partners as main contacts and partners in providing information and recruiting key stakeholders in the disaster management cycle and warning system.

Table 2: Demonstrators involved in Task 2.2

DEM	Study Area	Country	Partners
DEM 2	Val d'Aran	Spain	UPC ARANTEC
DEM 3	Lattari mountains	Italy	CMCC UNISA
DEM 6	East fjords	Iceland	IMO NCIP
DEM 9	Dorset county	UK	BGS UK MET
DEM 10	Bern canton	Switzerland	UNIGE

Figure 3: Map of Demonstrators in the HuT, including those involved in Task 2.2

The data collection and analysis were guided by the following research objectives and questions developed by the lead researchers after consultations with DEM partners:

RQ1: Designing effective, scalable, integrated, and inclusive action-based warnings

How are decisions made on the use and design of warnings, so that they can be integrated, scalable, and standardised (if this is desirable) in theory and practice? How do these decisions affect actions to specific warnings considering inclusivity across languages, cultures, backgrounds, non-residents, and technologies?

- *[Related to Subtask 1] Decision-making processes by key stakeholders: integrating behavioural sciences to aid warning effectiveness, e.g., different iconographies and designs of systems.*

RQ2: Implementing multi-hazard warning systems across different scales

How can multi-hazard warning systems (MHEWS) be implemented across different scales including local, national, and regional, whilst also integrated within a multi-risk and multi-vulnerable environment?

- *[Related to Sub-task 2] Multi-scale warnings: elements involving society, bottom-up approaches from community-based warnings, integration with top-down regional or national government or international warnings systems.*

RQ3: Communicating inclusive warnings within a multi-risk context

How does everyone communicate warnings for different hazards with different users and different communication strategies for risk, hazards, impacts?

- *[Related to Sub-task 3] Multi-directional warning communication: how to involve the public and key stakeholders; how to embed warnings into the fabric of society.*

Figure 4: Multi-Step Research Process (designed by UCL)

Following a comprehensive desk review of background information and policy documents for each DEM study area, consultative meetings were held with DEM partners to initiate the data collection process (see figure 4 for step-by-step process). DEM partners provided contextual information to facilitate adaptation of the data tools and interview protocols to each DEM site context. A stakeholder analysis was conducted in order to (i) identify relevant stakeholders, i.e. actors involved in warning systems and risk, hazard, and disaster management processes in each DEM site, and (ii) categorise key stakeholders (see Reed et al 2009) based on background research and consultations with the DEM partners, and supported by thematic literature (Reiter et al 2022; André et al 2012; Reed et al 2009). Stakeholder analysis elicited information on the range of actors at different governance levels in each DEM site and allowed for unified sampling between the five DEMs. Key actors and agencies were identified for their role in the disaster risk management phase (prevention, preparedness, and response and recovery), sector (research, governance, private sector), and operation level (local, regional, national).

A list of potential interviewees were identified through stakeholder mapping and additional participants were identified through snowball sampling, i.e. suggested by interviewees. The total amount of interviews was decided based on a sufficient representation from each key stakeholder group (identified and validated together with the DEM partners), and the theoretical saturation of the collected material which, was ensured based on preliminary thematic analysis of the material (i.e. field notes) (Timmermans & Tavory, 2012). Theoretical saturation, here, means that repetition in the discussions indicated that there would not be significant changes in the descriptions of the existing warning systems, the related decision-making process, and extent of integration of multi-hazards.

UCL lead researcher designed the semi-structured interview protocol and questions based on the research objectives from the Task 2.2 proposal and consultations with DEMs (see Annex 1). The interview protocol was piloted and implemented during the first field visit in DEM10, then adapted for contextual and language adaptability. Based on the stakeholder mapping and analysis, participants were recruited for interviews following purposive sampling methodology. The target sample in each DEM site was 15-25 participants. Field visits of DEM sites ranged from 10 to 14 days depending on the sample size.

Semi-structured interviews were conducted in English, Italian, German, Catalan, and Spanish. Semi-structured interviews were translated, transcribed, and analysed using thematic coding and qualitative content analysis, guided by the predefined themes in the interview protocol (see e.g., Flick 2021; Braun and Clarke 2021). Interviews with actors from multiple perspectives and across different sectors were conducted to increase research validity.

Potential limitations to this study are related to the scope of task and methodology. Since this research focused on the role of decision-makers and relevant stakeholders in the DRM and warning system, this study did not gather extensive data from the public as it was outside the scope of the study. This could pose potential limitations in understanding the user perspectives and the effectiveness of warnings (e.g. how well the system meets population needs and concerns). However, this limitation is aimed to be overcome by the subsequent task following this study, Task 2.3, which will focus on public engagement and provide necessary input from local populations in the DEMs. Methodologically, a limitation could also relate to analysis carried out by two different researchers, potentially leading to interpretation bias and coding variability. This can lead to difficulties in comparing or synthesising responses from different countries. However, this limitation was overcome by the two researchers reviewing each other's sections and ensuring intercoder agreement. Communication and language differences between research teams across different countries may also vary across disciplines and cultures. This potential limitation was addressed by circulating the report with all partners for review, fact-checking, and identification of potential gaps. Another limitation was the large amount of qualitative data (e.g. interview

transcripts, field notes, policy documents) to analyse in a limited time. Given project deadlines, it was decided to conduct more in-depth analysis in preparation of published papers. Another potential limitation of this study was conducting research within a new context and country system. While the researchers had thematic expertise in the topic under study, the researchers worked closely with DEM partners to ensure they understood the contextual specificities of each country. The entire research process was conducted in collaboration with the DEM partners as well to ensure a relevant sample and diverse perspectives from key stakeholders.

8. DEM 10 Bern Canton, Switzerland

8.1. Overview and background

This section provides a description and analysis of the hazard management and warning system of Switzerland. First, a brief history of the Swiss DRM system is outlined with a focus on how past disasters triggered important changes and led to the current iteration of its system of disaster risk management. Based on interviews with federal, cantonal, and local stakeholders, we outline the strengths, challenges, and gaps identified and provide recommendations on best practices and lessons learned on ways to improve the system. The main hazards that affect Switzerland and authorities cover include:

- Floods
- Avalanches
- Debris flow
- Storms (Rain, Wind, and Thunderstorms)
- Mass movements (Rockfalls and Landslide)
- Forest fires
- Frost/Ice and Slippery Roads
- Heatwaves

This section is based on a review of grey literature and DRM organisations websites, risk and hazard management reports, on-site observations, and 15 stakeholder interviews conducted with national, regional (Bern canton) and local (municipal) stakeholders from the Federal Office for Environment, LAINAT Steering Committee, Civil Protection system, MeteoSwiss, Natural Hazards Division, Forest Office and forest fire management, Cantonal Water Regulation Authority, municipal authorities, natural hazard advisors, scientists and researchers, private companies tasked with installing warning systems, and resident experts. Interviews were conducted in English and German during March 2024.

Case Study: Zulg River, Steffisburg Bern Canton

The research carried out in Switzerland examined the DRM and warning systems across the federal, cantonal, and municipal scales. The selected case study was Bern Canton and specifically the Zulg river floods and cascading debris flows affecting the municipality of Steffisburg and beyond. The Zulg warning system served as a test case for the EU ANYWHERE project (<http://anywhere-h2020.eu/>).

Bern is the capital of Switzerland and a UNESCO world heritage site situated downstream of the head-watershed of the Aare River. Triggering meteorological forcing are rain-on-snow events, local convective rainfalls and upper air cold cut-off lows ultimately causing serious inundations in the area. Furthermore, compound, and cascading effects often exacerbate the situations: instream wood mobilization in the upstream rivers often contribute to an exacerbation of the flood situation. High sediment loads stemming from landslides and riverbank erosion, but also related wood mobilisation, potentially clogging bridges and weirs. The Zulg is a mountain river that is 23km long and flows through Steffisburg and into the Aare river in Bern canton. In the Zulg catchment, heavy local precipitation is common and leads to flash flooding carrying debris and wood downstream. Various flood events in recent years have demonstrated the high risk potential

of the river and its cascading effects. In July 2012, exceptionally high local precipitation intensity of 80–87 mm/h led to a fast-flowing flood and large amounts of driftwood into the Steffisburg area and leading into the Aare river, presenting a threat to both the cities of Steffisburg and Bern (Flussbau AG, 2012). Due to the heavy and significant amount of precipitation, runoff of the Zulg river increased rapidly and caused mass movements on the hillslopes, bank erosion and sediment mobilisation along the riverbed causing a sequence of effects (Schauwecker et al. 2019) (see figure 5 and 6).

Figures 5 and 6: Flooding and Debris Flow of Zulg River July 2012 (Source: Steffisburg Fire Department shared with lead author)

The flood caused damage in Steffisburg, flooding some streets, affecting few buildings, and destroying bridges, and a camping site in the valley floor. After receiving a phone call from a resident upstream of the river, local fire fighters were alerted and immediately patrolled the river area, warning populations with loudspeakers to leave the river banks, and closed access to the bridges.

The Zulg river catchment event demonstrated the potential of a local thunderstorm in the Swiss Prealps to cause severe damage in Bern, 30 km downstream and while local precipitation was not predicted or forecasted high local rainfall intensities were registered in the Zulg valley, there was no precipitation in Bern, where the situation was critical just a few hours later (Schauwecker et al. 2019). Following the event review, authorities concluded that initiation of the warning was dependent on an informal, ad-hoc system based on the presence of local residents who contacted the responsible entities (Flussbau AG, 2012). As a consequence of the event, a warning and alarm system was designed and installed by the private company Geopraevent, which includes a radar gauge and a webcam in the upper Zulg river. The system automatically sends SMS and voice calls to the fire and police departments of Steffisburg when the water levels are high (Schauwecker et al. 2019 (see figure 7).

Figure 7: Flooding event of June 2021 (Source: Steffisburg Fire Department shared with lead author)

8.2. Disaster Risk Management and Warning System

Switzerland has a long track record of reviewing, analyzing, and revising their natural hazard management strategy following major disasters (Hess and Schmid 2012). The devastating floods and cascading risks of 2005 were one such event that was foundational in prompting major changes to prevention, early warning, and response measures in Switzerland. During these floods, overbank sedimentation, landslides and debris flows affected large parts of the country, claiming seven lives and costing CHF 3 billion. The disaster prompted major calls to action to improve alert systems, coordination, and hydrological and flood monitoring systems.

Post-event reviews carried out by the Swiss Federal Office for the Environment (FOEN) found that improvement in forecasting, hazard mapping, warning, and response measures could have reduced the losses incurred by 20% (Bezzola and Hegg 2008). The analysis identified several weaknesses in the Swiss DRM system, including the lack of coordination between the responsible federal authorities and resulting delays and inconsistencies in the transmission of timely warnings and information (Hess and Schmid 2012). Another crucial gap identified was that local authorities had difficulties “in interpreting the official warnings and transforming them into the necessary rescue and relief actions” (Hess and Schmid 2012: 910). A key lesson identified / learned was the limited exchange of information between response authorities and experts specialised in meteorology, hydrology, geology and engineering at all levels. The event also highlighted that while the Swiss system had well-established warning systems and operation centres for weather and avalanche forecasting, flood forecasting was not well developed.

The main recommendations from analysis of the 2005 floods and other disasters called for (1) an improvement of inter-institutional collaboration and, (2) the need for participatory local expertise and partnerships to monitor, mitigate, and warn of incidents (Hess and Schmid 2012). As a result, the Swiss Federal Council implemented the Optimisation of Early Warning and Alerting of Natural Hazards (OWARNA) to mandate responsible federal authorities to implement associated measures at organisational, structural and technical levels to prevent, mitigate, and respond to natural hazards. Three significant initiatives were developed: the founding of the coordinating body of multi-hazard risks, Steering Committee on Intervention in Natural Hazards (LAINAT), the data-sharing platform, Joint Information Platform for Natural Hazards (GIN), and local natural hazard advisors (LHNA). These have been instrumental in Switzerland’s current hazard management and its strengths in dealing with multi-hazard risks.

In terms of governance and policy, Switzerland has various strategies at national level that outline how to deal with climate extremes and natural hazards, including Management of Risks from Natural Hazards and Programme agreements and the Federal Council strategy for adaptation to climate change in Switzerland, among others.

8.3. Governance Structure and MHWS

The Swiss policy on dealing with natural hazards is based on the concept of integrated risk management, which involves reducing vulnerability and limiting impacts. Integrated risk management takes all types of hazards and their resulting risks into consideration, assessing them via comparison through multi-stakeholder processes in which authorities, experts, and affected communities agree on an acceptable risk level and risk reduction measures (Swiss Confederation 2022).

Dealing with natural hazards in Switzerland involves the complex cooperation between various authorities and specialist entities organised on the three levels: federal, cantonal, and municipal. Included in the hazard management system is a range of private actors that support and supplement the system in different capacities, including weather services, forecasting, warning, and hazard mapping. The Federal Office for the Environment (FOEN) is responsible for “the protection against natural hazards as well as accidents and safeguarding the environment and human health against impacts” ([Art.12: Organisationsverordnung für das UVEK](#)). While FOEN and specialised government departments tasked with warning and monitoring of risks, civil protection is responsible for mitigation and response. The Swiss Federal Office for Civil Protection (FOCP) consists of five partner organisations, i.e. the police, fire brigade, healthcare system, technical services and the protection and support service (see figure 8).

Figure 8: Cycle of measures involved in integrated risk management as defined by the Swiss Federal Office for Civil Protection (FOCP) (Source: FOCP 2019).

Responsibility for legislation and the formulation of natural hazard management policy lies with the Confederation and federal authorities, which also provide financial support to the 26 cantons and are responsible for warning and alerting the population and authorities in the case of a hazard event. The cantons are responsible for the enforcement of the federal laws, for contingency planning and for cantonal emergency management. The communes are responsible for the planning and implementation of preventive measures and also have to deal with natural hazard events on-site.

8.3.1. Multi-hazard Warnings in Switzerland

Currently, warnings are issued for severe weather (wind, storms, rain, snow, slippery roads, frost, heat), floods (rivers but not surface runoff), snow avalanches, forest fires, and earthquakes. Droughts and mass movements, such as landslides are under development.

Federal agencies are involved in issuing natural hazard warnings:

- Federal Office of Meteorology and Climatology (MeteoSwiss) → warns of severe weather and climate-related risks
- Federal Office for the Environment (FOEN) and Office for Forests and Natural Hazards → warns of floods, landslides, forest fires
- Institute for Snow and Avalanche Research (WSL) → warns of snow and avalanches
- Swiss Seismological Service → warns of earthquakes

8.3.2. Warning Sequence and Chain of Responsibility

The responsible authorities at national level coordinate the issuing of warnings through LAINAT. Clear responsibilities have been assigned: MeteoSwiss provides information about dangerous weather conditions, the Federal Office for the Environment about floods and related landslides as well as forest fires, the Institute for Snow and Avalanche Research about avalanches, and the Swiss Seismological Service about earthquakes. In a situation, in which several natural processes may lead to a major disaster (e.g. heavy precipitation and floods), it is planned to issue joint warnings and information, which will be prepared by the aforementioned natural hazards authorities. In the warning chain, the Federal or national authorities issue nationwide alerts and warnings, the Cantons disseminate and enrich the warnings as well as taking actions if necessary or coordinating with the municipalities, and lastly, the municipalities take actions to respond and manage risks and hazards (see figure 9). Through the subsidiary approach, the first responsibility to act upon the warnings is the municipal level through civil protection.

Figure 9: Swiss Warning Sequence with all scales involved in order of responsibility developed by lead author

8.3.3. Warning Design and Content

All warnings are issued on a five-level scale (see figure 10 and 11). The warnings issued by Federal authorities and MeteoSwiss currently contain information on the following elements: Type of event (e.g., "thunderstorm"), warning level (1, 2,3,4, or 5), description of the warning level ("no or minor danger", "moderate danger", "considerable danger", "high danger" or "very high danger"), name of the affected area, time period in which the warned event is predicted to occur, meteorological parameters (e.g., wind speed in km/h or 24 h sum of precipitation), potential amplifying factors if applicable, a web-link to general recommendations for action as well as the name of the sender of the message. MeteoSwiss warnings contain all the information required within the five elements that a warning message should contain according to Mileti and Sorensen (1990): hazard, location, guidance, time, and source.

Scale	Meaning
5 (dark red)	Extreme risk
4 (red)	High risk
3 (orange)	Considerable risk
2 (yellow)	Moderate risk
1 (green)	Little or no risk

Figure 10: Official Warning Level for Natural Hazard warnings (Source: [Natural Hazard Platform](#)).

Figure 11: Threshold Levels for Warnings (Source: Office for Forests and Natural Hazards 2018).

Many different actors, including private weather services and apps and the government-run MeteoSwiss and MeteoAlarm can issue warnings up to level three. However, when the alert level reaches a higher level (level 4 or 5), the Single Official Voice (SOV) process is activated to ensure alignment of alert level across multiple channels through media and mobile apps. The government can initiate a Single Official Voice process (SOV), according to which the media and all private actors are obliged to publish the same uniform warning and alert level. Warnings for different hazards are threshold based (see figure).

8.3.4. Communication, Dissemination, and Delivery of Warnings

Warnings are disseminated through the public Swiss natural hazard portal (NHP), MeteoSwiss app and website, and AlertSwiss app and website and all coordinated through the Steering Committee Intervention in Natural Hazards (LAINAT). The [Natural Hazard Platform](#) is a public-facing website where all information about current warnings and alerts of hazards are shared, including warning message, time and duration, alert level, and recommended actions (see figure below). NHP provides real-time information on alerts and warnings on a five-point alert level with recommended behaviour to take before, during and after natural hazard events (Lienert et al. 2021). The warnings are posted both on a map of Switzerland where users can select areas and regions on the map to illustrate affected regions, as well as in list form with order of severity. The NHP serves as a 'one-stop shop with icons, pictures, and detailed explanations on warning information for eleven hazard categories provided in five languages: German, French, Italian, Romansch, and English. Harmonised warning levels are depicted on a scale from "no/minor danger" (green), moderate danger (yellow), considerable danger (orange), high danger (red) to very high danger (dark red).

The NHP developed in 2014, is a milestone of the implementation of the Swiss Federal Council's resolution OWARNA and the development of LAINAT, in order to "improve the protection of the civilian population and the related warning processes" (Lienert et al. 2021). LAINAT, a coordination committee made up of four Federal offices and two Federal research Institutes is responsible for consulting, coordinating and developing natural hazard warnings at the strategic and operational level within the Swiss Federal administration (Wernli-Schärer et al. 2016).

MeteoSwiss currently distributes its warnings to the public via its mobile app (MeteoSwiss app), its website (www.meteoswiss.ch) and the Natural Hazard Portal (www.natural-hazards.ch). Additionally, information about the event and the warning is shared on social media. Warnings are also broadcast in public service radio and television. Online and print media also often report about MeteoSwiss warnings in their articles in case of impending severe weather. For very extreme events, MeteoSwiss additionally sends its warnings to Meteoalarm (www.meteoalarm.org), a website of European states' national meteorological services providing weather warnings, where they can be retrieved and redistributed by other actors such as Google and Apple.

Figure 12: Screen shot from 27.01.2025 of Warnings in Switzerland (Source: [Natural Hazard Platform](http://www.natural-hazards.ch)).

The Alertswiss app was a national app that was developed as an information platform to provide warning information for hazards affecting the whole of Switzerland and cantons selected by the user. The app is operated by the federal government and the cantons through the Federal Office for Civil Protection FOCP. The Alertswiss app sends push alerts to users “if they are in an at-risk area or have subscribed to a particular area as a favorite in the app” for a wide range of hazards (20). If someone does not want to download the app, there is open access to the Alertswiss website. Since May 2021, a pilot project delivers Alertswiss messages to all private radio broadcasters in Switzerland (FOCP 2021b). The app provides three danger level messages which users can decide which danger levels they want to be informed about.

1. information, for safety-relevant messages below the warning threshold;
2. warning, for possible dangers or events with behavioural recommendations;
3. alarm, for immediate dangers with mandatory behavioural instructions.

8.3.5. Multi-hazard Coordination

Swiss Steering Committee on Intervention in Natural Hazards (LAINAT)

To achieve necessary coordination and collaboration between relevant authorities in the government, the Swiss federal institutes responsible for issuing natural hazard warnings joined forces in 2008 in the Steering Committee Intervention in Natural Hazards (LAINAT). As a coordination body, LAINAT has been operational since 2009 and strengthens institutional processes to clarify political, strategic and technical responsibilities for effective decision-making and hazard management. The agencies included are the Federal Office for the Environment (BAFU-FOEN), the Federal Office of Meteorology and Climatology (MeteoSwiss), the Federal Office for Civil Protection (BABS-FOCP), the Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research and, the Institute for Snow and Avalanche Research (WSL-SLF), the Swiss Seismological Service (SED), and the Federal Office of Topography (swisstopo) has also been a member of LAINAT (see figure 13). The LAINAT coordinating body:

- Promotes preparation for natural hazards and climate extremes
- Coordinates mandates arising from the Federal Council resolution on the "Optimisation of Warning and Alerting" (OWARNA)
- Manages projects on hazard preparation, warning and alerting
- Steers and advises on the implementation of strategic issues in the field of warning systems, warning interfaces and distribution channels
- Is responsible for coordinating and integrating warning across agencies and ensuring a coordinated approach

Figure 13: LAINAT Partners

A management board, consisting of experts from the participating bodies, is responsible for the preparation and implementation of decisions of the directorial conference. The LAINAT secretariat is affiliated to the Federal Office for the Environment. The Committee's mandate is specified in a legislative act that regulates responsibilities and procedures in the event of nuclear, biological, chemical and disasters (refer to ABCN-Einsatzverordnung, SR 520.17)

Common Information Platform for Natural Hazards (GIN)

The Joint Information Platform for Natural Hazards or Gemeinsame Informationsplattform Naturgefahren (GIN) combines all available data on natural hazards in Switzerland in a user-friendly map application. It provides a solid foundation for identifying natural hazards early and preparing for them in a joint and coordinated manner with all responsible authorities at all levels, federal, cantonal, and municipal. This information has been available centrally to experts via the Confederation's Joint Information Platform for Natural Hazards (GIN) since summer 2017 (see figure 14). It includes measurements and observation data, forecasts and predictions, warnings, models and bulletins. The GIN platform combines data in a range of specialist areas (weather data, water levels, flow rates and wind and temperature data) on a single platform, allowing for a simpler and faster comprehensive analysis of the situation.

Figure 14: GIN Platform (Source: [Federal Office for the Environment FOEN 2023](#))

Examples of data shared between federal, cantonal, and municipal authorities as well as relevant actors include:

- Real-time measurement data from 1,200 weather stations, 300 water-monitoring stations and 150 snow-monitoring stations
- Weather forecasts and predicted water levels and flows
- Earthquakes with expert assessments
- Imaging data such as satellite images or precipitation radar
- Natural hazard warnings
- Situation assessments by experts provided in bulletins

Federal, cantonal, municipal, and local natural hazard experts have access to the platform free of charge once they have registered. GIN currently has around 3,000 users, including:

- Federal Office of Meteorology and Climatology (MeteoSwiss)
- WSL Institute for Snow and Avalanche Research (SLF)
- Federal Office for the Environment (FOEN)
- Swiss Seismological Service (SED)
- Emergency services (police, fire, etc.)
- Civil defence personnel
- Armed forces
- Cantonal specialist staff
- Municipal specialist staff
- Natural hazard advisors
- Regional management staff
- Mountain railway operators
- Private engineering firms

As a centralized data tool that aggregates various types of information related to natural hazards, including weather data, water levels, flow rates, and temperature data, it provides real-time, reliable data for natural hazard advisors and the public to enhance preparedness, decision-making, and response.

Key Features and Benefits of GIN (adapted from [FOEN](#))

- **Comprehensive Data Access:** GIN centralizes diverse data (e.g., weather, water levels, flow measurements, and temperature fluctuations) essential for assessing natural hazards like floods. This allows for faster, more efficient analysis during emergencies.
- **Time Savings:** By offering up-to-date, integrated data, GIN helps save valuable time during crises, enabling early intervention and improved protection for the population.
- **Improved Data Value:** Aggregating data from multiple sources increases its value, as more comprehensive datasets enhance the accuracy of hazard assessments.
- **Cooperation and Sharing:** GIN enables cross-organizational collaboration by making data from all Swiss natural hazard offices accessible on a single platform. It supports international data-sharing efforts for public protection.
- **Preparedness Support:** GIN helps users prepare for disasters by enabling them to create custom data dossiers for various scenarios, making it easier to access necessary information during an emergency.
- **Personalized Information:** Users can customize the platform to suit their needs, including setting up notifications for critical data thresholds. The dossier function allows for efficient data organization and retrieval.
- **Streamlined Collaboration:** The platform facilitates cooperation among different crisis teams by allowing the quick sharing of data and dossiers.
- **Learning from History:** GIN provides access to historical data for retrospective analysis, helping experts learn from past events to improve future response strategies.
- **User-Friendly Visualization:** GIN offers interactive maps, diagrams, and timelines to easily visualize complex data, ensuring that it is accessible to all users, from crisis managers to the public.
- **Real-Time Data:** GIN ensures high availability of real-time data, with updates every 10 minutes from monitoring stations across Switzerland. The platform is capable of handling large data volumes (up to 2.7 GB/day) without sacrificing performance.

- **Reliable Technology:** With a 99.9% availability rate, GIN operates through two redundant data centers, ensuring reliable service even under heavy loads. It is built using open-source software and includes automated bots to monitor data flow.
- **Multilingual Accessibility:** The platform is available in five languages—German, French, Italian, Romansh, and English—making it accessible to a broad range of users.

Local Natural Hazard Advisors (LNHA)

Analysis of major events in Switzerland underscored the need for local expertise as a crucial prerequisite for dealing successfully with incidents. Local authorities, civil staff units, and emergency authorities are particularly dependent on local expert knowledge in order to monitor and assess risk, interpret forecasts in the local context and trigger emergency measures (Buser et al. 2012). Given these needs and the critical role of local experts, a project was started in 2010 to formalise this process by building the capacity at the municipal civil level with local natural hazard advisors (LNHA). The main tasks of LNHA are to interpret warnings, use measurement data and observations in the local context and thus advise and support municipal and cantonal staff units and emergency services with their local expertise during events (Häberli et al. 2021). They also assist local authorities with emergency planning and management of natural hazard events.

LNHAs are provided training and support and are embedded within a larger action plan to optimise warning and alerts in the event of natural hazards under the OWARNA project (Wernli-Schärer et al. 2016). The basic training is modular and tailored to the needs of the cantons, covering topics such as meteorology, runoff and flood generation, geological mass movements, dealing with hazard data and documentation, occupational safety, information gathering, basic methodological techniques and staff work (Häberli et al. 2021). Each of Switzerland's three levels of government – Confederation, cantons and communes / municipalities have a specific role to play in relation to this training: the Confederation through FOEN supports the cantons by providing the training documents in German and French and dispensing basic training to the cantonal trainers, covering both technical and teaching aspects; the cantons receive financial assistance to help them customise and carry out their training; and the municipalities recruit LHNAs and integrate and organise them into the civil unit at the municipal level.

In addition to the basic training, the FOEN also hosts annual exchanges of experience covering recent events and the latest developments in forecasts and warnings. Since 2021, a total of 390 LNHA have been trained in 17 cantons across Switzerland (Häberli et al. 2021). However, there is no legal obligation to establish the LNHA role within individual communes and training takes place on a voluntary basis in the cantons. Therefore, the LNHA role is implemented differently in each canton, depending on topographical, geological and organisational factors and the canton's risk assessments.

8.4. Strengths, Gaps, and Recommendations

This section outlines key strengths, gaps, and good practices of DRR activities and warning systems that were identified during the course of the research analysis. Some limitations and challenges were explicitly identified by interviewees given their expertise and experience, while others were identified through analysis by the researchers. However, the authors refrain from citing direct quotes from the interviewees to protect participant confidentiality. Recommendations on how to address the gaps and challenges are also provided. Good practices are highlighted as examples that can be transferred and scaled to other DEMs and potential areas to collaborate with other DEMs are also discussed.

8.4.1. Strengths and Good Practices

1. Top down and Bottom-up integration and Local Natural Hazard Advisors

One of the most effective practices of the Swiss system is the system of bottom-up and top-down integration between federal, canton, and municipal levels. This is supported by data sharing through GIN (see pg.33). Through natural hazard advisors and municipal authorities, the downstream is involved in the process of observing and monitoring hazards, which does not happen in other countries. The presence of trained LNHA means that communes have an expert who can assist the authorities and, where appropriate, the emergency services in dealing with events. Often, training an LNHA triggers a process within the commune that goes far beyond event management. Better use is made of emergency plans, organisational measures are consolidated and there is a growing awareness of integrated risk management. Local Civil staff unit structures and processes are further developed and risk dialogue with the population is enhanced. For the cantonal authorities, LNHA act as 'sensors', flagging up the needs and challenges faced by communes and helping it to provide more effective support. Joint implementation of the three-tier 'Local natural hazard management' concept strengthens cooperation between the cantonal authorities and the communes, thereby consolidating the integrated system of hazard management.

2. Multi-hazard Warning Coordination through LAINAT and Single Official Voice

The Steering Committee Intervention against Natural Hazards (LAINAT) brings together the federal agencies and partners involved in developing and issuing natural hazard warnings. Under this umbrella, partners coordinate and collaborate closely with each other. This is a great strength of the Swiss DRM system and unique from the other DEMs, providing for coordination, collaboration, and harmonisation between all stakeholders and partners involved in the warning process. This is a particularly useful exemplar of implementing multi-sectoral, multi-hazard warnings and coordination during events of greater magnitudes, affecting more than one area, such as heavy precipitation with flood risk and debris flows. If an event involves more than one specialist agency, often a characteristic of multi-hazard and cascading events, joint warnings are issued on the basis of an agreed assessment of the hazard situation working through LAINAT and the Single Official Voice principle. When the relevant cantonal and municipal authorities communicate the warnings, the National Emergency Operations Centre (NEOC) is responsible for ensuring that the warnings issued to the public are coordinated, in terms of content and timing, with those issued to the authorities (Cantons/Municipalities).

Coordination of warnings also happens due to the Single Official Voice principle. Despite having many different public and private weather services and apps and warning challenges, all actors and agencies take a coordinated approach when issuing warnings using a harmonised scale of 1-5 for identifying the hazard category for each warning. It is recognisable as a warning issued by the Swiss government and publicised in an easily understandable and standardised format. The SRG and commercial licensed radio and television broadcasters are legally obliged to publish these warnings.

3. Joint Platform for Data Sharing: GIN

As the central information hub for natural hazards, the GIN platform is a powerful tool that improves the efficiency and effectiveness of natural hazard management between all relevant stakeholders. By centralizing data on a shared platform, it enhances coordination, integration, harmonisation and collaboration, supporting timely decision-making, disaster preparedness, and public safety, while offering personalized features and tailoring for diverse user needs. GIN allows for combined and user-friendly visualisation of the data in real time along with access to all warnings provided by all relevant entities. In addition, GIN strengthens the collaboration of the Swiss warning centres

by initiating cooperation such as integrated assessment and provision of joint bulletins in multi-hazard situations such as a combination of snowmelt, heavy rainfall and floods.

4. Multi-stakeholder Partnerships

Participatory multi-stakeholder partnerships at different levels have been developed in Switzerland that include the government, private sector, and to a lesser extent universities and the public. This includes the National Platform for Natural Hazards (PLANAT), the National Centre for Climate Services (NCCS), among other public-private partnerships. PLANAT is an extra-parliamentary commission with 18 members from national and cantonal authorities, universities, insurance companies, and the private sector. NCCS brings federal authorities together in a virtual network and serves as a knowledge hub for climate services. This type of collaboration provides a whole-of-society approach to disaster risk management and warning communication, however, more work is needed on incorporating other sectors of society as well as more robust public engagement.

5. Delineation of Roles and Responsibilities between Scales

The Swiss system, through its subsidiary principle, provides clear delineation of roles and responsibilities at each administrative level (national, cantonal, and municipal). For example, hazard maps, land use planning, and emergency action plans are required at the municipal level and shared (and approved) by the cantonal authorities. This is a very productive way to not only ensure that roles and responsibilities at all relevant administrative levels and for all stakeholders are clearly defined and outlined, but also to provide the necessary support and capacity building to effectively address prevailing and expected risks and hazards. Joint planning and coordination of DRR activities by all stakeholders has also helped to reduce duplication and redundancy between scales of work, although this does vary from canton to canton.

6. Risk-informed Planning and Hazard Maps

Swiss municipalities, with the support of federal and cantonal offices have hazard maps covering flooding, rockfalls, landslides and snow avalanches. They serve as a baseline for developing or adapting land use plans or zoning. The relevant legislation specifies how the zones are to be used and if construction permits can be issued. Additionally, online platforms such as Naturgefahren-Radar or Schutz vor Naturgefahren provide information on natural risks to buildings relevant for building owners as well as for architects and planners. In terms of risk assessment and planning, the national disaster risk assessment [Disaster and Emergencies in Switzerland](#) uses a multi-hazard and whole-of-society approach by analysing 44 hazards in the domains of nature, technology, and society jointly with experts from the public and private sector and with representatives of academia, insurers and associations. The results inform national preparedness planning, exercises and strategy development. In addition, sub-national entities conduct their own risk assessment and preparedness planning, as they are the main actors responsible in the context of civil protection and disaster management. Furthermore, conducting risk assessment and preparedness planning at community level is also important for tackling the risks as close to their source as possible. The flood-risk research initiative offers different tools to assess damages to buildings due to flooding (damage simulator) or to visualise the damage that flooding could cause. The public can contribute their own photos of past events to a nationwide repository. Risk overviews of gravitational natural hazards are created by overlaying the hazard assessment with land use plans, whereby the affected assets are identified. This shows, for example, whether a person, a building or a section of a road would be affected by a landslide or by flooding. A uniform national reference framework for hail hazards data, including information on hail frequency, hailstone sizes and return periods was developed in private-public-partnership with insurance companies. Hazard maps also show the distribution and severity of potential

surface runoff risk. It covers the whole of Switzerland, both developed and undeveloped regions, and is publicly accessible online.

7. Multilingual Web Platforms

Given Switzerland's diverse population, multilingual needs are well-served by authorities and warning channels. All of the warning apps and websites generally display information in German, French, Italian, Romansh, and English.

8. Post-event Evaluation and Analysis

The Post-Event Review Capability (PERC) was developed to provide evaluation, analysis, and review of major events. PERC is a flexible method that provides research on and independent reviews of large flood and wildfire events. It seeks to answer questions related to aspects of flood resilience, flood risk management, and disaster intervention. It looks at what went well, as well as opportunities for improvement, and results in a set of actionable recommendations to build back better and to reduce future risks.

8.4.2. Gaps and Challenges

1. While the approach of integrating bottom-up and top-down coordination and data-sharing through LAINAT and GIN between federal agencies, cantonal authorities, and communes are quite effective, the level of harmonisation between cantons and municipalities is very variable. Depending on experience with previous disasters, capacities, resources, and interests, some cantons and municipalities do not have the same level of local expertise and monitoring of hazards. Additionally, while the concept of natural hazard advisors is a clear and unique strength of the Swiss system, it has been identified that not all cantons have active or committed natural hazard advisors. Conducting a survey of natural hazard advisors across each canton the country and reviewing differences or gaps in their capacities would be a necessary first step towards harmonising this approach across cantons and the country. The differing implementation of LHNAs across cantons was raised as a challenge also by Häberli and colleagues' study (2021).
2. The researchers note the strength of Swiss authorities in dealing with natural hazards and climate extremes, however, the predominant focus has been narrowly on weather and floods. While there is increasing attention to mass movements like landslides and rock falls, national landslide warnings are still under development. Working with DEM 3 and landslide experts from the Campania region can provide important insights on how to design and implement landslide warnings. Furthermore, collaborating with DEM 3 as well as DEM 6 can provide learnings on warning coverage for other risks, including environmental, biological, and other natural and non-natural risks.
3. The upstream warning process is strong in Switzerland, but there is a lack of engagement with the downstream--public (users). Currently, the public must download the MeteoSwiss or Alertswiss app or visit the Natural Hazards Platform in order to find information about warnings and recommended measures and actions. It would be important to include users in the design and decision-making process of warnings through public engagement and first mile co-created solutions. Greater inclusion of users' was also identified by Appenzellar and colleagues (2024) in their study of understanding the impacts of MeteoSwiss warnings. Additionally, there is currently no cell broadcasting capabilities in the country. Further engagement with the public through disaster risk education and awareness campaigns, preparedness and mitigation exercises will help to improve how the public receives and acts on warnings. Integrating a first-mile approach is necessary to better the Swiss hazard management and warning system. While there is a dearth of focus on public engagement and education campaigns, MeteoSwiss has launched a pilot

project to evaluate the social impact of its warnings, evaluating social impact and social verification (Appenzellar et al. 2024).

- There are many different apps and web platforms for the public to use for receiving warning information about hazards, including the civil protection run, AlertSwiss app and website, MeteoSwiss app and website, the Natural Hazard Platform, and private channels. It is, however, crucial that these platforms share consistent information and streamline warnings and alerts. While the MeteoSwiss and Natural Hazard Platform have similar hazards listed on their websites, the AlertSwiss website has a completely different structure with different headings that are not streamlined with the two other platforms. Furthermore, textual and visual descriptions also differ on the AlertSwiss app and website and it does not have the national alert levels that coincide with those listed on MeteoSwiss and Natural Hazard Platform. Furthermore, while it was noted that the AlertSwiss app provides warning information for specific hazards nationally or in a specific area, it is important that what this coincides with hazard warning information on the Natural Hazard Platform as well as MeteoSwiss. For example, as evidenced by the photos below taken on the same day, the Alertswiss website has had the same ongoing warning for a danger of rockfall, landslide, and debris flow in Brienz / Brinzauls in Canton GR. Whereas on the MeteoSwiss and Natural Hazard Platform sites there were no such warnings for the same region but rather yellow-level avalanche warnings. Warning messaging, especially on official channels must be consistent, clear, and accurate in order to ensure legitimacy and trust in sources and information. Given that AlertSwiss is operated by the same partners of the other channels and under LAINAT, it is important that partners work together to streamline warnings. It would also be beneficial to conduct further research on how users use different apps/websites and which they find useful and which are confusing or redundant—questions thus remain on which warning communication channels are most used. While the study by MeteoSwiss (Appenzellar et al. 2024) found that 40% of people mentioned using the MeteoSwiss app as their source for warnings, there is a gap in identifying the other 60% of the population as to which warning channel they use.

Figure 15: Screenshot of warnings displayed AlertSwiss on 17/02/25 (Source: Federal Office for Civil Protection [Alert Swiss](#))

Figure 16: Screenshot of warnings displayed MeteoSwiss on 17/02/25 (Source: [MeteoSwiss](#))

8.4.3. Recommendations and Opportunities for Collaboration with other DEMs

1. Whilst the subsidiary principle ensures local interpretation and contextualisation of risks and measures, it would be important to also implement some oversight throughout each level of governance (federal, canton, and municipality) and provide downstream support and capacity-building to ensure that each level is able to carry out their specific roles and responsibilities. For example, the mandate of acting on warnings lies with municipalities, this has left the timely communication of warning and necessary measures largely up to municipalities without any checks or oversight in the case of inaction. This can lead to disasters, such as the July 2021 flooding in the canton of Neuchâtel and the surrounding Lake area, where the cantonal authorities alerted the municipalities and gave them a 3-day advance notice of imminent flooding, but the municipalities failed to warn residents and visitors until it was too late. This flood event and issues around warning campers and visitors have been examined in the BAFU post-event report (figure 17 below). Greater harmonisation between the scales of governance, especially at the downstream level of municipalities would help to ensure that authorities' can warn, act and respond in a timely manner.
2. It would behoove Switzerland to join the rest of Europe in providing cell broadcasting technologies for warnings. This has been identified as a need by those interviewed and discussions are in progress to implement cell broadcasting, while funding issues constrain the implementation. Through some projects, however, there are specific areas, (Steffisburg) that have private-run SMS-alert warnings that are provided to first responders locally. Learning from all other DEMs can provide helpful information on best practices and what to do when implementing these technologies.

Figure 17: Post-event report of July 2021 Floods depicting flooding around Lake Neuchâtel (Source: BAFU shared with lead author)

3. Warning and alert level decision-making in Switzerland are generally based on a threshold system. While there are advantages and disadvantages between threshold-based warnings vs impact-based warnings, especially given the hazard type, it is important to examine which systems work best for multi-hazard risks and for which contexts, accounting for risk, exposure, and vulnerabilities such as the season, population numbers, and risk experience of those affected. For example, if there is heavy precipitation and flood forecasted during the summer with many tourists and campers in a populated area, such as Lake Neuchâtel, issuing a higher level warning might ensure appropriate responses from local authorities and the population, whereas if the same weather was forecasted in the winter in an area where residents are more familiar with such hazards, it would not necessitate a higher level warning. This was explicitly mentioned by interviewees referencing the July 2021 floods in Lake Neuchâtel, where authorities and the public alike did not expect the lake to be flooded even though it was forecasted. While impact-based warnings have their own advantages and disadvantages, it is important to have some level of contextual factors considered during warning decision-making, especially considering populations that are not accustomed to hazard events. DEM 6 (Iceland) and DEM 9 (UK) has a wealth of experience in impact-based warning decision-making and targeting of specific populations (e.g. tourists) taking into account exposure and vulnerability risks. There is also research on impact-based warnings, its effective and evaluation in DEM 9 from UK MET office that Switzerland can draw upon.
4. Learning from DEMs, specifically DEM 3, DEM 6, and DEM 9 can provide lessons on various ways to have deeper engagement with the public. Examples include volunteer services, public simulation and exercises, open days, and disaster risk education and awareness campaigns. For national level campaigns and disaster risk education see sections on DEM 3; for regional and

hazard-based examples of public engagement, see section on DEM 6 (Seydisfjörður, Iceland) and DEM 9 (Dorset, UK).

5. While post-event reviews model are part and parcel of Swiss disaster policy, there is a need to also incorporate feedback from the public on the effectiveness, quality, and timeliness of warnings and actions by authorities. Greater engagement with users and having multi-channel feedback mechanisms, such as those implemented by DEM 6 (Iceland) following the landslide events of 2020 can provide better models of evaluating warning processes, opening communication channels between government authorities and the public. MeteoSwiss's social verification pilot project and flash polls is a great first step in this direction.
6. While collaboration is strong between government authorities and the private sector, there is a need for further collaboration with the public via universities and scientific communities. Collaborations with the private sector and public-private partnerships, including with Mobiliarlab and Geopraevent, have filled key gaps in the DRM system by drawing on these partnerships to provide expertise and development of warning and alarm systems, risk assessments, and hazard mapping (Wabbels and Bezzola 2022; Weingartner et al. 2024). However, much of this collaboration with the private sector has focused on flood and avalanche warning and detection systems. There is, however, now greater emphasis given to landslide and rockfall risks, especially in high risk areas. Collaboration with other partners in the HuT can provide practical insights on covering multi-hazards. Learning from DEM 3 (Italy) and DEM 6 (Iceland), for example, on how government engages with researchers and universities through scientific councils for multi-hazard risks could provide important lessons and opportunities for further engagement.

9. DEM 6 East Fjords, Iceland

9.1. Overview and background

This section provides an overview of how disaster risk governance and management is organised in Iceland between the national and local levels. While the overview covers all phases of the DRM cycle, the focus is predominantly on the prevention and communication of natural hazards and climate / weather driven disasters. The natural hazards that are potentially disastrous in Iceland and that are affected by climate change, include:

- Meteorological hazards
- Hydrological floods
- Landslides and rockfalls
- Avalanches
- Volcanic activity

This section brings together a review of grey literature and DRM organizations websites, on-site observations, and 20 stakeholder interviews conducted with national, regional (East Fjords) and local (municipal) stakeholders from the Civil Protection system, National Meteorological Office, volcanic activity experts, regional development organisation and with locals who experienced the catastrophic landslide event in Seyðisfjörður in 2020. Interviews were conducted in 5-6/2024 (mostly individual, some in pairs/ small groups).

Case Study: Seyðisfjörður, East Fjords

The focus of the study was the East Fjords region, where devastating landslides in 2020 affected the town of Seyðisfjörður (Figure 18). As numerous landslides occurred over the duration of three days, the area of evacuations and areas where people were asked to have caution were expanded in many steps as the situation unfolded, in some ways causing confusion and decision-making delays, according to interviewees.

This crisis revealed gaps in the information provided to the locals before, during and after the events (see, Bartsch, 2024). One main gap identified included that the public were not aware of how the system works, and where the responsibilities lay resulting in confusion on who needs to be listened to and who to contact. The locals were left unsure of many aspects of the crisis most notably regarding actions as well as prevention and preparedness to possible future events. As a response to these gaps, several actions were taken:

- Town hall meetings were organised based on community concerns following the event to address the situation and the needs of the residents of Seydisfjordur. Citizen town hall meetings provided information and updates on various issues, such as IMO discussing avalanche hazard/risk assessments to the population. While these meetings were held in Icelandic, the proceedings of the meeting were translated and published in English and Polish afterwards to be more accessible to the international community in the town. The town hall events supported two-way communication the post-disaster, which reflects a growing emphasis in the Icelandic DRM in recent years, i.e. (i) helping public servants from different agencies that are involved from the onset of the event (e.g., the municipality, the local chief of police, the temporary civil protection service center and the local coordination group for psychosocial support) to better understand the needs of the residents, and (ii) to provide

expert information and consultation to the residents from different sectors, usually from IMO and the Natural Catastrophe Fund in Iceland. After the 2020 landslide event, for example, the IMO avalanche and landslide specialists participated in several meetings. Eventually, the long-term planning and recovery tasks are transferred to the local agencies, and the municipality took over managing the town hall meetings.

Figure 18: Damage from Landslides in 2020 in Seydisfjordur (Source: [IMO 2021](#))

- A social resilience study (Halldórsdóttir, 2023) measured the social cohesion of the locals and the findings were communicated to the residents and other stakeholders, such as local businesses, to help recovery after the natural hazard event. The government also set up an initiative to support local businesses after the events. These findings have demonstrated the value of supporting socio psychological and economic needs of the locals, particularly in the response to the situation in Reykjanes peninsula. Volcanic eruptions in the peninsula in 2024 affected the Grindavik municipality in many ways, including the possible permanent evacuation of Grindavík town that was destroyed by earthquakes and lava flows in November and December 2023.
- In Iceland, changes in frost-thawing cycles and permafrost have made it more challenging to forecast land surface movements and landslides. However, following the landslide events in Seyðisfjörður with the heavy rain for several consecutive days and subsequent melting of the snow, new geospatial monitoring instruments were installed upon the request from the community. Also protective measures, including building defenses for landslides and avalanches have also been developed in the area.

9.2. Disaster Risk Management and Warning System

The Department of Civil Protection and Emergency Management (DCPEM), under the Ministry of Justice, is the supervising and collaborative coordinating body of civil protection and emergency management in Iceland ([Civil Protection Act No 82/2008](#)). The CP operates on two levels in Iceland, both at state and local levels that address the different stages of the DRM cycle (see figure 19). The National Commissioner of the Icelandic Police (NCIP) in Reykjavik is the head of national civil protection coordination and command in emergency situations. During an emergency a National Crisis Command Center (NCCC) is activated if needed and coordinated by the NCIP in case of emergency.

Figure 19. The organizational chart of Civil Protection in the DRM system (DRM phases on the right-side column) (Source: NCIP).

On the local level, Iceland is divided into nine regional Police Districts. The local chief of police is in charge and responsible for response measures when an adverse event occurs within the district. Operations at the local level are managed at the Local Crisis Coordination Center. The 21 Civil Protection Committees in Iceland, which are located around the country, are responsible for hazard and risk analysis, contingency planning and emergency drills.

The Iceland Meteorological Office (IMO) sits in the Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate, and has a central role in the disaster risk management system in Iceland given that most disastrous events are caused or affected by natural hazards. The IMO has a remarkably broad range of expertise in the field of natural hazards and it conducts research and provides expert services on fields of meteorology, hydrology, glaciology, climatology, seismology and volcanology. The IMO's tasks include:

“1. to monitor natural hazards and issue warnings and forecasts of imminent danger caused by weather and weather-related factors, earthquakes, volcanic eruptions, floods, landslides and avalanches; ... 13. to carry out risk assessments due to natural disasters at the request of the civil protection authorities or other authorities.” (Article 3, Act no. 70/2008 on Icelandic Meteorological Office (IMO))

that are further specified in terms of the warnings as follows:

“Care shall be taken to ensure that warnings are presented in a clear and unambiguous manner. The Meteorological Office shall communicate its warnings without delay, including to the Civil Protection Department of the National Commissioner of Police ...”, and other relevant actors including the media and the air traffic control (Article 9, [Act no. 142/2004 on meteorological forecasting](#)).

Collaboration between the organizations in the DRM system is the cornerstone of a well-functioning warning system in Iceland, and is secured by both formal and informal arrangements and communication. A security council coordinates the interaction between the ministries on national level civil protection issues relevant for both ministries. The cooperation between different government agencies on DRM is also legally binding in terms of providing information and assistance, for instance, for risk assessments and contingency plans (Articles 15, 16, 18, Civil Protection Act No 82/2008). However, as often stated in the interviews, the cooperation between relevant parties in Iceland works well also due to cultural and contextual factors, such as the relatively small size of the population, and groups of professionals that are familiar with each other, and often manage extreme and multiple natural hazards requiring cross-sectoral expertise.

Iceland has evolved the development and implementation of DRM systems following crisis events. For instance, in the aftermath of the catastrophic avalanche events in 1995 in the Westfjords region that caused 34 deaths (see, e.g., Bernhardsdóttir, 2001), avalanche and landslide legislation was renewed, with new funding for preventive and protective measures established, and a new risk monitoring system activated (see, [Act no. 49/1997 on landslides and avalanches](#)). The Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate states that *“The work on risk assessment for avalanches has been a model for assessing risk posed by other natural hazards, including floods and volcanic eruptions.”* (Ministry of the Environment, Energy and Climate, nd) which was confirmed in the interviews of the related agencies.

The Eyjafjallajökull volcanic eruptions in 2010 that led to major international aviation air traffic disruptions drove changes in the aviation warnings systems and processes, whilst also highlighting the need to address the psycho-social effects of disasters in the recovery phase of the DRM cycle by starting local branches of the Red Cross (RC) around Iceland instead of the previous single unit. Furthermore, COVID-pandemic in 2020-2021 changed the understanding on what type of expertise is needed in the CP to address the more complex crises, namely, broadening the focus from the response phase to more equally cover the different phases of the crisis management. As one of the interviewees from the civil protection describes it: *“it became simply too challenging to confront all the new and unexpected events one after the other, and then return to daily tasks”*.

Prior to the pandemic, in 2019, management and communication with civil protection changed to keep all relevant actors updated in a timely manner. Since then, regular civil protection meetings led by the NCIP, or NCCC in emergency situations, have been opened to *all relevant* local agencies, including, the second and third respondents i.e. the search and rescue units (S&R), the RC in Iceland, the energy infrastructure agency *Landsnet*, the emergency line (112), the road and coastal agencies, and the telephone operator. Later, COVID changed the practice of meeting on-site, to on-line meetings which increased the accessibility and inclusivity on risk and response assessment.

Warnings were previously based on climatological thresholds as markers for single meteorological events, but single event warnings were not enough to communicate the risks to vulnerable groups. For example, simultaneous strong wind and low temperature conditions in summer cause a risk to sheep farmers in the East, but interpreting the two climatological thresholds together by the users was considered too demanding. The current warning system was launched in 2017 and is based on the likelihood and societal impact of a hazardous event reach the public and various

stakeholder. The forecasters now address various societal and meteorological factors when issuing warnings which demand contextual local knowledge, e.g. the month in winter when people are in the mountains hunting birds, when the camper van season starts, or during lambing season.

9.3. Governance Structure and MHWS

9.3.1. Multi-hazard Warnings in Iceland

The key responsible actors in the DRM system are the Civil Protection and the IMO. Table 3 lists their key inputs, identified in the interviews, to each of the phases of the DRM cycle. In addition, several other expert organizations and individuals provide input to the system that are presented in the text after the table.

Table 3. Roles of IMO and NCIP throughout the DRM/warning cycle (developed by second author)

DRM Cycle	Iceland
Risk assessment (RA); Preparedness & prevention	IMO: all natural hazard risk assessments; in collaboration with relevant agencies, e.g. the Road Administration to assess the risks for road infrastructure DCPEM: all CP risk assessments and contingency/ emergency plans; informed by the IMO RAs; local RAs and plans in cooperation with the Local Civil Protection Committees and the local community
Detection & observation; Monitoring	IMO: all hazards + UiO: volcanic hazards + Snow observers (IMO): avalanche and landslides seasonally DCPEM: hazards addressed in CP plans
Forecast; Decision-making on warning; Dissemination & communication	IMO: all hazards DCPEM: hazards addressed in CP plans + Dissemination by all relevant agencies (see section 9.3.2)
Response	IMO: hazard expert in the situation room DCPEM: hazards addressed in CP plans Other relevant actors in the emergency response incl. S&R, RC, etc.
Evaluation & feedback	IMO: regular or needs based evaluation of the risk assessments, contingency/ emergency plans; citizen and user feedback is collected on all services DCPEM: regular or needs based evaluation of all the CP risk assessments and all contingency/ emergency plans Civil Protection Committees: regular or needs based evaluation of local CP risk assessments and contingency/ emergency plans

The IMO conducts risk assessments on natural hazards as requested by the government. Products generated include hazard zoning maps (currently on avalanches and landslides and hydrological floods addressing risks to critical infrastructure and people as per residential housing and commercial buildings (avalanches and landslides) and outdoor recreational users on ski areas (avalanches) (see, IMO, nd (a,b,c)). Volcanic risk assessment in Iceland is an on-going

collaborative project that Gosvá started in 2012 for which the main output is the Icelandic Volcano Catalogue (see, IMO, 2025a) that is managed in collaboration with the IMO, University of Iceland and the DCPEM.

There are three types of Civil Protection contingency/ emergency plans: (i) National plans, for emergencies of national extent, e.g. pandemics; and specific agencies, e.g. natural hazard emergency plan for tourist service (NCIP, 2018); (ii) General plans for Civil Protection district that cover various hazards including the less likely and/or severe natural hazards for the region; (iii) Specific plans for Civil Protection district on specific hazards or events that are of high severity such as volcanic eruptions in Mýrdalsjökull.

The IMO carries out monitoring, analysis, forecasting and warnings on most natural hazards. Local snow observers are employed seasonally by the IMO to provide local landslide and avalanche observation, detection and monitoring. The observers have a dual role of (i) IMO employee, (ii) trusted / well known person in the community, (often) with several roles, e.g. police officer, local council member, local business owner etc. The department of civil protection and emergency management (DCPEM) participates in the monitoring and issuing warnings for the hazards that are currently considered relevant for the civil protection, namely, hazardous weather events, avalanches, landslides and volcanic activity. The seismic activity and hydrological floods, for example, are currently not considered to cause severe damage to the population according to an interviewee in the CP.

Two daily meetings are held to assess risks related to natural hazards and weather, information is exchanged and necessary actions deliberated. Internal meetings are held at 10 AM every morning at IMO between the meteorologist on duty, avalanche specialist on duty, landslide specialist on duty and natural hazard specialist (seismic activity, river floods) on duty to assess weather and potential upcoming risks. The on-duty specialists on meteorology and natural hazards are always located in the same room, which eases the communication also beyond the daily meetings. Information meetings are held at 2 PM every day with all stakeholders including DCPM, IMO hazard groups, IMO weather (incl. evening weather news person); depending on the situation also mayors, fire brigade, road authority, landlines and other infrastructure, and news agencies. For the volcanic activity monitoring and hazard assessment, there is a separate weekly meeting with the DCPM, IMO and the University of Iceland (UoI) volcanic expert representative.

A decision to issue a weather warning is made based on measurements of factors such as precipitation, wind, temperature, water level in rivers and boreholes, sea level, deformation of soil etc.; weather forecasts; threshold levels in some cases; anticipated societal impact (e.g., how much population is affected) and always on expert opinion as well. Decisions on evacuations are always made by more than one person.

The warnings on natural hazards are under constant evaluation. They are issued based on the daily monitoring meetings if not earlier/ later by the specialist on duty in IMO unless the situation is more uncertain and then an additional meeting would be called. The NCIP is in charge of the civil protection alerts, in consultation with the relevant regional police commissioner. The accountability for warnings lies hence with IMO and Civil Protection, both locally and nationally.

When deciding on issuing a red weather alert, the IMO contacts the DCPM directly via phone to start aligning their contingency plans. In case the person on duty does not answer immediately, IMO calls 112.

Response

The Civil Protection is responsible for calling in appropriate actors in all hazard situations requiring emergency response, i.e. activation of civil protection response plans according to the emergency level / phase:

- 1) uncertainty level / phase, where communication with stakeholders is started and hazard monitoring and assessment increased;
- 2) alert level / phase, where preventive measures are taken locally and the communication is broadened to cover broader public and warning information on restrictions and recommendations;
- 3) emergency level / phase, where active measures are taken to ensure security, save lives and avoid loss and damage.

In practice, the emergency responses are handled with the resources at the relevant geographic / governance level. Should the emergency escalate from the local level, then operations are managed through the Local Crisis Coordination Center (LCCC,) and if outside support is needed they contact the national crisis coordination center (NCCC) that provides the required support. The LCCC contacts the Red Cross if there is a need for opening a mass emergency shelter, which is more often needed for tourists than locals in Iceland. In any emergency phase, it is always the Local Chief of Police/ the LCCC that decides on measures taken. They may receive information and guidance on the regular on-line Civil Protection meetings, for example on coordination on additional resources for the emergency site, such as specialist on different types of search and rescue (Search and Rescue (SaR) needs (avalanche SaR, airplane SaR, dog patrols).

9.3.2. Communication, Dissemination, and Delivery of Warnings

The IMO issues public and aviation warnings on meteorological and natural hazards (see Table 5). IMO shares the warnings on their webpage and social media. Depending on the type and severity of the warning the IMO distributes it directly to Civil protection, and to news agencies, and communicates directly also with other relevant agencies in a targeted way, e.g. in terms of icy conditions the road network agency, hospitals, and municipal maintenance who all need different information to decide their actions. In case of avalanche and landslide warnings, IMO contacts the local police and road network agency directly, and in case of volcanic hazards, it calls stakeholders in aviation directly. Aviation SIGMETS (Significant Meteorological Information) are coordinated between countries.

The IMO weather warnings are disseminated through meteoalarm.org and WMO warning portals to various end users such as google and Weather Company. All relevant IMO warnings are disseminated through the Road Authority website (Fig.20) and Safe Travel App and web pages for tourists in Iceland (Fig.21), and through insurance companies to their clients.

Figure 20: Screenshot of Road agency Site, providing traffic information, road conditions, warnings, and adverse road safety related weather conditions (Source: <https://umferdin.is/en/definitions>, visited 12.1.2025).

Figure 21: Safetravel website and app run by ICE-SAR, geared towards travellers (see <https://www.icesar.com/>) (Source: <https://safetravel.is/>, visited 12.1.2025)

When a civil protection emergency level is activated it is communicated through the DCPEM website, with a press release, and through social media. The cell-broadcasting / location-based SMS alerts may also be issued. DCPEM also shares the IMO warnings and other information from IMO on social media. The DCPEM social media accounts are one of the most visited accounts in Iceland. On local level, the local police prefers to use social media, thus far mainly [Facebook](#), for sharing warnings and hazard information for the local communities

Municipalities share warnings on their websites and provide provisional local information. Local communities' own [Facebook groups \(e.g. in Seyðisfjorður\)](#) typically reshare warnings and hazard information actively. Tourist operators are important in sharing the warnings and communicating the risks to the tourists.

National broadcasting company (RÚV), radio and private news agencies that locals follow are the key media disseminating the warnings. RÚV has a legal obligation to pass on hazard information and news. The RÚV and the private broadcasting company Sýn provide the most urgent warnings on their news every hour. IMO media communication is very active, including being actively interviewed in the news to provide explanations on what the weather means for daily life.

Type of Warning and Contents of Messaging

Meteorological warnings (Fig. 22) are impact based and assess the risk by the likelihood and societal impact of a hazardous event (Fig. 23). Landslides and flood warnings are in development and currently showing hazard threshold-based information (Fig. 25). Avalanche warnings are impact and risk based (Fig. 24). Earthquake maps and volcanic aviation color code (Figure 26 and 27) are hazard based with provisional information on the impacts. Each hazard has its own warning system, and there is no single system that includes everything. However, since IMO issues all warnings on natural hazards, cascading and compound effects for instance are more easily considered than if the warnings were issued in separate institutes. For instance, warnings are issued on increased risk of rockfall during periods of high seismic activity.

Inclusivity of the warning system

Warnings are provided in Icelandic and English depending on the website. Citizens can give feedback on the system through social media and it is evaluated. A particular challenge in reaching all people with the warnings is the tourists who do not know where to seek information on the warnings. One of the interviewees proposed that the SMS alert system could be taken in use for this purpose, to alert people when their mobile location crosses to a hazard prone area. For example the warning for an eruption at Hekla volcano could be very short notice and many tourists in the summer are walking in the eruption zone which is highly dangerous (and not only in CP alert / emergency phase), or a tourist may reach a spot of rarely occurring hazards such as sneaker waves in the popular tourist spot Black Sand beach in Vík where there are infographics on site that people don't often look at. However, SMS alerts coverage has not been 100% effective, according to a number of interviewees, i.e. some people within the geo-fenced area do not receive the alerts or receive them too late. However, this is consistent with the literature on warning standard of practice which notes that while mobile technologies like cell broadcasting play a significant role in rapid transmission of messages, it is important to have multiple channels of communication and not solely relying on one dissemination method (Taylor and Rokhideh 2024). As such, interviewees highlighted that in emergency situations, their social networks and relationships within the community helped cover this gap to some degree, i.e. people communicated with each other about the alerts and notified those who did not receive an alert.

Figure 22: Screenshot of IMO weather warning map illustrating a yellow warning on gale, rain and wind conditions for 8 of the 11 forecasting regions (Source: <https://en.vedur.is/alerts>, visited 11.1.2025)

Impact Matrix of the Icelandic Meteorological Office

	Minimal or no hazard. No damage likely.
	Medium or high likelihood of medium impact weather which can have localized affects. This weather could affect travels between different areas of Iceland. The weather is potentially hazardous if precautions are not taken and can cause damages or accidents. Yellow warnings are fairly common and should not cause systematic disruptions to transport, public services or infrastructure. Yellow warning can also indicate the possibility of very severe, high impact weather 3-5 days ahead.
	Medium or high likelihood of medium or high impact weather. This weather can will likely have short term impact on transportation, public services and infrastructure. This weather may cause damages or accidents. Can be a threat to lives if precautions are not take. Amber warnings happen every year. Show caution and make the necessary arrangements.
	High likelihood of extreme weather causing high societal impact. Extreme weather with very hazardous conditions is forecasted. This weather can cause threat to life and property. High likelihood of nationwide disruptions to transportation, public services and infrastructure. Pay close attention to all available information and updates from IMO and Civil Protection.

Figure 23: IMO’s Impact matrix of color-coded alert levels for weather warnings (Source: IMO, nd (e)).

Figure 24: Screenshot of Avalanche warning bulletins (Eastfjords) (Source: vedur.is/avalanches/forecast/east_fjords, visited 11.1.2025).

Figure 25: Screenshot of flood risk map, noting also that the spatial illustration of the risk on the map is currently unavailable (Source: <https://en.vedur.is/#tab=hydro>, visited 12.1.2025).

Figure 26: Screenshot of aviation warnings for volcanic risks for aviation illustrating a yellow level for the Reykjanes volcanic system (Source: <https://en.vedur.is/earthquakes-and-volcanism/volcanoes/>, visited 1.11.2025).

Table 4: Hazard Warning Table developed by authors

Hazard	Warning/ Emergency Is covered by the emergency plan, who issues the warning?	Info provided Action, Risks Impact, Forecast, monitoring, etc.	Communication Through which channel(s)?	Scale (municipal, district, national level, etc.)	Timing of Warning When is the warning issued?
Meteoro- logical hazards	<p>IMO issues warnings</p> <p>DCPEM issues CP alerts</p> <p>Road safety warnings issued by the Road Authority</p> <p>Covered in local emergency plans</p>	<p>CAP OASIS 1.2 standard for weather (green, yellow, orange, red); 5 day warnings for each local forecast area (11 in total)</p> <p>Impact-based</p>	<p>IMO: webpage, social media, direct communication</p> <p>DCPEM: website, press release, social media; SMS alert according to the emergency plan</p> <p>Road Authority website; Safe Travel App and website</p>	<p>IMO: inter-national and national and local</p>	<p>IMO updates warning map daily</p> <p>CP alerts issued according to the emergency plan</p>

<p>Hydro-logical floods</p>	<p>IMO issues warnings</p> <p>DCPEM issues CP alerts</p> <p>Flood risks covered in the local emergency plans</p> <p>Covered in local and special emergency plans</p>	<p>Colour coded warnings for floods are under development</p>	<p>IMO: webpage, social media, direct communication</p> <p>DCPEM: website, press release, social media; SMS alert according to the emergency plan</p>	<p>Local</p>	<p>IMO updates warning map daily</p> <p>CP alerts issued according to the emergency plan</p>
<p>Landslide</p>	<p>IMO issues warnings</p> <p>DCPEM issues CP alerts</p> <p>Covered in the local emergency plans</p>	<p>Colour coded warnings for landslides are under development</p>	<p>IMO: webpage, social media, direct communication</p> <p>DCPEM: website, press release, social media; SMS alert according to the emergency plan</p>	<p>Local</p>	<p>IMO issues warnings when certain thresholds are reached</p> <p>CP alerts issued according to the emergency plan</p>
<p>Earth-quake & Rockfall</p>	<p>IMO issues warnings</p> <p>Covered in the local and special emergency plans</p>	<p>Earthquake early warning maps (IMO, nd (d))</p> <p>Warnings on increased of rockfalls are issued during periods of high seismic activity</p> <p>Hazard-based</p>	<p>IMO: webpage, social media</p>	<p>Local</p>	<p>Early warning maps updated when activity is detected</p>

<p>Avalanche</p>	<p>IMO issues warnings</p> <p>DCPEM issues CP alerts</p> <p>Avalanche risks covered in the local emergency plans</p> <p>Covered in the local emergency plans</p>	<p>Five stage color code for regional avalanche forecasting (European standard).</p> <p>Impact-based</p>	<p>IMO: webpage, social media, direct communication</p> <p>DCPEM: website, press release, social media; SMS alert according to the emergency plan</p>	<p>National and Local</p>	<p>IMO updates warning map daily</p> <p>CP alerts issued according to the emergency plan</p>
<p>Volcanic activity</p>	<p>IMO issues warnings for aviation.</p> <p>DCPEM issues CP alerts</p> <p>Covered in the local and special emergency plans</p>	<p>Four level aviation colour code (standard of International Civil Aviation Organisation (ICAO)) indicating the volcanic activity, accompanied with notifications in case of changes in activity including details on the hazard and the possible impacts. Criteria based on specific thresholds for each volcano.</p>	<p>IMO website; social media, direct communication</p> <p>Iceland Volcano Catalogue website (Fig 28)</p> <p>DCPEM: website, press release, social media; SMS alert according to the emergency plan</p>	<p>National</p>	<p>Risk map updated daily; CP alerts issued according to the emergency plan</p>

9.4. Strengths, Gaps, and Recommendations

This section outlines key strengths, gaps, and good practices of DRR activities and warning systems that were identified during the course of the research analysis. Some limitations and challenges were explicitly identified by interviewees given their expertise and experience, while others were identified through analysis by the researchers. However, the authors refrain from citing direct quotes from the interviewees to protect participant confidentiality. Recommendations on how to address the gaps and challenges are also provided. Good practices are highlighted as examples that can be transferred and scaled to other DEMs and potential areas to collaborate with other DEMs are also discussed.

9.4.1. Strengths and Good Practices

1. Adaptability, local expertise and cross-sectoral collaboration

The DRM system in Iceland functions well for various reasons, including the highly educated experts that are used to working with changing and challenging hazardous events and across organizations, the experience from working in different collaborating organizations i.e. having the view from inside and outside, and the adaptability of practices that is learned from experience of dealing with the unexpected hazards.

The warning system builds on the low threshold communication between organizations on risk assessments, warning decision-making and warning communication. It has demonstrated over several examples how the system is revised actively when new types of risks or vulnerabilities emerge. Most importantly, the evaluation and revision of the system is based on collaboration with international networks (on weather warnings), and national and local experts, and with sensitivity to the local experiences and needs.

2. Preparedness on expected and unexpected multi-hazard risks

Iceland's DRM system which includes IMO, NCIP, and other relevant partners have amassed a wealth of knowledge and practice on dealing with many hazards and risks. Preparedness by local risk assessments, contingency plans and emergency drills between emergency authorities is highly developed in Iceland. Another strength of the system is that less prominent hazards, such as sea water rise and earthquakes, are observed, monitored and analysed. Meteorological warnings have high visibility in society and the impact-based colour-scale on danger is better understood than the previously used single climatological threshold warnings used previously. These are shared with road-authorities and Safe Travel to provide clear messages on warnings, providing map-based illustration and alert messages.

3. Post-event Review and Community Engagement after Disasters

One of the key strengths the authors identified is engagement with communities after devastating events. After disasters, such as the landslides in Seyðisfjörður in 2020, multiple meetings are held between authorities and communities to address the concerns and needs of affected residents. Assessing the needs of residents is a core component of work when an event occurs. This is done in close collaboration with different actors and agencies following the onset of the event, such as the municipality, the local chief of police, the temporary civil protection service centre, and local coordination group for psychosocial support. Specialists from different sectors participate in these meetings providing information and consultation to the residents, usually spearheaded by representatives from IMO and the Natural Catastrophe Fund in Iceland. The tasks related to the impact are then gradually transferred to the local actors (i.e. long-term and recovery tasks), and the municipality takes over and manages the town hall meetings. What is remarkable is that this engagement is long term. For example, four years after the landslides in Seyðisfjörður, Múlaþing municipal authorities in collaboration with partners like IMO continue to hold workshops for the community on the causes and conditions that made the landslides in 2020 exceptional and how to deal with future risks given climate extremes.

4. Citizen participation in specific DRM roles (response, snow/landslide observers)

Bottom-up activity in local DRM situations is common due to the isolated locations and history of managing adverse situations with local resources. It may be partly due this background that trusted and well-known individuals that often have many roles, as well as active local groups that do not have official position in the system, may have an important supporting role on the preparedness, warning and response phases. For instance, in the 2020 events in Seyðisfjörður the local police officer and snow observer (two roles) had actively reached out to the locals to

start evacuations when observing the imminent risk of a landslide before the civil protection emergency level alert was given, which possibly saved lives.

9.4.2. Gaps and Challenges

1. While the DRM system in Iceland functions extremely well in current conditions, the gaps regarding documentation, regulation and protocols in practices, however, may pose people in unequal positions as the knowledge is not openly available for everyone. This may cause challenges when the DRM system is faced with novel extremes of hazards and compound events due to climate change, that requires counting in more personnel and new actors.
2. There are some issues and limitations related to effective warning communication and what to do as well as language barriers. IMO does an excellent job at putting all relevant information about the hazard, location, duration, and impacts on its website with alerts listed on IMO's home page and links to NCIP's website for recommended actions and advice on what to do. NCIP also provides information on their website but unfortunately this information on the NCIP webpage is in Icelandic. See below (figures 28 and 29) an example for landslide alert provided on IMO's website and the linked webpage on NCIP that is written in Icelandic. Furthermore, the linked NCIP page does not provide any information about what to do for affected populations with regards to managing or dealing with the landslide risk, evacuations, etc. Whilst this is the mandate of NCIP, partners from NCIP have informed us that a new and improved civil protection website is under construction for these purposes.

Figure: 28: IMO Warning on Landslide Risks in Southeast and East Fjords, screenshot 18/02/25

Figure 29: Screenshot of linked page from IMO’s Homepage to NCIP Warning depicting messaging only in Icelandic, screenshot 18/02/25

3. There are gaps regarding preparedness to hazards that are currently not considered severe or likely enough or the preparedness for which is in development. For instance, forest fire hazard mapping is planned. Furthermore, there are gaps in utilizing the risk information at the local level for preparedness which is reported to be due to lack of reach or willingness to act, e.g. regarding the avalanche and landslide hazard zones.
4. While the warnings are relatively well reached by the locals, a gap remains regarding the effectiveness of warnings on the “last-mile/first-mile”. The familiarity of dealing with hazards, possibly false perception of “knowing the nature” and sense-of-belonging to a place may sometimes result in overlooking the warnings.
5. For people moving in and visiting Iceland from abroad it may be difficult to understand which warnings to follow and how to interpret them. The warnings may be interpreted wrong due previous knowledge, e.g. the weather warnings are impact-based and, therefore, a yellow weather warning in Iceland may indicate a different weather situation - often far worse - than in other countries. It is also more unlikely for visitors and new residents than for the locals that the social network fills in the missing information.
6. While the Civil Protection protocol activation is very effective in Iceland, a two-sided communication and action gap in the emergency response phase exists particularly with rarely occurring and unusual hazard events for which the hazard and action information is not necessarily as readily, if at all, available. Overall, independent activity of locals in emergency situations caused by natural hazards in Iceland may be contradicting the official guidelines and communication on hazard and warnings that may pose the formal DRM system in a challenging

position. For instance, in the 2020 landslide event in Seyðisfjörður, the independent actions of some locals may have undermined public trust in the official warning system. However, they are often implemented out of perceived need for action to reduce risks in lack of official guidelines or clear instructions for action particularly with novel types of hazards and unforeseen extents of hazard events.

7. Another gap is related to communication between scales of decision-making, i.e. National Commission of Police with the regional, municipal, and local police departments. It was noted during interviews that during emergency situations when there is heightened uncertainty about appropriate decisions and measures to take, some difficulties arise. While the system of decision-making has changed over the years where central authorities have increased decision-making power, some local-level officials noted that the previous system of the decision to evacuate and other measures should be given back to local authorities and follow a bottom-up approach rather than the current top-down approach. This became especially evident during the landslides in 2020 when local authorities and citizens having seen the initial landslides wanted to issue an evacuation order but were still awaiting confirmation from central authorities, according to interviews. Questions about the pressure of decision-making and who is better to issue an evacuation order (central CP or local authorities) still remains. However, during the recent Grindvik volcanic eruptions this was mitigated as the location is much closer to the capital and easier to access by specialists and central offices.

Additionally, this relates to issues communicating warnings to the public in a timely manner. During the course of interviews, the effectiveness and timeliness of warnings they received to evacuate faced many obstacles, which interviewees related to decision-making and communication gaps between the different levels of authority but also relying on certain modes of delivery such as location-based SMS alerts. While SMS texts are used during the evacuation process, procedures also include authorities calling residents or knocking at their doors. However, during the landslides in 2020, this proved difficult because of safety and road conditions and some residents, especially those who were not Icelandic, did not receive timely important information about where to go or what to do when the landslides occurred. Experts and residents noted that this system only works if it reaches every user, including foreign residents and non-residents. This highlights the importance to promote and implement multi-channel communication strategies and in multiple languages.

9.4.3. Recommendations and Opportunities for Collaboration with other DEMs

1. Overall, the Icelandic DRM and MHWS function as exemplary models of dynamic multi-level management systems for constantly changing and relatively unpredictable natural hazard environments. However whilst, the locals highly used to living with extreme environmental conditions may be familiar with actions and measures to take, there is a major gap with tourists and foreign residents on the basics of bio-geo-physical hazards, where to get warnings, and what to do when dealing with climate extremes and hazards. Iceland partners can learn from DEM 3 (Italy) with regards to their nation-wide and regional disaster risk education public campaigns. Frequent campaigns such as the “I don’t Take Risks” and [simulation exercises](#) on various risk scenarios can help raise awareness and inform populations who have moved to the area. Iceland’s use of multilingual signs and color-coded alerts such as the signs in Reynisfjara is very useful, however, adding videos on how to act before, during, and after a dangerous situation such as those added on Italy’s civil protection website can help inform tourists of the dangers and risks they face.
2. Iceland’s use of snow observers for monitoring and observing avalanche risks is also being adopted for landslide risks, at least in Seydisfjordur. However, while these observers receive

training and regular courses from IMO and specialists in the department of avalanche and landslides, it is important to incorporate them more fully in the hazard monitoring system. Establishing a network of local observers, much like DEM 10 (Switzerland's) system of Local Natural Hazard Advisors (LNHA), which are embedded in the DRM system (see DEM 10 section for more information) could provide a more harmonised approach and integration of multi-level hazard monitoring and observation. While snow observers in Iceland are similar to those in Switzerland in terms of professional background and local expertise, their insights on contextual dynamics and local conditions can be better integrated across IMO's hazard monitoring system and IMO partners can gain valuable insights from Switzerland's integration of LNHAs on ensuring coherence and integration across all regions. This system of "citizen scientists" could also be rolled out to include local residents and raise awareness of risks and preparedness measures like those done in Dorset (DEM 9) and in Italy (DEM 3).

3. The web platform for gathering all knowledge sources together and communicating for different audiences developed in the HuT is well suited to fill the gaps identified in Seydisfjordur. However, this type of platform would be highly beneficial to be rolled out nationally as well through the partnership between IMO and NCIP. Web platforms for risks and warnings have been carried out nationally in DEM 3 (Italy) under the [Civil Protection](#), DEM 10 (Switzerland) with the [Natural Hazard Platform](#), and DEM 9 (UK) with the Met Office. All of these web platforms provide a map that shows current hazards and warnings, warning information, and recommended actions to take to manage and respond to risks.
4. Furthermore, while the IMO and NCIP have a long-established partnership, it might be beneficial to have a data-sharing platform where information about warnings, risk assessments, and actions and response measures could be shared. DEM10, Switzerland, for example has a Joint Information Platform for Natural Hazards ([GIN](#)), which combines all available data on natural hazards in Switzerland in a user-friendly map application for all authorities. These could be additional resources for Iceland partners to use when implementing the web platform. Furthermore, we recommend some improvement and better coherence with regards to communicating risk mitigation measures on NCIP's webpages and social media platforms (i.e. Facebook page) for alerts. As point 2 in the Gaps and Challenges section highlighted, the linked pages provided on IMO's website to NCIP's pages for further information on actions and response measures are generally incomplete and in Icelandic. It is imperative to provide any information about managing or dealing with potential risks in clear, consistent, and multiple languages. Lessons can be learned from all other DEMs on providing multilingual information about actions, preventive measures, and videos and visual information on disaster risks, including DEM 9 (UK), DEM 3 (Italy), DEM 10 (Switzerland).
5. The challenge of reaching non-residents, visitors, tourists, and foreign residents is one that is prevalent for Iceland partners as well as other DEMs that receive high volumes of visitors including in Dorset, Campania, and Val d'Aran. Iceland has a number of initiatives including the use of colour-coded and alert-scales warning signs in risky areas, the Safe Travel app, and the road authority website (<https://umferdin.is/en>). Firstly, it is important to ensure that these apps are consistent with official websites of responsible authorities, including IMO and NCIP, including on hazard information, warnings, and guidelines and actions to take. For example, the Safe Travel app had a heavy wind warning listed in the app for the Snaefellnes Peninsula, forecasted 72-90km/h. However, this should coincide with IMO's yellow-level alert for Southerly gale or strong gale in the south and west regions. Not only is it vital to have the same consistent messaging about the warning between IMO and the Safe Travel app including the yellow warning level (which Safe Travel did not include) but also with consistent information about the full hazard and forecast, i.e. IMO forecasted 65-90 km/h gusts as well as snow and sleet, "Blowing snow can be expected

with poor visibility and bad travel conditions” whereas Safe Travel only listed “heavy winds” for the peninsula and had a different range for gusts forecasted.

Furthermore, there should be consistency and detailed information on actions and measures to take between the different apps and web pages. In the same example, IMO’s website note that “Conditions can be hazardous for vehicles that are sensitive to wind,” but did not provide any further information or link to NCIP guidance. Actions and response measures for populations to take should be already set out by NCIP in collaboration with partners that then can be shared to ensure consistency and harmonisation across apps and authorities. For the same hazard forecasted, the Safe Travel app cautioned, “Difficult driving conditions for vehicles that take on wind.” However, neither of these statements are action-oriented or provide specific information. How would a visitor know if their rental vehicle is sensitive to or takes on wind? While this might be very plain and obvious for Icelandic people, visitors or foreigners unfamiliar with Iceland's rough terrain and hazard conditions are generally ill-prepared and unaware.

Secondly, it would be very useful to have surveys conducted with visitor populations on how effective these initiatives are and awareness levels of such information provision methods. Organisations that work closely with local populations such as GNDR can provide guidance on this. Recommendations on having information sheets at hotel desks and tourist sites as well as training hotel personnel on basic disaster risk information that can be provided to visitors were also highlighted during discussion. However, the authors recognise that this can be difficult given Iceland’s already burdened workforce and limited population.

During interviews, local residents provided novel ideas in providing information to foreign residents about disaster risks. Building on IMO’s effective system of hazard mapping, it was noted that when moving into a city in Iceland, risks that the area faces could be shared with new residents in an information packet. This was mentioned as a result of many foreign residents claiming they were not aware that Seyðisfjörður was a landslide-prone area and did not have prior information on local risks provided by the municipality or household authorities.

10. DEM 2 Val d'Aran, Spain

10.1. Overview and background

This section gives an overview of how disaster risk governance and management is organised in Val d'Aran, including an overview of the DR governance and management in Spain and in the autonomous Community of Catalonia where the sub-territorial Val d'Aran system is embedded. The brief overview covers all disaster types and phases of the DRM cycle. Additional information on the national level warnings is collected to the table in the section 13 at the end of this report. In this section, the focus is on the prevention and communication of natural hazard and climate/weather driven disasters. More precisely, the focus is on the main natural hazards that are potentially disastrous in Catalonia and Val d'Aran and that are affected by climate change, namely:

- Meteorological hazards, including floods
- Avalanches
- Landslides
- Forest fires
- Droughts

This section is based on a review of grey literature and DRM organizations websites as well on the 15 stakeholder interviews conducted in English and Spanish in 9-11/2024 in Barcelona, Val d'Aran and online. The interviewees constituted of 20 territorial and sub-territorial stakeholders and some of the interviews were held in small groups of 2-4 persons.

Case Study: Val d'Aran, Catalonia

The research carried out in Catalonia examines the DRM and warning systems across the national and local scales. The focus of the study was the selected Val d'Aran territory located in the Aran valley on the Catalanian-side of the Pyrenes. The Aran sub-territory constitutes of nine municipalities that divide into 33 villages which are located mostly along the Garonne river. The river crosses to the French side of the Pyrenes and the coordination of the river management involves cross-border collaboration. An extreme flood event in river Garonne exacerbated by unusually heavy snow accumulation in 2013 caused unforeseen damage to infrastructure and mobility in the valley (Figures 30, 31, 32).

Based on the interviews the 2013 flood event in the Val d'Aran territory was seen to have lead to several renewals in the system, most importantly:

- initiating the process of strengthening the territorial civil protection services
- increasing interest and resources put into the flood monitoring system that has further lead to developing the monitoring systems of other hazards as well
- increasing the interest and efforts to develop the sub-territorial and communal hazard specific civil protection plans and private sector self-protection plans.

In addition to the occasional meteorological hazards, more recently, the risk of landslides has been considered to increase in the region by experts, and forest fires are an emerging risk according to both the experts and authorities. Droughts are currently not considered as an important risk in the region, while they have become more severe in Catalonia in the past years. However, floods, landslides and droughts are generally considered by the public and public authorities as relatively

rarely occurring or minor hazards for which preparedness is not considered a priority. The priority for the public, authorities and businesses are the avalanches in the winter season that are a regular risk to mobility in the valley when they cut off the sparse road connections, and to the seasonal skiing tourism, which is an important economic sector in the Aran valley, particularly the Baquiera resort. The Aran valley Avalanche center and ski resorts have long experience of managing the avalanche risks and the EWS is highly developed.

Figure 30: The town of Arties in the upstream was worst struck by the 2013 flood event flushing away building parts and road infrastructure (Photo provided by Arantec).

Figure 31: Vielha, the capital of Val d'Aran, is lower from Arties and it was not as badly hit by the flood, whilst the main traffic lanes were completely inundated (Photo provided by Arantec).

Figure 32: Road between Val d'Aran and France-side of the Pyrenes collapsed during the event (Photo provided by Arantec).

10.2. Disaster Risk Management and Warning System

The governance in Spain is decentralized and divided into three levels – national, territorial and local. Here, territorial refers to the autonomous communities that have legislative competence. Local governance level refers to provinces and municipalities and they do not have legislative competence. There are a total of 17 Autonomous Communities (AC) in Spain. In the autonomous community of Catalonia, there are four provinces that constitute 42 sub-territories or ‘comarcas’ covering the 947 municipalities and towns of Catalonia. Aran sub-territory has a unique legislative competence position due historical reason.

The ACs have full legal competence i.e. are responsible for the emergency management except for in the case of a national emergency being declared. A national emergency may be declared when an emergency affects several ACs. However, national emergencies have not been declared in recent years, including the catastrophic flood events related to the DANA phenomena, also known as the Cold Drop phenomena, that crossed Autonomous Communities borders (see, Chavda, 2024; IFRC, 2022).

The national disaster risk management legal and policy framework constitutes of several laws, strategies and plans, but is currently built particularly on four civil protection (CP) instruments in force, namely (IFRC, 2022; MITECO, 2021):

- The National Civil Protection Law 17/2015
- National Civil Protection Strategy
- National Plan for Civil Protection Emergencies
- The National Civil Protection Specific Plans for Forest Fires, Floods, Earthquakes and tsunamis, Volcanic activity, Adverse Weather events, Hazardous substances accidents, Transport of Dangerous goods, and Nuclear and radiological risks.

The Interior Ministry is the responsible authority of Spanish Civil Protection and its Directorate General of Civil Protection and Emergencies (DGPCE) is the governing body of planning and coordinating the national civil protection system (SNPC) that builds on the different Civil Protection Plans (Fig.34) (DGPCE, 2020). Under the DGPCE, the National Council of Civil Protection (NCCP) has the role of coordinating and collaborating between all the relevant public administration representatives from the three levels of governance dealing with issues of civil protection. The NCCP is the national contact point for the European Civil Protection Mechanism and the Sendai Framework. The CP Commissions of Autonomous Communities (AC) are composed in a similar way.

Climate change as a risk enhancing factor is addressed in broad terms in the National Civil Protection Strategy but climate change adaptation is not legally required to be integrated into the civil protection processes. However, “-- the National Strategy encourages revising and updating the civil protection framework with the aim of ensuring and enhancing policy and legislative coherence with existing instruments on CCA.” (IFRC, 2022, p.32).

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Figure 33: Organizational chart of the Spanish emergency management system (Source: ECHO, 2019).

The national adaptation plan (NAP) 2021-2030 by the Environmental Ministry (*Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico, MITECO*) addresses DRM as one key lines of action (MITECO, 2020). A framework for coherence of the disaster risk management and climate change adaptation planning systems in Spain introduces relevant governance instruments for climate change related disaster risk management instruments and organizations (Table 5) (MITECO, 2021).

Table 5: Key climate-related risk governance in Spain (adapted from MITECO, 2021: 41-42).

Key risk	Governance instruments	Responsible organisations
Extreme rainfall and floods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Directive 2007/60/EC Royal Decree 903/2010 Flood Risk Management Plans (PGRI) (MITECO, nd(a)) National Prediction and Monitoring Plan of Adverse Meteorological Events (<i>Meteoalerta</i>) (AEMET, 2025b) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Directorate General for Water (DGW) - <i>Demarcations hydrographic, MITECO</i> AEMET - MITECO Civil Protection - <i>Interior Ministry</i>
Coastal events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Law 22/1988 Strategy for Adaptation to Climate Change on the Spanish Coast (MITECO, nd(b)) <i>Meteoalerta</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DG Coasts & Sea - MITECO AEMET Civil Protection
Forest Fires	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Law 43/2003 State Civil Protection Specific Plan for Forest Fires (DGPCE, 2015) Forest Fire Prevention and Firefighting Action Plans 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DG Biodiversity, Forests and Desertification - MITECO AEMET Civil Protection

Droughts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Law 10/2001, National Hydrological Plan • Law 11/2005 amending Law 10/2001 on the National Hydrological Plan • Special Action Plans in Alert and Eventual Situations Drought (PES) (MITECO, nd (c)) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DGW • AEMET • Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (MAPA)
Extreme winds	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meteoalerta 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AEMET • Civil Protection
Heatwaves	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Law 33/2011 • National Plan of Preventive Actions on the effects of excess temperatures on health (Ministerio de Sanidad, 2024) • Meteoalerta 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ministry of Health • AEMET • Civil Protection

10.2.1. Autonomous communities - Catalonia

The ACs have similar civil protection organizational structure and legal and policy framework as in the national level. The Ministry of Home Affairs and Public Security (*Departament d'Interior i Seguretat Pública*) of the Government of Catalonia (*Generalitat de Catalunya*, in short *GenCat*) is the responsible authority of Catalanian Civil Protection and its Directorate-General of Civil Protection of the Government of Catalonia (DGPC) is the responsible coordinating and planning body for civil protection and emergencies. Under DGPC are, for example, the Operations Coordination Centre of Catalonia (CECAT) for emergency coordination (created by Decree 246/1992, of 26 October) and the CP Commission of Catalonia.

The Law 4/1997, of 20 May, on Civil Protection in Catalonia states the obligations of the Catalanian civil protection public authorities and the policies, most importantly, the Civil Protection Plans and the Special Plans for the different hazards and the risk assessments they are based on. The Catalanian Water Agency (ACA) has the mandate for drought risk management, including the drought risk assessments and the Special Drought Plan (PES), approved by Agreement GOV/1/2020, of 8 January (see, ACA, 2025)

10.2.2. Val d'Aran sub-territory

The Aran sub-territory of Catalonia has its own governance *Conselh Generau d'Aran* that has the authority on the public-private emergency service body *Pompiers Emergencies* (PE) that consists of the sub-territorial fire department, health emergency service, civil protection and mountain rescuing services as well as the sub-territorial emergency operations room 'SCAran' (Fig. 34). The authority on planning and management of emergency services and civil protection, including the coordination and collaboration with municipalities, was transferred from the local municipalities to the Conselh Generau in 2015 based on the law 1/2015 of Special regime of the Val d'Aran. The Aran sub-territory constitutes of nine municipalities that each have the mayor and a municipal technician as the key decision-making authorities in an event of emergency and on issuing warnings and evacuation orders. Municipalities also have a drought management responsibility through their water supply competence i.e. the municipal and sub-territorial councils are in responsibility of securing sustained water consumption to secure drinking water.

Figure 34: The organizational chart of Aran sub-territory emergency services (Source: PE presentation material).

10.3. Multi-hazard Warnings in Spain

10.3.1 Warning Design and Content

Risk assessments and Plans for preparedness and prevention

The key actions for preparedness and prevention are defined in (i) the Specific Plans by the Ministries of Environment and Health who lead the regular or needs-based risks assessments the plans are based on, and in (ii) the National Civil Protection plan and CP Specific Plans that are based on legally binding regular risk assessments lead by the DGPCE carrying them out together with relevant agencies. In addition, Spain has cross-border agreements on civil protection with Portugal, France, and Morocco that includes risk assessment of which is mainly used with France on forest fires.

Similarly, the key actions for preparedness and prevention at the ACs are defined in the AC Civil Protection plan and CP Special Plans that are based on legally binding territorial risk assessments done in collaboration with the sub-territorial authorities (*comarcas*) and the meteorological agency that identify vulnerabilities and the risks related to each hazard and list the municipalities that need to do municipal action plans for specific risks (see, GenCat – Dades Obertes, 2025). The CP risk maps (see, ICGC, 2025) show the civil protection risks of different hazards and the vulnerabilities (incl. locations and equipment of emergency services). The risk mapping also guides urban planning strictly, while exceptions are done occasionally when a planner provides an alternative risk management plan.

A basic municipal emergency plan is required from communities larger than 20,000 people, tourist municipalities, and municipalities considered to be at special risk according to the Civil Protection Commission of Catalonia. It is a multi-risk plan and covers risks that do not have a municipal

action plans for specific risks. In the Val d'Aran region, all municipalities do not yet have all these action plans in place or approved.

In Catalonia, the CP Special Plans (see, Departament d'Interior i Seguretat Pública, 2024) for natural hazards cover the plan for floods (INUNCAT), forest fires (INFOCAT), avalanches (ALLAUCAT), and meteorological extremes including extreme snowfall (NEUCAT) and wind (VENTCAT). Landslides are not considered to cause high enough risk at the moment to be under CP jurisdiction and they are mainly locally managed, i.e. by municipalities. However, as the landslides may cause severe damage particularly during flood events, it has been proposed by experts that they would be included in the flood risk management scheme. The General Directorate of Forests and Environmental Management of the Department of Agriculture, Livestock, Fisheries and Food is responsible for drawing up the basic forest fire danger map that classifies the municipalities of Catalonia according to their level of danger.

Special Drought Plans (PES) for the different river basins are done in cooperation with the relevant administrators and companies and lead by Hydrographic Confederations in Spain for the shared basins of rivers crossing autonomous territories - in Catalonia, namely Ebro and Júcar, and by the Catalan water agency (ACA) for the 18 internal basins of rivers originating in Catalonia. Most of the external river basin areas in Catalonia, including the Aran territory, belong to the jurisdiction of Hydrographic Confederation of Ebro basin (CHE). However, ACA provides certain criteria as well as support on the Ebro basin water supply management (see, ACA, 2025). The drought management actions in internal and shared basin demarcations are guided by the PESs. More precisely, in Catalonia the PES is described as follows:

“The essential hydrological planning tool for acting in drought situations PES is as a preventive management tool that maintains permanent surveillance on the evolution of water reserves and establishes for each scenario and scope of action the progressivity of the measures that combine demand management with the availability of the resource.” (ACA, 2025)

Plans for heat related health issue prevention in national and Catalan levels are conducted by the Ministry of Health and the ASPCAT respectively, based on risk assessments conducted in collaboration with relevant agencies, most importantly, the AEMET and the SMC, respectively. General self-protection plans (HERMES) (see, Departament d'Interior i Seguretat Pública, nd) are required from businesses and other relevant private or third sector actors whose premises may expose several people at risk due natural or other hazards. In addition, specific preparedness plans are required for certain hazards, for instance, all relevant actors in drought management - urban, agro-livestock, industrial and recreational-sports - must have a drought management plan, i.e. water saving plan that the water agency approves. The self-protection plans are integrated into the public CP system and regulated by relevant authors in the AC level. In Val d'Aran, the system was criticized laborious and unfair for small businesses. All the campsites in the region are currently obliged to do HERMES and there is an ongoing process of developing an online platform for making, communicating and monitoring the plans which raised hope in the critics.

Detection, observation, monitoring and forecasting

The specific agencies in Spain and Catalonia have the legal obligation of data collection and analysis (detection), monitoring and forecasting related to the hazards addressed in the special plans. These agencies are also responsible for communication of the hazards to relevant agencies and issuing warnings. Detection, monitoring and forecasting of meteorological hazards in Spain is done by the AEMET and in Catalonia by the Meteorological Service of Catalonia (SMC). The risks of hazardous meteorological situations are identified based on threshold values, and the degree of danger based on the relation of the likelihood and severity of the event compliant with the

National Plan for Forecasting and Monitoring of Adverse Meteorological Events (Meteoalerta) (see, Servei Meteorològic de Catalunya, 2024). Meteoalerta aims to converge the system with the European framework of the Meteoalarm project (EUMETNET, 2025) which means providing timely information and a 72h forecast on the adverse weather phenomena (see, MITECO, 2021). In addition, detection and monitoring of flood hazard in the Val d’Aran region is carried out by Arantec.

Detection, monitoring and forecasting of avalanche hazards is the responsibility of AEMET in Spain, The Cartographic and Geological Institute of Catalonia (ICGC) in collaboration with the SMC in Catalonia, and The Avalanche Center of Val d’Aran in the sub-territory. They all follow the European Avalanche Warning Services (EAWS) standard for assessment of the danger based on a function of several factors. The vulnerable areas in Aran region are, for instance, mapped by local experts, including mountain guides and rangers, acknowledging areas in higher use by the skiing and backcountry tourists, and the roads that are sensitive to avalanche blockages and important for the locals and ski-tourists. The snow conditions on-site are monitored 3-4 times weekly by the forecasters, in addition to the automatic monitoring stations and daily on-site observations provided voluntarily by local ski-patrollers and mountain guides.

Detection, monitoring and forecasting of forest fire hazards is the responsibility of the Directorate General for Forests and Environmental Management that carries out a daily assessment of the fire hazard and a 48-hour forecast, following the Canadian fire danger index, based on the dynamic meteorological variables (records, present weather and near forecast) and the state of the vegetation or the causality in the occurrence of fires. Nationally, the daily weather risk for forest fire is assessed by the AEMET following the same danger index (see, AEMET, 2025a). However, it is beyond this report to clarify the full legal competencies related to the national level forest fire risk management. In Val d’Aran, the detection and monitoring of forest fire hazards is carried out by the forestry expert of the Conseilh Generau, however, without a legal competence.

Detection, monitoring and forecasting of drought hazards in Spain is the responsibility of the Hydrographic Confederations and in Catalonia the ACA, that collaborate with the AEMET and SMC respectively on the meteorological drought detection, monitoring and forecasting. A seasonal forecast is given at national level in December until March of the reservoir inflow (see, Sánchez-García et al 2022). In Val d’Aran, there is no special agency to carry out detection, monitoring or forecasting of drought hazards.

10.3.2 Warning Sequence and Chain of Responsibility

Decision-making on warnings and response

The specific responsible agencies issuing warning bulletins of the hazards addressed in the special plans are obliged to provide the hazard information directly to the CP who decides on further communication with relevant actors to decide on activation of the emergency/CP action plans that involve further guidelines on the responses, including those related to warnings.

Emergency situations in Spain are addressed on three level scale with the first level signifying a local level emergency that activates a municipal emergency plan or special plan that is handled with local resources. The second level emergency means escalation of the local emergency to the autonomous community (AC) level, the activation of the AC Civil Protection plan or Special Plan, and provision of resources by the ACs Civil Protection and other relevant AC authorities. A level three emergency signifies the escalation of an emergency beyond the ACs capacity or a nuclear emergency or war situation which are always national level emergencies, and the Interior Ministry taking over the emergency coordination as well as providing resources, including the Military Emergency Unit Unidad Militar de Emergencias (UME) i.e. the emergency division of the Armed

Forces. The UME can be activated also at the request of any competent authorities, regardless of whether or not a national emergency is declared (see, IFRC, 2022: 16).

In Catalonia, the actions and communication between the organizations are guided by the three levels of action in the Special Plans, namely, (i) prealert, (ii) alert and (iii) emergency phases.

The SMC has the role of expert organization in all communication to hazards related to weather, but they have a specific role in activation of the Special Plans for floods (INUNCAT), snowfall extremes (NEUCAT), and wind extremes (VENTCAT). The prealert phase is activated by the SMC by calling to the Operational Coordination Center of Catalonia (CECAT) of the Interior Ministry whenever a threshold for moderate degree of danger is expected to be reached. Communication at this first phase is between the technicians in the SMC, CP and possibly other relevant organizations who discuss via phone or Teams the details of warnings being issued such as the spatial and temporal occurrence and intensity of the events. The Civil Protection Plan is activated in the alert phase when a high level warning is issued. This is the second level of communication held between the technicians and managers SMC, CP and other relevant organizations via phone or Teams to share more detailed information needed and to decide on the need for a shift to a third level of communication. Third and highest level of communication means on-site gathering of the political decision-makers, directors and managers of the CP, SMC and other relevant organizations and committees to make decisions based on the warning forecasts, for example, restrictions in the territory to cut roads, to confine people to their homes, or closing schools in an area where flooding is expected as well as issuing the cell broadcast alerts with specific instructions in the areas where the event is expected.

The ICGC issuing a warning of high risk of avalanches signifies the prealert phase of the Catalonian Civil Protection plan for avalanches (ALLAUCAT). Both the ALLAUCAT and the Municipal Action Plans (PAM) can be activated in alert or in emergency phases, depending on the avalanche danger degree and/or the impact on vulnerable elements. The Rural Agents follow a protocol Pla Alfa for their actions of forest fire surveillance and prevention in the face of situations of forest fire hazard (Departament d'Interior i Seguretat Pública, 2025). The plan evaluates hazardous situations on a scale of 5 ranging from 0 for low danger to 4 for extreme danger. Levels 0 to 2 are applied at the county level. Levels 3 and 4 are applied at the municipal level and entail the activation of the Rural Agents in surveillance of the issued restrictions on specific risk activities. The activation of level 3 of the plan, together with the analysis of other risk indicators, implies the activation of the INFOCAT Civil Protection Special Plan prealert phase and the communication between the relevant agencies and the CP on actions and warnings. The activation of level 4 of the plan, together with the analysis of other risk indicators, means the activation of the INFOCAT Civil Protection Plan in the alert phase.

The ACA is in the lead responsibility of drought management in the 18 internal basin areas in Catalonia, including the hazard communication, and drought measures guiding and monitoring (see, ACA, 2025). Hydrological drought emergency was last declared in Catalonia in January 2024.

In addition, the Val d'Aran territorial government gives river flooding warnings per each municipality provided by the Arantec monitoring and analysis system SmartyPlanet API (see, www.arantec.com) (Fig. 35).

Figure 35: Val d’Aran flood hazard monitoring information include river water level and flow information on each of the settlements along the rivers in the region; the degree of danger is indicated with a colour-coded flag; note that only part of the figures are visible in the screenshot (Conselh Generau d’Aran, 2025).

Evaluation and feed-back

The preparedness plans and risk assessments are evaluated regularly or when needed. For most of the plans and assessments this is mandatory. Only the Special Plan for forest fires (INFOCAT) addresses the need to revise the plans at national and municipal level due to climate change so to better address the adaptation needs. Other relevant Special Plans do not explicitly state the need for revisions due climate change (ALLAUCAT, INUNCAT, NEUCAT, VENTCAT). However, it is generally stated that all plans are revised when needed.

Based on the interviews, the warning system is evaluated continuously based on experiences gained in action and from active development work engaging in national and international networks. For instance, the Catalanian CP unit for research and development is currently involved in several weather and climate risk monitoring and warning research and development projects. The Aran region warning system is in the development phase.

Cell broadcast alerts are tested regularly and test alerts are assessed with voluntary surveys done by the CP. A general citizen feed-back system called ‘Espais d’ experiència ciutadana’ that translates roughly as ‘Citizen Experience Space’ is created in the territorial government to assess their different digital services in terms of citizens’ experiences on e.g. the usability and accessibility. This assessment system is used for example to assess the Website of the Meteorological Service of Catalonia, however, there are yet no recorded assessments of the cell broadcast alert system.

Issuing warnings

The specific agencies in Spain and Catalonia that have the legal obligation of detection, monitoring and forecasting of hazards addressed in the special plans are also responsible for issuing warnings and hazard information. In addition, the ICGC provides risk bulletins and hazard information on landslides in Catalonia, but warnings *per se* are not currently issued.

The legal capacity on issuing warnings is generally considered necessary for the warning system to work properly, which is due to the hierarchical system, but also for that the legal capacity indicates resources. The interviewees did not indicate any prominent disagreements on the current share of the warning issuing capacities in the Catalonian level, or between the vertical levels of governance. The capacity on landslide warnings is, however, still missing. In addition, the legitimate warning policy in the Val d’Aran region is yet unclear with all other hazards apart from avalanches.

10.3.3 Communication, Dissemination, and Delivery of Warnings

The communication of the warnings is three-fold. First, the warning is communicated to the public by the responsible agencies primarily through their websites using geospatial visualisations, i.e. hazard/ risk maps illustrating the areas at risk with colour-code indicating the degree of danger that may also include provisional information on the hazard and on proposed actions. Social media channels are also widely in use by these agencies for sharing the warnings.

Sometimes the information and the weather warnings by the SMC and AEMET differ from each other (see figures 36 and 37). This may be due to the different data sources used by the two agencies, or because the SMC considers a more detailed level of analysis of the risks based on its better territorial knowledge.

Figure 36: Catalan Meteorological Services’ weather warning map illustrating a yellow and orange warning on wind for several comarcas, and orange warning on sea conditions on the north-east (Source: visited 12.1.2025: <https://www.meteo.cat/prediccio/general>).

Figure 37: AEMET warning map shows lower prediction on the warning. The legend shows warnings on an hourly basis and differentiates between the different hazards (Source: visited 12.1.2025: <https://www.aemet.es/en/eltiempo/prediccion/avisos?w=hoy&a=pb>).

Second, more detailed warning bulletins (Fig. 38) on meteorological hazards, avalanches, landslides and droughts synthesizing the relevant hazard information and indicating the degree of danger are issued mainly for warning communication with other agencies. Bulletins are used to inform the civil protection to start discussion on the need for activation of the special plans and the consequential actions that may include, for example, alerts to the population. The CP uses their communication channels for sharing the warning and giving out instructions for actions in case of alerts. Level of detail on the hazard provided by the responsible agency to the CP depends on the degree of danger and the involved experts. In Catalonia, the SMC and CP consider their interaction in these cases to work very well.

Third, the warning and hazard information may need to be communicated directly to other relevant actors, such as municipal technicians and experts in other agencies, such as the water or rural agency. In these cases, the issuing agency provides information on the level of detail necessary to the receiver. For instance, the Catalan Road Authority needs information on the probability of floods and avalanches reaching the road-network to provide road safety warnings in real-time on their webpages (Fig. 39).

Figure 38: Warning bulletin by the Catalan Meteorological Services on specific weather related hazard used in direct communication with the CP and other relevant stakeholders.

Figure 39: Catalanian road authority provides warnings for hazardous meteorological road conditions through a real-time road condition map service (Source: <https://mct.gencat.cat/>).

To exemplify the communication on warning through the CP the information flow diagram of a meteorological emergency in Catalonia (Fig. 40) illustrates how the SMC issues a warning bulletin (*Avís*) of a hazardous meteorological situation to Civil Protection who then summons the relevant organisations, for example, the state hydrological agency (CHE) in the case of floods; the *Mossos d'Esquadra* i.e. the National Police of Catalonia and the fire brigade (*Bombers*) in case of needs for their actions; the municipal councils (*Ajuntaments*) that represent the 947 towns and municipalities of Catalonia in case of a meteorological emergency affecting their town or municipality; and the other agents (*altres*) including the road authority in case of roads being affected, and representatives of the health services, in the event that people may be injured in the meteorological emergency.

Figure 40: The process of communicating the hazard and warning information in case of a hazardous meteorological situation (Source: SMC presentation).

Warning types

The warnings by the responsible agencies provide information on the hazard type, degree of danger, and spatial and temporal exposure, and in some cases, recommendations for actions. There are differences on the resolution, danger scales, index-colours and provisional information between some of the warnings addressed in this report. The inconsistencies were generally not considered problematic by the interviewees regarding the relevant agencies, however, the view of the public on the matter was not generally well understood.

The meteorological warnings in Spain and in Catalonia define the meteorological hazard type, the degree of danger based on the relation of the likelihood and severity of the event using threshold based risk levels on colour coded 4-scale from green indicating no risk (not shown in the risk maps), yellow indicating moderate risk, orange significant risk and red extreme risk. The geographic resolution of the warnings is provincial (Catalonia, for example, divides into four provinces) for AEMET and municipal for SMC. The warnings issued by the SMC do not provide any descriptions on impact nor recommendations on actions, whereas the AEMET warning legend introduces very general level brief description on impacts and recommendations for each of the three risk levels (see, AEMET, 2025b). Recommendations for actions in Catalonia are only issued by the CP via the cell broadcast alerts to mobile phones and other communication methods in emergency situations. The cell broadcast alerts are on two levels: (i) pre-alert/alert of the Special Plan being activated that gives instructions for preparatory actions e.g. “avoid all unnecessary travelling outside/ on the roads/ in public transportation”, (ii) emergency alert for evacuation instructions etc.

The avalanche warnings in Catalonia and Val d’Aran define the risk on a colour-coded 5-level danger scale from green (low danger) to red (high and extreme high) on geographical resolution of 100km². The visual illustrations and colour for the highest level of risk that the two agencies use differ slightly, but the resolution and spatial cover differs more (see Figures 41 and 42).

Figure 41: The Val d’Aran avalanche risk map illustrating considerable danger on higher latitudes in more detailed resolution than the ICGC map (source: visited 12.1.2025, <https://en.lauegi.report/bulletin/latest?region=ES-CT-L-01>)

The danger bulletin provides detailed information on the hazard. The bulletin reading instructions provide detailed explanations of the information provided with illustrations and colour-coding, e.g. the danger scale legend introduces general level brief descriptions on impacts and recommendations for each of the danger levels (see, Centre de Lauegi d’Aran, nd).

Figure 42: ICGC Avalanche risk bulletin illustrating three levels of danger in six regions (source: visited 12.1.2025, <https://www.icgc.cat/en/Thematic-areas/Risks-and-emergencies/Avalanches/Avalanche-Danger-Bulletin-BPA>)

Forest fire warnings in Catalonia are given with degree of danger on colour coded 5-scale on a 5km resolution map and according to administrative borders depending on the scale of warning: for comarca level on scales 0-2 and municipal level on the high risk levels 4-5 (Fig 43 and 44). The warnings do not involve information on the impacts or recommended actions, instead, they indicate restrictions on fire risk activities that anyone carrying out such activities should follow (Fig. 45). The information provided on the risks, restrictions and warnings are dispersed on several web sites and relatively difficult to find.

Figure 43 and 44: Catalonian forest fire hazard maps with 5km resolution (a on left) and on municipal/ comarca scale (b on right) illustrating yellow (moderate) and orange (high) level warnings on several municipalities/ towns around Catalonia (source, visited 12.1.2025, <https://agricultura.gencat.cat/ca/ambits/medi-natural/incendis-forestals/perill-incendi-diari-informe-setmanal/mapa-perill-incendi/>).

Figure 45. Forest fire warning related restrictions are listed in the agricultural departments' website with a notification on the relation of the restrictions on the risk level; note the full list is not visible in the screenshot. (Source: <https://agricultura.gencat.cat/ca/ambits/medi-natural/incendis/>).

Drought warnings in the internal basin area of Catalonia are given with degree of danger (emergency) on colour coded 6-scale on map with the resolution of municipal administrative borders (Fig 46). The warnings are linked to information on the impacts and recommended actions that are easy to find and understand. The risk map is updated daily and all hazard, vulnerability and risk data are openly available (see, ACA, nd). The drought warnings for, basically the other half of Catalonia, i.e. in the Ebro basin are provided by the national Hydrographic Confederation (CHE) in monthly bulletins using a colour coded 4-scale of degree of danger (emergency) of drought (Fig. 47). These bulletins are mainly for administrative use and there is no information found on the CHE web site directed at citizens on the impacts and actions related to the different drought danger levels. The same information is provided in the weekly hydrological bulletins by the MITECO website (see, ITECO, 2025) where it is stated that warnings are given when relevant. The danger degrees are related to activation of special action plans for drought that are openly available on the agencies websites. The previous Ebro basin drought action plan was from 2018 and it is currently in revision.

Figure 46: The drought risk map for Catalonian internal basins (Visited 18.11.2024, <https://aplicacions.aca.gencat.cat/visseq/estat-actual>).

Figure 47: The drought danger monthly bulletin by the national Ebro basin Hydrographic Confederation (CHE) (Source: CHE, 2024).

Figure 48: Forecast map of hazardous meteorological situation illustrating the simple colour codes, illustrations and patterns (Source, visited 11.1.2025, <https://www.meteo.cat/predicccio/general/informe/>).

The interviewees considered the inclusivity and accessibility of the warning systems in Catalonia to be relatively well addressed regarding people with different types of disabilities and special needs. However, not many interviewees could give examples of how this is actually achieved, which is a limitation of the sample rather than the warning system itself. The high alerts signal volume in the cell broadcast alerts and large font in the alert text are meant to enhance the accessibility for hearing and visually impaired. To enhance the accessibility for all people all warning maps directed to the public, namely the weather and fire maps, use simple and well recognized traffic-light colour coding, and simple illustrations for the different weather hazard types and the development of the hazard, as well as easy-to-find links for further information. For meteorological hazard maps, users can choose distinctive patterns (*Visualiza els mapes amb trames*) for the colour-codes for colour-blind on the weather risk maps (Fig. 48).

The languages used in warnings are a limiting factor for accessibility. The AEMET provides weather warning maps in all five official languages in Spain, and in French and English. In Catalonia, all warning and hazard communication is done in the two co-official languages, Catalan and Spanish, and all warnings including the cell broadcast alerts are given also in English. Avalanche warnings by the ICGC are given in three languages (CAT, ES, EN), whereas those by the Val d'Aran Avalanche Center (ACVA) are given in seven (CAT, ES, ARA, EN, DE, FR, IT). The ACVA and the Baquiera ski resort provide risk information and warnings with consideration of different backgrounds of the tourists.

To enhance the reach of the warnings, the AEMET, SMC and CP use several communication channels. The social media channels are considered particularly important for the CP. The CP X-site has over 1000 followers and the Facebook site over 45'000 followers. To receive the cell broadcast alerts, certain configurations in individual phones might need to be changed which may be an obstacle for people with limited skills and knowledge.

Table 6: Spanish Hazard Warning Map developed by second author

Hazard	Warning/ emergency Who issues the warning? Is it covered by the emergency plan?	Information provided Action, Risks Impact, Forecast, monitoring, etc.	Communication Through which channel(s)?	Scale (municipal, district, national level, etc.)	Timing of Warning When is the warning issued?
Meteoro- logical hazards	Meteorological Service of Catalonia (SMC) issues warnings and communicates with the CP on activation of the Special Plans (INUNCAT, NEUCAT, VENTCAT) and the according actions, including issuing alerts.	Colour coded 4-scale risk chart in public communication; 72h prediction of the development of hazard provided Cell broadcast alert recommends actions	SMC website, bulletins, direct communication with relevant organisations via phone/ Teams/ on-site; SMC social media accounts (X, Facebook, Instagram, YouTube) Cell broadcast alert; GenCat website and social media (X ; Facebook)	Catalonia	Warning maps updated regularly three times a day; more often when needed (SMC) Alerts in high danger situation issued immediately (CP)
Floods	Warnings are created automatically by the Arantec system, issued by the territorial government Siren alert in an emergency situation used in some municipalities; issued by mayor.	Colour coded 4-scale danger information (low, medium, high, very high) on level of the river on the monitoring spots at each of the municipalities along the rivers in Aran region	Territorial government website & the Arantec platform; in case of an extreme flood event a siren alert is used to warn people in municipalities.	Val d'Aran	Currently updated every 15 minutes; siren use based on deliberation

<p>Avalanche</p>	<p>The ICGC issues warnings in snowy period, communicates with the CP on activation of the Special Plan (ALLAUCAT) and the according actions.</p> <p>The Avalanche Center of Val d’Aran (ACVA) provides the territorial warnings</p>	<p>Colour-coded 5-level standard (EAWS)</p> <p>Impact information and action recommendations given on general level for each danger level of the public warnings</p> <p>More detailed hazard forecast info for the ski-resorts and road authority</p>	<p>ICGC website, bulletins, direct communication with relevant stakeholders. CP issues warnings through their channels in the case of activation of the Special Plan</p> <p>The ACVA websites, bulletins, direct communication with relevant actors</p> <p>Ski-resorts website, app and on-site info-panels.</p>	<p>Catalonia</p> <p>Val d’Aran</p>	<p>Public avalanche bulletins daily in snowy season</p> <p>ICGC: alerts in high danger situation are issued immediately</p> <p>ACVA hazard forecast in snowy season three times a day for the road authority</p> <p>Direct communication with relevant actors (e.g. skiing resorts) more often when needed</p>
<p>Landslide</p>	<p>Cartographic and Geological Institute of Catalonia (ICGC) provides hazard and risk information for urban planning, but not yet for warning forecasts.</p> <p>Not covered by the special action plan</p>	<p>Landslide risk information for urban planning uses a three-scale colour coded risk index</p> <p>The rainfall induced landslide forecast warning system is in development; the planned warnings would be similar to flooding (colour coded 4-scale chart)</p>	<p>ICGC website, bulletins, direct communication with relevant stakeholders</p> <p>Landslide hazard information and data openly available (see, ICGC, nd)</p>	<p>Catalonia</p>	<p>Needs based</p>

Forest Fire	GeCat Agricultural department provides hazard maps and forecast, communicates with the CP on activation of the Special Plan (INFOCAT) and the according actions.	5-scale colour coded fire hazard index follows the European standard; 48h forecast; municipal level information on actions	GenCat CP and the Agricultural department websites.	Catalonia and sub-territories and municipalities	The Agricultural Dpt updates forest fire hazard maps twice daily and occasionally more often if needed. Up to municipal leaders to decide on warnings in high danger situations
Drought	Catalonian water agency (ACA) provides the warnings. Covered by the Special Drought Plan (PES)	A 6-scale colour coded index for drought state and scenarios Impact info, action recommendations and restrictions defined in the colour code legend (see, ACA, 2025)	Catalonian water agency (ACA) websites and bulletins.	Catalonia	Daily
Drought	Ebro basin drought danger information is provided by CHE & AEMET Covered by the Special Drought Plan (PES)	4-scale color coding used for water shortage PESs provide the action recommendations	CHE & AEMET websites	State and sub-territorial	Monthly

10.3.4 Multi-hazard Coordination

The disaster risk management cycle phases are addressed in the three levels of governance in Spain (see Table 7) by public authorities responsible of civil protection, and with regards to natural hazard and climate/ weather driven disasters, the Environmental and Health Ministries and their agencies at the state level and most importantly the meteorological agencies at both state and AC level are in key role at the assessment, preparedness and prevention of disasters. The meteorological agencies also take part in the decision-making on warnings issuing, coverage and content, as well as on dissemination. At the sub-territorial level, the DRM cycle phases are covered partly by the AC level agencies in terms of risk assessments, monitoring and observation, whereas the municipalities and sub-territorial governments have the main responsibility of preparedness, decision-making on warnings and response at the local level emergencies.

Table 7: Key responsible actors in the disaster risk management cycle at the three governance levels in Spain, and their inputs to each of the phases of the DRM cycle, illustrating the cross-governance interactions (developed by second author).

DRM Cycle phase	Val d'Aran	Catalonia	Spain
Risk assessment (RA)	DGPCC: assessments on the need for municipal action plans for specific risks The Avalanche Center of Val d'Aran (ACVA): avalanche risk and vulnerability maps	Directorate-General of Civil Protection of the Government of Catalonia (DGPCC), Ministry of Home Affairs and Public Security: RAs for the AC Civil Protection plan and Special Plans carried out together with relevant agencies, sub-territories and SMC	Directorate General of Civil Protection and Emergencies (DGPCE), Interior Ministry: Regular Civil Protection RAs by the DGPCE & relevant agencies; cross-border civil protection RAs, mainly for forest fires with France CP authorities. Environmental Ministry (MITECO): leads RAs for the relevant plans and strategies (see below), carried out with relevant agencies Ministry of Health: regular RA on the Effects of Excessive Temperatures on Health with AEMET
Preparedness & prevention	Municipalities: municipal emergency plans & specific action plans; preventive controlled fires Local businesses: HERMES Ski-resorts: contingency plans; preventive explosive triggering of avalanches Road authority: preventive explosive triggering of avalanches	DGPCC: The AC Civil Protection plan and Special Plans; regulation of the Private & third sectors' HERMES plans ACA: PES Public Health Agency of Catalonia (ASPCAT): Operational plan to prevent the effects of heat on health (POCS) (ASPCAT, 2024)	DGPCE: The National Civil Protection plan and Specific Plans MITECO: NAP, PGRI, Meteoalerta, Coastal Adaptation Strategy, Forest Fire Prevention Plans, PES Ministry of Health: National Plan for Preventive Actions against the Effects of Excessive Temperatures on Health

Detection & observation; Monitoring & Forecast	Arantec: local flood risk SMC: weather extremes ACVA: avalanches; assistance from Local avalanche experts on on-site avalanche observation	SMC: weather extremes	AEMET: weather extremes
Decision-making on warning	Mayors and municipal technicians: activation of 1 st level emergency & municipal plans consequently	DGPCC: activation of 2 nd level emergency & CP plans consequently; discussion with SMC and relevant agencies	DGPCE: activation of 3 rd level emergency & CP plans consequently; discussion with AEMET and relevant agencies
Issuing warnings (legal competence)	ACVA: avalanches	SMC: meteorological hazards ICGC: avalanches Directorate General for Forests and Environmental Management: forest fires ACA: drought hazards in Catalonian internal basins	AEMET: meteorological and avalanche hazards nationally National water agency: drought
Dissemination & communication on warning (see Ch 3.1)	Mayors and municipal technicians Conselh Generau d'Aran: flood risk	SMC, DGPCC, ASPCAT, ACA, all other relevant agencies: websites, social media, direct communication with relevant stakeholders DGPCC: Cell boadcast alerts	AEMET, DGPCE, all other relevant agencies: websites, social media, direct communication with relevant stakeholders Ministry of Health: communication on heat health risk through webpages; daily on-demand SMS/email service

Response	Municipalities: coordination of implementation of CP plans Conselh Generau d'Aran - Pompiers Emergencies (PE) & SC Aran: first response & coordination Local businesses: activation of HERMES; contribution to public response actions, e.g. excavation	DGPCC - CECAT: coordination of implementation of CP plans	DGPCE - CENEM: coordination of implementation of CP plans
Evaluation & feedback	Municipalities: municipal plans evaluated regularly or needs-based	DGPCC, SMC; all relevant agencies: all prevention & preparedness plans evaluated regularly or needs-based DGPCC: Feedback from citizens collected	DGPCE, MITECO, Ministry of Health, all relevant agencies: all prevention & preparedness plans evaluated regularly or needs-based

10.4. Strengths, Gaps, and Recommendations

This section outlines key strengths, gaps, and good practices of DRR activities and warning systems that were identified during the course of the research analysis. Some limitations and challenges were explicitly identified by interviewees given their expertise and experience, while others were identified through analysis by the researchers. However, the authors refrain from citing direct quotes from the interviewees to protect participant confidentiality. Recommendations on how to address the gaps and challenges are also provided. Good practices are highlighted as examples that can be transferred and scaled to other DEMs and potential areas to collaborate with other DEMs are also discussed.

10.4.1. Strengths and Good Practices

1. International Standardised Warnings through Cell Broadcast Technology

The main strength of the DRM systems in Spain is that it uses international standards for the warnings on all levels of governance, when applicable, i.e. for avalanches, weather, forest fire risks, and the cell broadcast alert, which enhances the accessibility for people coming from different regions and countries. In Catalonia, all official warnings/ alerts are provided in the two official languages, Catalan and Spanish, and in English. The cell broadcast alerts provide clear action recommendations during an emergency situation. The standardised web-based and cell broadcast warnings in use are provided in user-friendly simple and well understood colour codes and illustrations, with provisional information available through links or dropdown boxes etc. The drought warnings at the Catalanian internal basin region use similar user friendly simple and well understood colour codes and illustrations, with easily accessible provisional information available

through links on the webpages. In Val d'Aran the avalanche warning platform is based on an open access software that translates the content to several languages to enhance the accessibility.

2. Territorial hazard and risk expertise

The hazards covered with the Catalanian warning system are multiple and the risks and vulnerabilities to them are highly diverse depending on the location, in particular. Key advantages for managing this type of a multi-scale multi-hazard warning systems (MHEWS) in Catalonia is that, unlike most other Autonomous Communities of Spain, the Catalanian Government has own weather service (SMC) that has more territorially focused expertise in weather related issues and their consequences than the AEMET. In Val d'Aran the sub-territorial warning system for avalanches is highly developed building on the local hazard expertise. In a similar way, the premises for development of the warning systems for other hazards are exceptional with the regional weather and climate related hazard monitoring already in place by Arantec and UPC, based on excellent understanding of the territorial unique features and its history, commitment to enhance the robustness of the region, and tight networks with relevant stakeholders.

3. Specific action plans for Individual Hazards

The specific action plans for individual hazards at all levels of governance are central boundary elements in the DRM cycle with regards to the natural hazard and climate/ weather driven disasters. The Catalanian level special plans and the risk assessments are a useful tool in supporting the warning contents and issuing in emergency situations due to them being conducted with detail, expertise and collaboration, and revised regularly.

4. Cross-sectoral collaboration

The SMC has a direct connection with the relevant agencies, i.e. the CP, the Water Agency (ACA), ICGC, and sub-territories such as the Val d'Aran region, guided officially by the special plans action protocols, but developed also in practice through experience of managing the familiar hazards. The cross-sectoral communication is reinforced through the mandate provided to the expert agencies in issuing warnings and their legal responsibility of communicating with the relevant agencies regarding the hazards and warnings. The collaboration and work division/ responsibilities between the CP and the SMC regarding warnings is clearly defined in the emergency action protocol, which is considered particularly effective when issuing cell broadcast alerts. In similar way, the Avalanche Centre in Val d'Aran is collaborating very closely and fluently with the other stakeholders in the region that are dependent on their hazard expertise. These collaborations exemplify partnerships that have developed around management of familiar hazards.

5. Development of locally-led warning system

In general, the Val d'Aran region warning system is in development, which leaves a gap, yet offers an advantage position as similar sub-territorial warning systems are not a standard in Catalonia, and a locally led system development can be built in a more inclusive way than on top-down basis. In the Val d'Aran region, the development of the avalanche warning system is a good example of an inclusive process that has been led by the local stakeholders who understand the local needs and networks, in collaboration with the Catalanian and international expert community, and streamlined with international standards and utilizing technology to assist in inclusivity. Furthermore, in the Val d'Aran region, the competence given to the Aran Conseilh in 2015 on CP and emergency governance seems to have enhanced the preparedness for quick and larger scale actions than previously under the municipal lead.

10.4.2. Gaps and Challenges

1. The significant gap in the Catalonian warning system is the hydrological drought risks on the shared basins, including the Val d'Aran region, that are covered only by the coarse resolution and scarcely published national level data. Drought warnings of national rivers basins are not cohesive with the Catalonian system that provides easy-to-reach information for all users. The national hazard and warning information system seems to be directed mainly to the drought experts/administration. In this sense, the Val d'Aran region is also in a blind spot in terms of drought risk information currently. The local governments and communities in the shared basins region are hence in somewhat unjust position in comparison to those in the internal basins side in terms of the warnings.
2. In a similar way, the lack of landslide warnings can be seen as a distributive justice issue, as the risk of catastrophic landslide events related to flooding are expected to increase but those in danger are currently not provided with timely warnings, while resources are put into other warnings.
3. Key gaps in inclusivity of the Catalonian level warnings are the limitations in languages used that exclude those not speaking Catalan or Spanish. While all SMC and Civil Protection warnings/alerts are also provided in English, the further hazard information and warnings on droughts are not easily accessible for non-Spanish/Catalan speakers, and it is particularly difficult to find action recommendations for any hazardous situations in advance. The warnings issued by the SMC do not provide any descriptions on impact nor recommendations on actions.
4. The cell broadcast alerts do not reach everyone and for tourists, immigrants and language minorities without local social networks, interpretation of what to do in an emergency situation can be extremely difficult. Moreover, while the collaboration and work division between the Civil Protection and the SMC is impressively effective, the delay in issuing cell broadcast alerts based on meteorological data is currently considered too long due the bureaucracy, i.e. the obligatory gathering of the emergency commission. It is seen by the CP that an automatic alert system would be necessary to enhance the efficacy.
5. A key gap in terms of reaching all audiences with the warnings that are provided through two or three governance level organisations, is that it may be difficult for the public to decide which source to use and how to interpret potential inconsistencies. Furthermore, the alignment of warnings between the different levels requires additional work on communication between the offices. For example, the warnings issued by the SMC do not provide any recommendations on actions, whereas the AEMET warning legend introduces very general level brief description on impacts and recommendations. The avalanche warnings are another example of the incohesiveness as the AEMET provides general Zaragoza level avalanche warnings, the ICGC the general Catalonian level warnings and the Aran Avalanche Center the local detailed warnings in addition to the ski-resort specific warnings and it is difficult/ not even completely possible for the public to identify whether/how the sources of the warnings differ. In cases of the lower governance level agencies having a view of higher risk than the higher governance level agency, they usually have a better forecast due to local knowledge, however, the warning communication and action taking may be challenged due lack of clarity, for instance, in action protocol when the local avalanche risk bulletin considers a need for a road closure that is under the authority of the Catalonian government and the ICGC has not given similar risk forecast.
6. The key gap in the special action plan system as a MHEWS tool is that the local level special plans are not timely conducted. A limiting factor is currently that climate projections are not downscaled to enough detail to help do the local planning. In Val d'Aran, the Civil Protection

officials consider this problematic as the protocols for actions, including issuing warnings in emergency situations, is not clear to all actors.

7. The Val d'Aran territorial CP is mainly focused on first response thus far, but development on services for preparedness is in process. However, the uncertainties and unclarities in the governance duties between the municipalities and the regional government and CP seem to hamper this process to some degree.
8. The gaps in local warnings currently are due to lack of political and public interest. Landslide and drought hazards are yet relatively rarely occurring and cause less risks than the more familiar hazards in the region, namely avalanches and snow accumulation. They are hence not in the agenda of politicians nor interest the locals much. The last flood event in the region was in 2013 and while it caused unforeseen damage, floods are generally considered by the public as rarely occurring hazards for which preparedness is not considered a priority. Forest fires are considered as an increasingly emerging risk, however, the Aran Conseil lacks capacity and resources for the DRM.

10.4.3. Recommendations and Opportunities for Collaboration with other DEMs

1. To fill the gap in landslide warnings, promising work is in the development by the ICGC and the UPC, and it is important that this work gets recognized also through the legislative competence required to gain sufficient resources for effective warning systems. With public-private partnerships like those with ARANTEC in Spain, there are opportunities already in place to engage with DEM3, (Italy) on advancing landslide warning systems. Parallel processes in DEM6 (Iceland) might also be beneficial to share experiences further on landslide warnings. In Iceland, the warning system for landslides are also currently in development with IMO as the lead in this endeavour.
2. There is a pressing need for more effective coordination between the many systems across local, regional, and national levels. While Spain's civil protection is technically supposed to provide coordination across scales, there are limitations that occur in practice given the highly decentralised system and different political allegiances, as was evidenced in the case of the Valencia floods. Thus, learning from DEM3, Italy's Civil Protection system of coordination could prove highly valuable for Spain. Furthermore, DEM10 Switzerland's development of a supra-coordinating multi-hazard body that is not dependent or beholden to institutional or political interests, LAINAT, could be a way to tackle the obstacles that Spain currently faces.
3. There is a need for a regional warning system in Val d'Aran due to its unique hazard-scape and geography in comparison to the rest of the Catalonia. The premises for developing such system are exceptional due to the territorial hazard and risk expertise, committed actors and networks in place. Open local stakeholder workshops and feed-back systems could be used to increase commitment by the locals and increase the inclusivity of the process, learning from, e.g. DEM6.
4. For designing warnings on other local meteorological hazards than floods that are currently missing from the Val d'Aran level, it is recommended that the same international standards as with the flood risk info and by AEMET and SMC would be used to increase accessibility and reach of the warnings. Local drought warnings are not currently provided, but the Arantec system basically provides data on meteorological droughts and this could be useful starting point for developing a territorial early drought warning system to complement the drought information provided by the state (CHE). Exchange and learning with DEM9 (UK) could prove helpful to developing this further given their wide expertise on impact-based multi-hazard warnings.
5. The 2013 flood event and even more recent changes in the snow conditions are acknowledged by the local entrepreneurs as signs of changing hazard conditions that may be harmful to business

and the local community, hence, stressing the importance of finding solutions to manage the related risks. The private sector stakeholders raised the importance of local networks that hold historical and local knowledge on the hazard occurrence and management as key factors in building trust and successful collaboration between actors from public and private sector for developing risk management in changing conditions. For instance, a local excavation/ earth moving contractor is an important actor in avalanche and landslide event recovery, and they are in direct communication with the local CP in case of emergency, and they find new ways of supporting the response phase when new types of events occur as the 2013 flood event response phase has taught. To our knowledge, DEMs3, 9, and 10 work with a variety of partners and draw on the expertise of engineers and private firms to fill gaps.

11. DEM 3 Lattari Mountains, Italy

11.1. Overview and background

This section provides a description and analysis of the hazard management and warning system of Italy. A brief history of the Italian DRR system is outlined, with a focus on how past disasters triggered important changes and led to the current iteration and developments in its system. Based on interviews with national, regional, and municipal authorities as well as climate scientists, researchers, and citizen volunteers, this section outlines the strengths and gaps identified. We also provide recommendations on best practices and lessons learned for further improvement and collaboration with other DEMs. The main hazards that affect Italy and that authorities cover include:

- Hydrometeorological (Rain, Wind, and Thunderstorms)
- Landslides and mudslides
- Avalanches/snow
- Earthquakes
- Volcanic activity
- Tsunamis
- Forest fires

Along with these weather, climate, and geological risks, the Italian Civil Protection also covers health risks, nuclear risks, industrial hazards or major accidents, and large dam risks.

Case Study: Lattari Mountains, Italy

The aim of this research was to examine disaster risk governance and management and warning systems across scales from the national level to the regional and the municipal level. The study focused on the Lattari mountain area, which administratively is in the Campania region. Within the Campania region, the DRR/warning system was examined to evaluate how it operates regionally as well as locally in Amalfi municipality, Sorrento municipality, Atrani municipality, and Napoli municipality.

11.2. Disaster Risk Management and Warning System

In Italy, civil protection is not just the responsibility of a single administration but is instead managed through an integrated system, a framework developed through lessons learned from numerous experiences of trial and error. Certain disasters throughout Italian history have been particularly monumental in underlining limitations and advancing specific developments and policy measures in risk management. One of the first cases was the floods of Florence in 1966 in Florence. With the loss of 101 people and millions of artworks destroyed, it was considered one of the worst floods in Italy's modern history, gaining international attention (Anziano et al. 2022). Young volunteers from all over Italy and the world mobilised to rescue the cultural artifacts of Florence, giving birth to a phenomenon that would change the course of civil protection—the importance of volunteers and civic participation.

Just over a year later in 1968, a 6.5 magnitude earthquake struck Belice, Sicily killing 296 people and 100,000 people losing their homes (National Civil Protection Service). Compared to previous disasters, the Belice earthquake served to point out the many organisational gaps in the national civil protection system, building planning and measures, and response to disasters in the eyes of the public (). Aid, recovery, and reconstruction efforts were delayed for months and even dragged on for years. During this time, the emergency management model lacked coordination or any coordination mechanisms, as was evidenced by the formal admission by the Government after the disaster of the 1966 floods. With Law n. 241/1968, the government decided to adopt a centralized approach and manage recovery and reconstruction directly from Rome. However, soon after this all changed after the establishment of regions and preference to decentralize functions to the Regions and local bodies.

In 1976, things were managed differently compared to previous disasters. The Friuli earthquake was a magnitude 6.4 quake that killed around 990 people and injured thousands. However, the arrival of relief and resources was very rapid, with military forces mobilized quickly to provide recovery efforts to the population. Giuseppe Zamberletti was entrusted leading the rescue and recovery operations and given the role of Extraordinary Commissioner for the emergency response by the prime minister. Zamberletti decided to create local coordination centers at the Municipal level and put army officers alongside the Mayors in the area. Things quickly began to work effectively and in coordination. The crisis was overcome in three months—a massive change from previous disasters that took years and even decades. Compared to Belice, for example, with the help of a coordinated local operation and military support, there was swift aid provided, evacuation of those in affected areas, and good communication and transportation systems to assist the population.

Thus, the Friuli earthquake was a defining moment in Italy's journey of disaster management, aptly called the 'Friuli model.' Zamberletti's use of local operational centers was established with regional governments and mayors working closely together, which previously had been managed at the central level. These operational centers aimed to create a managing body, led by the mayor, composed of representatives of public and private administrations in each municipality, giving mayors and citizens a vital role in the management, response, and reconstruction of disasters. The Friuli earthquake also prompted the development of modern building codes in Italy and initiated changes in Italian efforts to identify distinct seismic zones throughout the country.

Then in 1980, the need for a national civil protection body was cemented following the Irpinia earthquake. The dramatic delay of recovery and relief operations, caused by the uncertainty of the epicenter and congestion of the road system, highlighted the urgency to establish a structure to deal with civil protection on a permanent basis. Under the guidance of Zamberletti, the Civil Protection Department was officially established in 1982, with which civil protection and emergency services were placed directly under the highest government figure, the President of the Council of Ministers. Law no. 225 of 1992 the Civil Protection Code was established and the National Civil Protection Service was born, enriching it with new tasks and responsibilities.

The new Law broadened scope of risk management beyond the concept of civil protection as a mere initiative of effective public assistance and response. The response or relief phase was framed as the third element on a cycle of four phases, starting from the forecast of risks of the territory to prevention and preparedness measures. The fourth phase, 'emergency overcoming' includes a series of interventions needed to ensure the return to normal activities, with which acceptable living conditions after a catastrophe can be quickly restored. Law n. 225/1992 brought three fundamental values to the sector, which are until today the basis of the civil protection system:

1. The awareness that an effective civil protection system must pre-exist prior to the event and cannot be improvised ad hoc in an emergency context;

2. The need for a civil protection presidium, previously identified and localized in all Italian municipalities, which, according to the principle of subsidiarity, are responsibly called to operate every day for the safety and protection of their citizens;
3. The understanding that, in order to guarantee the necessary intervention capacity in the case of emergency events, it is necessary to involve organized volunteering.

The principles of subsidiarity and integration have been the most significant in bringing the contextualized management of events closer to communities and citizens (see figure 49 below). The 1992 Law that gave birth to the current civil protection system was reformed in 2018 by the Civil Protection Code. The 2018 Code is a unified and simple text pulling together and modifying all previous legislation regulating the sector.

Figure 49: How Subsidiarity works in Italian Civil Protection System – Source: Italian CP (from presentation shared with author)

11.3. Governance Structure and MHWS

The Italian civil protection system named the National Civil Protection Service is a multi-level organizational structure: the system is based on the constitutional principle of subsidiarity (Italian Constitution, art. 118) which from the first level, the Mayor, rises to the provincial or regional level up to the national level. It includes both the structures and the activities put in place to protect life, property, and the environment from all risks deriving from disasters through forecasting, prevention, emergency management, and emergency response.

According to Art. 1 of Legislative Decree n. 1/2018 – Civil Protection Code:

“The National Civil Protection Service [...] defined as a public utility service, is the system that performs the civil protection function consisting of the set of skills and activities aimed at protecting life, physical integrity, property, settlements, animals and the environment from damage or danger of damage resulting from disasters of natural origin or deriving from human activity.”

The Italian civil protection is a complex system entrusted to all administrative levels of the State. A “central” national department (under the direct control of the Prime Minister) coordinates a network of regional centres, each one in charge of forecasting and managing hazards inside its administrative territory, while at the local level the most important authority of civil protection is the mayor of each municipality. Other bodies (e.g., provinces) constitute an intermediate level between the municipality and the regions, ensuring an effective management of complex hazard scenarios.

It is set up as a whole-of-society system in which responsibility for risk prevention, mitigation, and response actively includes the national, regional, and local authorities but also every citizen. It involves the collaboration of state administrations, the scientific community, the private sector, and civil society.

Under Italian legislation and norms, citizens have both a right and duty of civil protection. It is therefore both “the duty of institutions to protect citizens but it is also a duty for the citizen, who has the obligation to know the risks to which his/her territory is subject and to adopt appropriate behaviour and self-protection measures. This way a group of citizens can be transformed into a resilient community” (5).

The system under Civil Protection includes:

- Prevention
- Risk Assessment
- Forecasting
- Preparedness
- Early Warnings
- Emergency Response and Overcoming

Prevention is one of the civil protection activities identified by Law no. 225 of 1992, later referred to the Civil Protection Code of 2018. It consists of all activities aimed at avoiding or reducing possible damage in the event of a disaster. Prevention activities include the alerting of the National Service, the civil protection planning, and training of service operators. Further significant preventive actions also entail the information to the population, the promotion and organisation of exercises at every territorial level.

Risk assessment is a cornerstone of the Italian system. The most recent document on risk assessment was issued by the Civil Protection Department in 2021 and consists of a summary of the relevant elements of risk assessment and management capacity, focusing on prevention and

preparedness measures. It aims to address the risks affecting the country and those that could lead to multinational transboundary effects.

Risk Management Planning and emergency plans are necessary to prepare the civil protection structures to face and manage an emergency. The Italian civil protection law requires that the local Disaster Management plan must be drawn up according to the criteria and the procedures of the guidelines adopted by the National Civil Protection System and the regional governments. Moreover, the legislation requires the local Disaster Management plans to be sent to the Region, the Prefecture and the Province for wide information. Each municipality is required to draw up its own plan with (i) the information on the features and on the structure of the territory and (ii) the lines of planning and the intervention model to provide a suitable response to any emergency. The plan is a series of intervention and operative procedures to cope with any expected calamity in a territory. It integrates the forecasting and prevention plans and allows the authorities to prepare and coordinate the relief interventions to protect the population and the cultural heritage in a risk area. For nuclear and volcanic risks, specific plans are drawn up nationally.

Risk Awareness and Preparedness are carried out in collaboration with all relevant actors. Municipal plans and local exercises are fundamental tools to inform citizens about the risks affecting their territory and on rules of conduct to adopt in an emergency. At the national level, risk information and communication are carried out by specific initiatives to promote the culture of civil protection, including the national campaign, *I Don't Take Risks* (in Italian: "Io non rischio") campaign, which will be discussed later. Trainings and exercises are regularly carried out with civil protection authorities at the national, regional, and local level.

11.3.1. Multi-hazard Warnings in Italy

Warnings and the communication of alerts falls under the prevention activities provided in the Civil Protection Code. Currently, warnings are issued for meteorological, hydraulic and hydrogeological risks through the network of regional Functional Centres responsible for issuing Warnings of adverse weather conditions and Bulletins/Alerts of hydrogeological and hydraulic criticalities. On the basis of the criticality levels expressed in the hydrogeological and hydraulic criticality Bulletins and highlighted in the regional criticality Warnings, the Presidents of the Regions and Autonomous Provinces establish the different alert levels for the territory.

The decentralised functional centres of the Regions concur in the management of the National Warning System. Each one of the 21 Italian regions and autonomous provinces (19 regions and the autonomous provinces of Trento and Bolzano) has a regional "functional centre" in charge of meteorological monitoring and forecasting. This activity includes a warning system for hazards covering the whole region and issuing, at least daily, a criticality state among four possible levels (absent, ordinary, medium, and high). To improve the forecasting effectiveness and the emergency response, regions are subdivided into alert zones (170 in total), each monitored and alerted independently. Every criticality level is coded with a colour (green, yellow, orange and red) and is characterized by a standardized description of the typical scenario expected on the alert zone. Each functional centre carries out in real time forecasting, monitoring and surveillance activities on weather phenomena. Each day the forecast is summarised and published in the 'bulletin of criticality' issued daily by the regional department. The bulletins of criticality of each region are then published on the main civil protection website (see figures below). There are 170 warning zones in the entire country and 8 in Campania region.

Figure 50: Daily Warning Bulletin issued by the Campania Regional Functional Centre (Source: picture taken of computer screen by lead author during interview with permission)

Figure 51: Network of Regional Functional Centers issues Bulletins and Warnings reporting both the evolution of hazardous phenomena and the criticality levels expected (Source: Italian CP)

The alerts issued by the regional centre are addressed to the mayors of the municipalities of the alert zones, which are in charge of activating all actions and response measures. These actions should be carefully planned and written in the civil protection/emergency plan, which is compulsory for every municipality. The plan contains a detailed description of the scenarios expected at the municipality level, a careful planning of the emergency response through objectives, strategies and personnel and means to be activated. The plan also describes the management procedures and how to convey the necessary information to the citizens. Each regional functional centre has developed their own warning system based on statistical rainfall thresholds, for floods and weather-induced landslides. Statistical techniques are then used to find a relationship between some rainfall parameters (e.g. rainfall intensity and duration) and the minimum rainfall conditions associated with floods, also considering the area of the river basins, and landslide triggering.

Functional centres report both the evolution of expected and/or ongoing phenomena, and the criticality levels (type, diffusion and severity of landslides and floods) assessed for the area under their jurisdiction. It is the job of the Regions and the Autonomous Provinces to issue alerts for local civil protection systems, while it is up to the Mayors to activate the Civil Protection Plans, inform citizens of risk situations and decide the actions to be taken to protect the population.

Figure 52: Italian 4-coloured Warning Map (Source: [Italian Civil Protection](#))

Figure 53: Italian Warning Bulletins and Surveillance Map (Source: [Italian Civil Protection](#))

11.3.2. Warning Sequence and Chain of Responsibility

Regions and autonomous provinces issue alerts for the local civil protection systems, whereas mayors are responsible for activating emergency plans and public information. According to the Italian regulations, the municipality is a key actor of the National Civil Protection System – structured in national, regional and local levels – and has the task to manage critical situations and assess and integrate disaster risk information at the local scale. Thus, mayors are the first line of response for managing and coordinating relief as well as assisting the population and organizing the available resources according to agreed emergency plans to counter specific risks on their territories. The mayor is responsible for transmitting alerts to the population, however, since there is no national regulation or indication for such specific tasks, this communication of alerts and warnings differs from municipality to municipality.

The warning is issued to the population once the regional functional centre transmits to the municipality the colour-code assigned to the connected alert zone. The communication to the citizens can be entrusted to the management of the municipal civil protection office (if present in the municipality), the press office, or the mayor secretariat, with the contribution of all the municipal personnel competent in these matters and the whole civil protection system (for example volunteering or first responders such as fire fighters) (see figure 54).

Figure 54: Warning Sequence (Source: From presentation shared by Dr. Michele Cavello)

In Italy, the mayors are the first Civil Protection Authority responsible for providing the population with adequate information on civil protection issues. Municipal plans and local exercises are fundamental tools to inform citizens about the risks affecting their territory and on rules of conduct to adopt in an emergency. At the national level, risk information and communication are carried out by specific initiatives to promote the culture of civil protection.

Operative Municipal Centre (COC)

In case of a local level emergency the mayor activates the Municipal Operations Centre (COC). If the Municipality cannot manage the event, the Provincial level is activated through the CCS (Rescue Coordination Centre) chaired by the Prefect. If an event happens at the provincial level, the Region then is in charge. The Council of Ministers may declare a National State of Emergency before or during an event that for its intensity and extension calls for immediate intervention and use of extraordinary means and powers. At the local level, according to the Campania's contingency planning guidelines, assistance to children, families, elderly and disabled people is guaranteed through a specific support function called "assistenza alla popolazione" activated in COC (Giunta Regionale della Campania Assessorato alla Protezione Civile, linee guida per la redazione dei Piani di Emergenza Comunale (February 2013), p. 21).

11.3.3. Warning Design and Content

The National, State and Regional Alerting System consists of 2 phases: (i) forecasting, aimed at assessing, when and where possible, the expected situation and possible outcomes; and (ii) monitoring and surveillance, to supervise the evolution of a situation and its possible impacts on the territory. The information to be included in warning messages in the criticality bulletin that is issued daily include:

- Colour-code of the criticality level;
- Municipality where the alert takes place;
- Risk type (in this case landslide risk): municipalities are often exposed to different risks and risk scenarios, which are considered in municipal civil protection planning and must be clearly specified in the alert messages;
- Alert duration: the duration of the alert should always be provided; the exact hour of start and end of duration of alerts is an information not precisely relatable to the actual period of risk. A qualitative description of the alert duration is more advisable for communication purposes (for example “in the evening of 4 November”);
- “Simplified” and updated event description: weather forecasts and regional warnings are provided at a larger scale than municipalities. Furthermore, the actual ground effect of weather conditions (event scenarios) can considerably vary depending on the specific features of the territory and structures. Therefore, in the message to the people, the description of the weather forecast and criticality level must be contextualized and made relevant to the territory, referring to some local issues and risk scenarios, using terms understandable to the general public;
- Safe behaviours to employ before, during and after an event; the transmission of self-protective rules to the population, whenever possible, is best done using info- graphics, images, photos or links.

The alert levels, uniform on the national territory and ordered by increasing severity degrees, are: yellow, orange and red alert. The civil protection authorities operating in the area match the operational phases (attention, pre-alarm and alarm) with the alert levels. The operational phases have to be activated according to the civil protection plans. In particular, the Municipality, depending on the alert received, activates the most appropriate operational phase to field the resources necessary to face the expected or ongoing event in its territory, also by informing its citizens, who have, in turn, the duty to implement self-protection behaviors.

11.3.4 Communication, Dissemination, and Delivery of Warnings

For all alert levels, the municipality website and variable-message signs (VMS) have been placed higher up in the list of communication channels since each municipality should have its own institutional site, which should be made known to the citizens and always be kept updated. There are also signs put in main places and infrastructures of a municipality (e.g. bus stops, along important communication roads, at the entrance of the city) and are the main means to reach also non-residents.

During a yellow alert, additional communication channels that can be activated are specific mobile apps and social networks, including Facebook and Twitter. Citizens receive information whenever an alert is issued, in some cases, they provide other relevant information such as risk maps and civil protection plans. Facebook and Twitter are the two most used social networks in Italy that are also suited to real-time and institutional communication.

During the orange and red alerts, emails and instant messaging applications are recommended over social networks. Specific apps are still preferred because, in the case of emails and instant messaging applications (like WhatsApp), the citizens have to register to a service and provide personal information.

Concerning the red alert, a further means of communication to the citizen can be the phone call, that is the information service that transmits a pre-recorded message of the mayor, which must be concise to be effective. This channel has been placed after Municipality website and VMS in terms of priority and is recommended only for the red alert because it has the strongest impact on the people risk perception and it should be reserved when the risk is at its highest and the possibility of a false alarm is low; furthermore, this service can be expensive for a municipality with little economic resources.

11.3.5 Multi-hazard Coordination

The Italian system takes a whole of Society approach coordinated under the civil protection system which involves government bodies, universities, scientific research institutes, and civil society. This collaboration is recognised and formalised through Competence Centres. Art. 21 of the Legislative Decree n. 1/2018 under the Civil Protection Competence Centres states that, within the Scientific Community and in line with the risks of civil protection:

“Research bodies and institutes, consortia and university structures make available knowledge and provide research and innovation products that can be integrated in civil protection activities, can be included among the Competence Centres. They provide services, information, data and technical-scientific contributions and elaborations in specific areas. These centres include research Institutions and Universities, but also State Administrations, Agencies and Basin Authorities.”

Competence Centres are often involved in emergency activities, during which risk or residual risk assessments, definitions of impact scenarios and monitoring of ongoing phenomena need to be carried out. In addition to the contribution to research, the Competence Centers, each for the subjects and risks they are called to contribute to the system, participate in the training activities of the operators of civil protection and information dissemination to citizens, with the aim of promoting the adoption of aware behavior and self-protection measures, as well as to provide information to the population on risk scenarios and on the good practices to be adopted. Furthermore, very often the Competence Centers contribute to information campaigns and exercise activities related to emergency planning implemented at national level, promoted by the Civil Protection Department.

11.4. Strengths, Gaps, and Recommendations

This section outlines key strengths, gaps, and good practices of DRR activities and warning systems that were identified during the course of the research analysis. Some limitations and challenges were explicitly identified by interviewees given their expertise and experience, while others were identified through analysis by the researchers. However, the authors refrain from citing direct quotes from the interviewees to protect participant confidentiality. Recommendations on how to address the gaps and challenges are also provided. Good practices are highlighted as examples that can be transferred and scaled to other DEMs and potential areas to collaborate with other DEMs are also discussed.

11.4.1 Strengths and Good Practices

1. Coordination and Integration through one Body- Civil Protection

The Italian case boasts a unique system of civil protection with an expanded role that goes beyond the general activities of response and emergency relief activities generally associated with civil protection in other countries to one in which prevention, preparedness, forecasting and monitoring, warning, mitigation, and recovery are all covered and coordinated by the civil protection through national, regional, and municipal offices as well as through collaborations with research institutes and the private sector. This provides a coordinated approach that is integrated vertically (top-down) across scales as well as facilitates data sharing between the national and regional authorities. However, given this expanded role there remain some limitations, including integration with the municipal level and bottom-up approaches which will be discussed further in the gaps section.

2. Comprehensive Scope of Multi-hazard risks Covered

The system set up in Italy serves as a best practice for a comprehensive multi-hazard system that covers a wide range of hazards. This wide scope includes hydrometeorological hazards and climate-related risks but also geophysical hazards, volcanic hazards, forest fires, and tsunamis. Following the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (2015-2030) guidance and the Hazard Profile guidelines, other hazards are also included- industrial hazards and accidents, nuclear, and health hazards. Multiple risks and hazards are monitored centrally in different departments of civil protection, but also across the country at specific institutes and competence centres.

3. Strong Citizen participation and Volunteering through Exercises and Campaigns

What is exceptional is the large number of volunteers and citizen participation in Italy both through the volunteer services in the national civil protection but also through the organisation of national disaster risk awareness campaigns and simulation exercises. The “Io non Rischio” or “I don't take risks” campaign was established in 2011 to promote awareness and information on the major risks affecting Italy and explains the measures and actions to adopt before, during and after an emergency. Cities around Italy have booths with volunteers promoting disaster risk awareness and education (see figure 55 below). Over the last few years, “I don't take risks” started being promoted in schools as well with a project designed to spread civil protection practices among the youth.

Figure 55: Nation-wide Campaign on DRR, Io non Rischio/I don't take Risks (Source: <https://iononrischio.protezionecivile.it/en/know/story/>)

There are also many simulation exercises that take place in localities on specific hazards, particularly on larger scale events such as volcanic eruptions. The majority of these simulation exercises have included civil protection authorities at the national, regional, and municipal level as well as civil protection volunteers. Most recently, however, the "Exe Flegrei 2024" in the Campania region was held in the volcanic risk red zones on Oct. 12, 2024, which included the public and provided information on hazard and what to do in case of a volcanic eruption. There have also been two annual National Civil Weeks to open up and share with the public the work of the civil protection.

4. Risk Education in Schools

A recent law in 2019, Law n. 92 has established that risk information and civil protection be taught in the national education program as part of the compulsory course of Civil Education. The text was designed to provide teachers, who work with students from 6 to 19 years old, with a wide range of detailed subjects, including historical, technical, scientific, operational and policy-making topics. The scope and depth of this work has been published in a textbook as a useful source of information for schools education but also wider audiences. This has helped to foster a culture of prevention and increasing public awareness and preparedness for disaster risks. In Italy 24 universities and numerous other organisations also offer courses on disaster risk reduction and management.

11.4.2 Gaps and Challenges

1. While vertical integration between the national civil protection and regional functional centres are strong, integration with downstream actors of municipalities still faces challenges. In addition, there is a need for horizontal integration between the different functional centres throughout the country. There is a major challenge of capacity between regions. There is a general recognition among civil protection actors that the northern regions have stronger capacities and resources for meteorology and climate science, which includes the functional centres of Emilia-Romagna, Venezia, Lazio, Lombardia, and Piemonte, which have large teams of hazard and flood specialists, meteorologists, hydrologic engineers, while the majority of regional functional centres in Southern Italy do not even have meteorologists in their centres nor the capacity to forecast and monitor risks in their region and therefore this is relegated to the central CP in Rome. Thus, the system of local monitoring and contextualism that is one of the good practices becomes flawed if it is not practiced across all regions. The Campania regional functional centre currently has one meteorologist on duty, working during office hours, presenting challenges during emergency situations where staff is needed to monitor the weather situation and rain gauges during all hours. This lack of harmonisation of capacity trickles down to municipalities as well, whereby monitoring and managing risks depends on the current staff's willingness, resources, and capacities. For example, in this study we focused on four municipalities, Salerno, Amalfi, Atrani, and Sorrento. The mayor and staff at Amalfi municipality have expressed a strong desire to have their own data and monitor data and sensors, given flood and landslide risks in the area and thus have developed a close collaboration with HuT DEM partners. Meanwhile, Sorrento municipality is happy following the minimal requirements stipulated in the civil protection code and relegates all monitoring activities to the regional centre. Atrani, on the other hand, neighboring Amalfi, aims to do more with regards to warnings but does not have the capacity or human resources to do so.
2. The Italian case is different from the other four DEMs in the study in that it lacks a civilian meteorological service that the entire country uses. Unlike other countries, meteorological services in Italy are operated by the Italian Meteorological Service (Servizio Meteorologico dell'Aeronautica Militare), an organizational unit of the Italian Air Force. This approach has been criticized for many reasons, namely placing military priorities above civilian priorities. Another challenge this poses is that each regional functional centre uses whichever weather models they

prefer and rely upon, resulting in different weather models used across the functional centres throughout the country. This could potentially lead to challenges when dealing with hazards that extend beyond one region. When speaking with meteorologists at the regional centres, they expressed the need for standard of practice for weather models as each uses a different model and approach to weather forecasting. Models that are used in Italy include COSMO and the EU ECWMF. Each Functional Center has the task of collecting and sharing with the entire network of Centers a series of data and information from different technological platforms and from a dense network of sensors located throughout the Country. In addition, although a civilian meteorology service was established by law in 2017, the Meteorology and Climatology Agency or ItaliaMeteo, it is still not fully in service due to competing roles. It has been a lengthy and continuing process to figure out what the establishment of ItaliaMeteo will mean for the regional functional centres and how it would work and be streamlined with the national civil protection weather services.

3. Lack of Harmonisation between municipalities in communicating and disseminating warnings—including channels used and warning design. The municipalities have the full authority and responsibility to communicate and deliver warnings issued by the regional functional centres in any manner and channel they choose. This provides important contextualisation for the particular cultural and social needs of each municipality but because there is no standard guidance that all municipalities could use to design their warnings, this could pose challenges moving between cities, especially since the majority of municipalities in the Campania region are very small and neighbor each other closely. Furthermore, due to differing levels of resources and capacities between municipalities, there is limited efforts in disseminating warnings through effective messaging, warning design, and multiple channels of communication (see figure 56a and b below on two different warning signs in the same administrative region). As shown in the figure, Sorrento municipality, which has a strong tourism industry and therefore more resources, warning signage is affixed permanently on wooden posts with messaging, measures to take or prohibited actions, stated ordinance associated with the warning, and translated into four languages. On the other hand, a small municipality next to Amalfi, Atrani municipality, also gets tourists but is much smaller and has a warning sign that has fallen on the ground, posted on laminated paper with no clear messaging nor language.
4. Another gap is the limited training that is given to the downstream levels of the municipalities and mayors. While Lombardy approved a Regional Standard for civil protection training in the 1990s, there is currently a lack of training for mayors and municipal authorities. The municipal authorities' ability to warn, act and respond is dependent on their own capacity, resources, strengths, and even individuals—there is no harmonisation or standardisation at municipal level. This has created many challenges at the municipal level with regards to roles and responsibilities as well as turn-over and sustainability of knowledge/expertise.
5. While weather data and data on rain gauges is shared on the national civil protection website, we were informed during interviews that this data is in different scales (e.g. hours vs days) and inconsistent with what is needed, posing challenges to data that the regional functional centres can use. User-friendly data and data-sharing between authorities at multiple scales were cited during interviews as needed to improve.

Figure 56a: Warning Sign in Sorrento affixed on wooden post (left), and Figure 55b: Warning Sign in Atrani fallen on the ground (right). Source: Photos taken by lead author

11.4.3 Recommendations and Opportunities for Collaboration with other DEMs

1. Since both Italy and Switzerland follow the subsidiary approach, whereby responsibility first falls to the local authorities, Italian partners can highly benefit from learning from the Swiss DEM 10 on its standard training to municipalities. Currently, mayors who come to office generally have no training on DRR, emergency response, or warning communication even though this is a required responsibility. During the study, mayors and municipal staff expressed how challenging decision-making is before and during disaster risks, and emphasised the need to understand and manage risks on how to effectively communicate with the public.
2. Italian partners can also learn from DEM 9 and DEM 10 on how to effectively carry out post-event analysis, evaluations, and reviews. Due to major emphasis on liability—there is a gap on post-event assessments, evaluation, and lessons learned in Italy. There have been many cases of scientists and/or authorities being tried and taken to court for not warning the public in a timely manner or mistakes made in the management of disaster response. In DEM 9, certain authorities are protected from prosecution, but they still carry out public investigations or inquiries. Meanwhile in DEM 10, they have an effective system of post-event reviews that does not blame individuals or agencies but includes a collaborative process of lessons learned, gaps, and changes and revisions necessary to improve the entire system.
3. While all warning bulletins issued by the regional functional centres are synthesised together and posted on the national civil protection website on a map, it is very difficult to discern. The map has limited information, without any information on the warning, the impacts of the hazard, or recommended actions to take. This information may already be written on different platforms, but currently is not all consolidated for daily warnings, which would make communicating and disseminating information with the public much easier and effective. Thus, the Italian DEM can

greatly benefit from learning from DEM 9 and DEM 10 on their national warning approach on the MET office website or national Hazard platform website, respectively. Both of these provide an open-access national platform whereby all information on warnings can be found with added information on impacts, location, timeframe, recommended actions to take, and where to go for further information. Additionally, there are apps that residents can download to receive this information on their phones. Currently, there is no national-level app for any warnings, including a national weather app or civil protection app, although the web portal of the national civil protection also features a specific version for smart phones, however it is not clear the extent to which the public uses this or is aware of it. When visiting Rome for the Civil Protection Open Days, representatives expressed that this is one of the key next steps national civil protection is planning to implement—a national civil protection app. Collaborating with the other DEMs on how they developed their apps and challenges they faced would be a productive learning for Italy.

4. Italian partners can collaborate with DEM 6 and DEM 10 on how to enforce the updating of emergency plans and hazard maps. Currently, at the municipal scale, emergency plans should be updated, but these plans are not validated or verified strictly at the national level by civil protection. In Switzerland, the cantons verify and keep copies of municipal emergency plans to ensure consistency and coherence but also provide support to municipalities. In both Iceland and Switzerland, there are validated hazard maps depicting hazard areas and evacuation zones in the case of an emergency. Iceland has recently developed hazard maps for landslides and this could be a great opportunity for Italy and Iceland to work together, given Italy's expertise in landslide monitoring.

12.DEM 9 Dorset, UK

12.1. Overview and background

This section provides a description and analysis of the risk management and warning system of the UK. First, a brief history of the UK system is outlined with a focus on how past disasters triggered important changes and led to the current iteration of its system of disaster risk management. Based on interviews with national, regional, and local stakeholders, we outline the strengths, challenges, and gaps identified and provide recommendations on best practices and lessons learned on ways to improve the system. The main natural hazards that affect the UK and that authorities cover include:

- Storms and storm surges
- High winds
- Coastal and fluvial flooding
- Coastal inundation
- Rain and Snow
- Climatic risks
- Landslides
- Heatwaves
- Wildfires
- Snow and avalanches
- Extreme heat

This section is based on a review of grey literature and DRM organisations websites, risk and hazard management reports, on-site observations, and 24 stakeholder interviews conducted with national, regional (Dorset county) and local stakeholders from the UK MET Office, British Geological Survey (BGS), Environment Agency (EA), Flood Forecasting Centre (FFC), Civil Contingency, Local councils, and public and voluntary organisations, as well as with residents and experts. Interviews were conducted in English and German during March 2024.

Case Study: Dorset Coast, UK

Dorset is a county in Southwest England on the English Channel coast. Its Jurassic Coast is included as a UNESCO World Heritage site. It represents a key tourist destination with a high economic value (2019: £1.8B >30M visitors, 41K jobs), with multiple areas exhibiting vulnerability to climate-related hazards throughout the year. The area is affected by multiple precipitation-induced hazards (intense rainfall, coastal/fluvial/pluvial flooding, landslide, storms and storm surges, coastal inundation) which cause significant impacts to communities. These hazards can occur as singular events or as compound/cascading events.

Dozens of landslides and rockfalls have struck the Jurassic Coast since 2012, when a young woman was killed by rockfall from a 160ft cliff collapse in Burton Bradstock two miles east of West Bay beach (see figure 57). It was reported that approximately 400 tons of rock fell in two rock-fall events approximately 20 minutes apart (BGS 2012). The BGS Landslide Response Team carried out a survey of the site, including a LiDAR survey logged onto the BGS National Landslide Database.

Figure 57: Rockfall near West Bay in April 2021 (Source: James Loveridge)

In April 2021, a large rockfall occurred between Seatown and Eype Beach in Dorset county, described as the biggest rockfall in sixty years, with boulders the size of cars plummeting to the beach (Millen 2021). There have been many rockfalls more recently in the area, including this past December in West Bay, blocking the beach between Freshwater and West Bay (Qurashi 2024). There have been others in the same area in October 2024 and the coastal path has been closed for some time, warning tourists and residents alike that the cliffs are unstable. Two major landslips occurred at Lulworth cove in early 2024 after days of heavy rainfall (BBC News 2024).

Geologists at BGS explained that parts of the Jurassic coastline are particularly prone to landslips and rockfalls due to extremely varying forms of rock structure and erosion (see figure 58 below). The cliffs in Burton Bradstock, for example, are made up of sandstone rock that is porous and acts like a sponge with rainwater, which seeps down through it and weakens it over time (Morgan 2024).

Landslide monitoring and observation occurs by the coastal rangers and by the Dorset Council. It is hoped that nowcast cell tracking methods, being developed within the Met Office, can be tested with a specific focus on providing improved situational awareness and storm evolution information.

Figure 58: Mapped Landslides on the Jurassic Coast from 2012-2024 (Source: Daily Mail Online with data from BGS)

12.2. Disaster Risk Management and Warning System

The UK Government regularly produces an assessment of the risks of civil emergencies facing the UK over the period of five years, known as the National Security Risk Assessment (NSRA). This classified risk assessment brings together the key risks that have the potential to cause a significant disruption in the UK. The NSRA provides Government and local responders with the means to prioritize and proportionately prepare for a range of eventualities. The public facing version of this assessment, the National Risk Register (NRR), is a resource for individuals and organizations wishing to be better prepared for emergencies. The NRR provides information, advice and access to resources on natural and anthropogenic hazards that pose a potential civil emergency risk including potential size and scale, likelihood and impact.

The first stage in producing the NRA is identifying the hazards that could impact the UK. This is primarily undertaken within the Government. Each hazard is 'owned' by a government department, which is responsible for identifying the 'reasonable worst-case scenario' for each hazard, and for determining its potential impact and likelihood. This permits comparison of each hazard type for prioritisation in emergency planning. Although the Civil Contingencies Secretariat (CCS) issues risk owners with common guidance on the assessment procedure, methodologies for estimating impacts and likelihoods vary between departments, and hence between different hazards. The assessments undertaken by departmental risk owners are compiled by the CCS for publication in the NRA.

The UK was one of the first countries to produce a national-level risk assessment and remains a world leader in this policy area (Stock and Wentworth 2019). However, several limitations have been identified in the risk assessment process, principally associated with: limited opportunities for bottom-up and non-governmental engagement, assessing the cumulative effects of multiple or concurrent hazards, and the exclusion of long-term trends, such as climate change, from consideration (Stock and Wentworth 2019).

Like in the other DEMs, the UK has experienced a number of disasters and severe natural hazard events that have been instrumental to key developments in its risk management system and governance structure. One of the most notable ones, both for its significant impacts and leading to important changes were the 2007 summer floods that affected 55,000 properties, costing £3.2 billion (EA 2007).

Following the devastating floods of 2007, the Pitt Review was commissioned to appraise all aspects of flood risk management in England. It contained 92 recommendations addressed to the government, local authorities, Local Resilience Forums, providers of essential services, insurers and others, including the general public. The review found that the UK system of providing information on potential natural hazard risks and delivering warnings, was too disjointed and scientific information was not translated appropriately into actionable and usable information (EA 2007; Cabinet Office 2008). The Pitt Review highlighted the need for “a national framework to help reduce the risks to the delivery of essential services resulting from natural hazards” (EA 2007: xxviii-xxix). It also recommended improving resource integration between scientific organisations, governmental departments, and emergency responders. This led to the formation of the Flood Forecasting Centre (FFC) in 2011, a joint undertaking between the Environment Agency (EA) and the Met Office. The FFC successfully demonstrated the benefits of cross-organisational and multi-agency collaboration to improve public services and warnings (Hemingway and Gunawan 2018).

The success of the FFC led to a desire to explore what further advantages could be gained by creating additional partnerships to provide an ‘all hazards’ approach to disaster mitigation. During 2010, the British Geological Survey (BGS), the EA, Met Office, and the Ordnance Survey undertook a feasibility project to assess ways to collaborate on a broader set of hydro-meteorological hazards. This resulted in the formation of the Natural Hazard Partnership (NHP) in 2011 (Hemingway and Gunawan 2018). The NHP brings together 22 public sector organisations and government departments to facilitate collaboration on disaster risk reduction research and advice.

12.3. Governance Structure and MHWS

Key legislation and policies in the UK delineating the structure of risk and emergency management include:

- [Civil Contingencies Act 2004](#) – A framework for civil protection in the UK.
- [UK national guidance on risk assessment](#) - How the level of risk posed to the UK is assessed nationally and locally, covering the National Risk Assessment and National Risk Register.
- [National Risk Register 2020](#) - This document outlines the key malicious and non-malicious risks that could affect the UK in the next two years, and provides resilience guidance for the public.
- [Emergency preparation, response and recovery](#) - What the UK government is doing about emergency planning in England and non-devolved areas.

Emergency planning for natural hazards is legislated for under the Civil Contingencies Act (2004). The Civil Contingencies Act, together with its supporting guidance, provides the legislative framework for UK emergency management, including natural hazards and other emergencies. The Civil Contingencies Act was developed to address inadequacies and limitations in UK emergency planning. It defines an emergency as:

- an event or situation which threatens serious damage to human welfare in a place in the UK;
- an event or situation which threatens serious damage to the environment of a place in the UK; or
- war, or terrorism, which threatens serious damage to the security of the UK

The Act specifies the roles and responsibilities of local responders for emergency contingency planning and civil protection. Two types of emergency responder are defined: Category 1 responders (e.g. local authorities, emergency services, National Health Service (NHS) bodies and the Environment Agency) and Category 2 responders (e.g. utility companies, transport companies and the Health and Safety Executive). Under the Act, Category 1 responders are required to:

- assess the risk of an emergency occurring;
- maintain and implement emergency contingency plans;
- inform the public about emergency planning and advise them in the event of an emergency;
- co-operate and share information with other local responders for risk assessment or mitigation;
- provide advice and assistance to business and voluntary organisations (local authorities only).

Category 2 responders are required to co-operate and share information with other relevant responders and, where appropriate, may be asked to participate in local resilience planning.

At a central government level, emergency planning is undertaken by the Civil Contingencies Secretariat (CCS) of the Cabinet Office and published in the classified National Security Risk Assessment (NSRA) and unclassified National Risk Register (NRR). In the case of climate change, the risk is assessed by Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs (Defra) in the UK Climate Change Risk Assessment (CCRA), which is published on a five-yearly basis (since 2012) and looks ahead to 2080 and beyond.

12.3.1. Multi-hazard Warnings in the UK

Warnings in the UK are developed and issued by multiple agencies, depending on the hazard and organisational remit of the agency. For example, some hydro-meteorological and weather warnings, as well as climatic risk information are provided by the Met Office, flood alerts are provided by the Flood Forecasting Centre (FFC) (partnership between the EA and Met Office), heatwave alerts are provided by the UK Health Security Agency (UKHSA) in collaboration with the Met Office, and terrorism threat levels are provided by the Joint Terrorism Analysis Centre and the Security Service (MI5). For seismic and landslide risks, BGS provides forecasts that are delivered to the Met Office under the NHP, but there are currently no warnings for landslide risks.

The Met Office issues impact-based warnings for severe weather through the National Severe Weather Warning Service. These warnings are given a colour (yellow, amber or red) depending on a combination of both the impact the weather may have and the likelihood of those impacts occurring following the warning impact matrix (see figure 60 below). Yellow and Amber warnings represent a range of impact levels and likelihoods. This means it is important to read each warning

to know what level of impact you can expect for your chosen warning area – and how likely those impacts are to occur. Impacts can include damage to property, travel delays and cancellations, loss of water supplies, power cuts and, in the most severe cases, bring a danger to life. Weather Warning Levels Guide provided by the Met Office comprise of:

Yellow Warning: Yellow warnings can be issued for a range of weather situations. Many are issued when it is likely that the weather will cause some low level impacts, including some disruption to travel in a few places. Many people may be able to continue with their daily routine, but there will be some that will be directly impacted and so it is important to assess if you could be affected. Other yellow warnings are issued when the weather could bring much more severe impacts to the majority of people but the certainty of those impacts occurring is much lower. It is important to read the content of yellow warnings to determine which weather situation is being covered by the yellow warning.

Figure 59. Warning Impact Matrix (Source: [Met Office](#))

Amber Warning: There is an increased likelihood of impacts from severe weather, which could potentially disrupt your plans. This means there is the possibility of travel delays, road and rail closures, power cuts and the potential risk to life and property. You should think about changing your plans and taking action to protect yourself and your property. You may want to consider the impact of the weather on your family and your community and whether there is anything you need to do ahead of the severe weather to minimise the impact.

Red Warning: Dangerous weather is expected and, if you haven't already done so, you should take action now to keep yourself and others safe from the impact of the severe weather. It is very likely that there will be a risk to life, with substantial disruption to travel, energy supplies and possibly widespread damage to property and infrastructure. You should avoid travelling, where possible, and follow the advice of the emergency services and local authorities.

In summer 2023, the UKHSA in collaboration with the Met Office transitioned to an impact-based alerting for high heat. The Heat-Health Alerting (HHA) system is part of the Weather-Health Alerting (WHA) system. Impact-based HHA systems have been developed alongside the Adverse Weather and Health Plan to provide risk information to professionals within the health and social care sector as well as the public (see figure below).

Figure 60. Heat-Health Alerting System Impact Matrix (Source: [UKHSA](#))

The Met Office regional daytime and night-time maximum temperature forecasts are monitored and when certain temperature thresholds are reached the Met Office and UKHSA undertake an assessment of the potential impacts and likelihood of those impacts occurring. Then a decision is made on whether an alert is needed, and if so, what type of alert to issue (GREEN, YELLOW, AMBER or RED). The updated Heat-Health Alert system is now more closely aligned with the Met Office National Severe Weather Warning Service impact-based alert system:

Green (summer preparedness): No alert will be issued as the conditions are likely to have minimal impact on health. However, during periods where the risk is minimal it is important that organisations ensure that they have plans in place and are prepared to respond should an alert (yellow, amber, or red) be issued.

Yellow (response): These alerts cover a range of situations. Yellow alerts may be issued during periods of heat which would be unlikely to impact most people, but those you are particularly vulnerable (E.g. the elderly with multiple health conditions and on multiple medications) and are likely to struggle to cope and where action is required within the health and social care sector specifically. A yellow alert may also be issued if the confidence in the weather forecast is low, but there could be more significant impacts if the worst-case scenario is realised. In this situation the alert may be upgraded as the confidence in both the weather forecast and the likelihood of observing those impacts improves.

Amber (enhanced response): An amber alert would represent a situation in which the expected impacts are likely to be felt across the whole health service, with potential for the whole population to be at risk and where other sectors apart from health may also start to observe impacts, indicating that a coordinated response is required. In addition, in some circumstances a National

Severe Weather Warning Service (NSWWS) Extreme Heat warning may be issued in conjunction with and aligned to the HHA. This situation would indicate that significant impacts are expected across multiple sectors.

Red (emergency response): A red alert would indicate significant risk to life for event the health population. A red warning would be issued in conjunction with and aligned to a red NSWWS Extreme Heat warning. Severe impacts would be expected across all sectors with a coordinated response essential.

Hazard impact models (HIMs) are currently in development for landslides, surface water flooding, and wind which provide support to impact based warnings and information (Aldridge et al. 2020; Hemingway and Robbins 2020). BGS has developed a comprehensive understanding of regional landslide hazard characteristics and landslide forecasting methodologies. These methodologies use landslide domains related to landscape evolution, geology and characteristic landscape process to evolve the landslide hazard assessment (Dijkstra et al. 2015).

12.3.2. Warning Communication

The Met Office is responsible for issuing weather warnings, including for rain, thunderstorms, wind, snow, lightning, ice, extreme heat and fog. The Met Office has an app that individuals can download to receive weather forecasts and warnings. Individuals can also sign up for Met Office email alerts and warnings. For flood warnings, individuals can sign up for flood warnings by inputting a particular location and post code on the webpage: <https://www.gov.uk/sign-up-for-flood-warnings>. This sign-up is related to the EA warnings as I understand it. MO does rainfall; FFC provides the Flood Guidance Statements which covers fluvial, pluvial and coastal flood hazard. EA provide the more targetted alerting based on this sign-up process. UK Health Security Agency (UKHSA) and the Met Office have been jointly issuing hot and cold heat-health alerts in England since June 2023. Individuals can sign up to receive air quality measurements, forecasts and alerts from UK AIR, the government's air information resource. Some Local Resilience Forums also offer a sign-up option for alerts to receive news and information about emergencies in a specific area.

Emergency Alerts is a UK Government service that can be used to issue warnings in a quick manner if there's imminent danger to life, through cell-broadcast technology. Alerts can be sent out to geo-fenced mobile phones for severe flooding, fires and extreme weather. Alerts can be sent by the UK Government, devolved administrations and other public bodies such as the police or local councils.

12.3.3. Chain of Command and Delivery of Warnings

Category 1 responders, such as emergency services and local authorities, are subject to the full set of civil-protection duties as outlined in the Civil Contingencies Act 2004 (section 4, 20, p12) including: "Arrangements to warn the public, and to provide information and advice to the public, if an emergency is likely to occur or has occurred." These arrangements are typically implemented via a Public Warning Task Group that works within Local Resilience Forums (LRFs). LRFs are multi-agency partnerships made up of representatives from local public services, including the emergency services, local authorities, the NHS, Met Office, EA, and others. Duties under the CCA rest with responders but can be exercised through the LRF. For example, the duty to prepare a Community Risk Register under Regulation 15 rests with Category 1 responders but must be delivered collectively as part of the LRF. LRFs are supported by Category 2 responders, such as the Highways Agency and public utility companies. LRFs for each region and contact details are

provided on the LRFs guidance page (<https://www.gov.uk/guidance/local-resilience-forums-contact-details>).

In particular the LRF role is the compilation of agreed risk profiles for the area, through a Community Risk Register; a systematic, planned and coordinated approach to encourage Category 1 responders, according to their functions, to address all aspects of policy in relation to risk, planning for emergencies, planning for business continuity management, publishing information about risk assessments and plans, arrangements to warn and inform the public; and, other aspects of civil protection duty, including the promotion of business, continuity management by local authorities; and support for the preparation by all or some of its members of multi-agency plans and other documents, including protocols and agreements and the co-ordination of multi-agency exercises (Cabinet Office 2013).

12.3.4. Multi-hazard Coordination

Natural Hazards Partnership (NHP)

The Natural Hazards Partnership (NHP) is a multi-government, multi-agency partnership between 22 UK public bodies:

- British Red Cross
- British Geological Survey (BGS)
- Cabinet Office
- UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology
- Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs
- Department for Transport
- England and Wales Wildfire Forum
- Environment Agency (EA)
- Government Office for Science
- Health and Safety Executive
- Met Office
- National Centre for Atmospheric Science
- National Oceanography Centre
- Natural Environment Research Council (NERC)
- Natural Resources Wales
- Network Rail
- Ordnance Survey
- Public Health England
- Scottish Environment Protection Agency
- The Scottish Government
- UK Space Agency
- Welsh Government

The aim of NHP is to provide authoritative, consistent, and useful hazard, impact, and risk assessment information to responder communities and governments. The NHP is underpinned by a Memorandum of Understanding between the partners which sets out the basic principles of collaboration and also maintains an operating plan that clearly defines the agreed priorities, activities and structures of the partnership (Hemingway and Gunawan 2018). At an organizational level, all NHP partners are public bodies from within, or associated with a UK, Scottish or Welsh government department. This ensures that members already operate in a similar organizational environment and all are working primarily to improve public services (Hemingway and Gunawan 2018).

The NHP Steering Group (NHPSG) sets the overall direction. Coordination and delivery of the Operating Plan are devolved to the Management Team. Delivery of science and services is led by the Natural Hazards Science to Services Group (HIS2G). Each group has a clearly defined remit within the partnership and consists of representatives from multiple NHP partners.

NHP partners are responsible for developing the information (risk assessment and forecast) for the Daily Hazard Assessment (DHA), which the Met Office compiles and publishes on the Hazard Manager website which the Met Office currently operates. The DHA provides a general overview of potential natural hazards as well as health implications that could affect the UK over the following 5 days (see figure 61 below), providing the basis for coordinated multi-hazard early warnings. It contains links to more detailed information to specific agency webpages about each highlighted hazard.

However, NHP partners currently can only upload generalised information on the Hazard Manager website but it was noted by interviewees that the system does not allow for partners to upload in their own data formats.

Figure 61a and b: Examples of NHP Daily Hazard Assessment; a) original DHA b) updated layout 2024 (Source: Hemingway and Gunawan 2018; Crown 2024)

The DHA uses the NHP Hazard Matrix to assess 9 natural hazards with hazard assessments up to 5-days ahead. The Hazard Matrix colors are consistent across all natural hazards resulting in a consistent message for impact assessment. It also allows for comparison of hazards based on likelihood and potential impact. The DHA is available on a daily basis to all UK Category 1 and 2 responders (emergency services and supporting organisations) using the Met Office's Hazard

Manager. Government organisations, emergency authorities, and local authorities can signed up to receive the DHA from Hazard Manager via email or SMS.

An internal report found that emergency and resilience professionals regard the DHA to be clear, reliable and useful, valuing the all-hazards approach and summary maps, while those in operational emergency response roles considered the DHA less immediately useful, those in strategic and managerial roles used it to increase their situational awareness and provide a 'heads-up' for the coming week (Hemingway and Gunawan 2018). An updated survey of users is due in 2025.

12.4. Strengths, Gaps and Recommendations

This section outlines key strengths, gaps, and good practices of DRR activities and warning systems that were identified during the course of the research analysis. Some limitations and challenges were explicitly identified by interviewees given their expertise and experience, while others were identified through analysis by the researchers. However, the authors refrain from citing direct quotes from the interviewees to protect participant confidentiality. Recommendations on how to address the gaps and challenges are also provided. Good practices are highlighted as examples that can be transferred and scaled to other DEMs and potential areas to collaborate with other DEMs are also discussed.

12.4.1. Strengths and Good Practices

1. Comprehensive Scope of Multi-hazard risks Covered

The DRM system in the UK serves as a best practice for a comprehensive multi-hazard system that covers a wide range of hazards. This wide scope includes hydrometeorological, geophysical, and climate-related hazards but also biological and health risks, extraterrestrial, and societal hazards like terrorism. Following the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (2015-2030) and the Hazard Profiles guidelines, the provision of multiple hazards are also critical for developing a multi-hazard warning system. Other DEMs gain valuable practical insights on how the UK operates multiple and connected hazards in a collaborative way with responsible authorities.

2. Impact-based Forecasts and Warnings and Evaluation

The UK has pioneered the use of impact-based warnings to enhance public preparedness and response to natural hazards. Scientists at the Met Office use novel risk and impact modelling integrating hazard forecast information with vulnerability and exposure datasets to assess the potential impacts and likelihood of impacts of natural hazards occurring (Hemingway and Robbins 2018; Tittley and Robbins 2013). Advancements in risk and impact modelling for forecast applications has helped not only improve forecasting and warning of hydro-meteorological hazards but also developed comprehensive impact models to understand the extent of different impacts caused by a range of hazards. Research from the Met Office has shown that this approach improves public understanding and response actions (2019). During flood events, impact-based warnings specify expected disruptions such as road closures, transport delays, or risks to homes and businesses, allowing people to take specific and informed actions. A study published by the Met Office in 2019 found that the introduction of impact-based warnings for flooding led to more timely evacuations and protective actions in at-risk areas. The Met Office provides a comprehensive overview of impacts for rain, thunderstorms, wind, snow, lightning, ice, extreme heat, and fog through the [Impacts Table Guide](#). Furthermore, in 2023, the Heat-Health Alerts transitioned to an impact-based alerting as well, providing users with information on the impacts likely to be observed as a result of high temperatures.

Recognising the developments and complexities of impact based forecasting and warning, from both a scientific and operational standpoint, it is important to test, verify and evaluate impact based forecasts and warnings regularly (Robbins and Titley 2018, Robbins et al., 2022). While impact-based approaches provide helpful and important information to users, it was noted during interviews, that at times, impact-based approaches are not as straightforward for those responsible for issuing warnings.. Traditional threshold-based warnings were cited as more straightforward and easier, reducing the pressure of making decisions related to impact severity. Interviews mentioned that having a team, rather than one or two meteorologists making this decision based on the impact forecasts would help ease decision-making burden during the process but also after when warnings are issued. However, as mentioned in earlier sections, there are advantages and disadvantages to impact-based vs threshold based warnings, and it is important to examine which works for specific multi-hazard contexts and for different users and vulnerabilities.

3. Multi-level Risk Mapping

Through the Civil Contingencies Act (2004), the central government (Cabinet Office), in collaboration with partners, is responsible for developing and publishing the classified National Security Risk Assessment (NSRA) and the unclassified National Risk Register (NRR). At the same time the Local Resilience Forums are tasked with compiling Community Risk Registers (CCRs) in compliance with their statutory responsibilities. This process helps to ensure that national resilience planning coincides with local-level emergency planning. It also allows for contextualised and localised assessments of risks.

4. Strong Research-backed approaches across Warning Systems

The UK system boasts cutting edge modelling, forecasting, and development of impact-based warnings in order to provide increasingly accurate and reliable services for adverse weather, ocean, and climatic conditions. Research at the Met Office, BGS, UKHSA builds on a range of scientific disciplines from fundamental atmospheric physics to ecosystem behaviour. However, it was highlighted during interviews that while Research and Operations meet and work together, this collaboration could be further strengthened especially when rolling out novel approaches and services to ensure that they are evidence based and drawing on the work of the research teams.

5. Well-Developed Local Networks

At the regional and local level, there are well-developed networks of partners working on DRR, including local councils, public and voluntary organisations. This was the case in Dorset County, where the local councils worked closely with Dorset Coast Forum, Jurassic Trust, and other organisations. It would be important to support and strengthen these existing networks as well as establish long-standing partnerships. BGS has developed this relationship during the course of this project.

12.4.2. Gaps and Challenges

1. Establishing secure and efficient channels for sharing data and documents between all NHP partners and also others remains a challenge (Hemingway and Gunawan 2018). This was a recurrent challenge brought up by many stakeholders during the course of interviews. For example, local authorities and organisations in Dorset noted the need for contextual risk information on the conditions of potential landslides, including rainfall, geology, rock composition, etc.
2. The NHP provides a valuable mechanism for multi-agency collaboration. However, the NHP currently does not have a legal mandate, posing many challenges with regard to management,

funding and financing, sustainability and long-term support from central government. NHP partners are not provided any resources or mechanisms to carry out NHP responsibilities and deliver the Daily Hazard Assessment. Sponsorship from the central government would not only provide the NHP with a legal mandate, providing the UK disaster risk community with a unifying focal point and coordination body for multi-hazard risk management and warning but also incentivise partners to continue to contribute and provide their services and expertise.

3. Among stakeholders there are different terminologies used for risks, specifically landslide risks, which can pose significant challenges in communication and response efforts. Variations in terminology may lead to confusion and misinterpretation among stakeholders, including the public. For example, the same phenomenon, landslides, in Dorset county is referred to by different stakeholders and the media in different ways, e.g. landslides and technical failure mechanisms are colloquially and in professional settings referred to as landslips, rockfalls, cliff falls, etc. Inconsistent terminology can hinder collaboration, as stakeholders may have different understandings of the scope of the risk or the necessary preventive measures to take. Standardising terminology is crucial for clear communication, effective risk management, and better preparedness.
4. Warnings are often issued at a national level, with Local Resilience Forums working to apply them at their level. However, coordination and communication between Local Resilience Forums can be challenging when working across regions. More multi-scale integration and coordination is needed, especially when dealing with multi-hazard events.
5. There are few formal mechanisms to integrate external expertise from universities and researchers, NGOs, businesses, and other stakeholders into decision-making processes. The way things are currently set up does not allow for the public and their input to be incorporated, except for deliberate projects such as the one under the HuT with BGS and local partners in Dorset. This collaboration could be scaled up on the regional and national level to include more non-government entities as well.

12.4.3. Recommendations and Opportunities for Collaboration with other DEMs

1. Lessons on how DEM3 (Italy) and DEM 10 (Switzerland)'s decentralised yet integrated system across national, regional, and local scales could be very productive for the UK. The UK currently operates under both a centralised system for the majority of services, including the design, decision-making, and delivery of warnings as well as a decentralised system through the Local Resilience Forums for assessing and responding to localised risks through the Community Risk Register and maintaining emergency plans. However, while the national government provides guidance to LRFs, there is limited oversight, integration, and coordination from the central or regional levels to the LRFs. Effective leadership, structures and streamlining processes are needed in order to deal with multi-risk events that are large-scale.
2. UK partners can gain practical lessons from the legally mandated coordinating body LAINAT from DEM10 (Switzerland). The Natural Hazard Partnership, while similar in scope but larger in size could benefit from how LAINAT operates in order to provide multi-hazard risk information and warnings in a coordinated way supported by central government, leading to efficient data-sharing arrangements as well as sustainable funding. DEM3 Italy's national civil protection multi-hazard, multi-agency also operates in this way.
3. Critical insights can be learned from Switzerland's data-sharing platform called GIN, which provides a secure and user-friendly mechanism for partners to exchange and share data, to fill current gaps in data-sharing between NHP partners and beyond.

4. UK partners can gain lessons from DEM6's use of Scientific Councils for different hazards. Currently, the UK has something similar under the Scientific Advisory Group for Emergencies (SAGE). However, SAGE is only convened in the event of a national emergency by the Cabinet Office Briefing Room (COBR) to provide independent scientific advice to support decision-making. While this is critical, it would be productive to expand the concept and application of SAGE further to more regular meetings between government entities and the scientific community to strengthen research on multi-hazard risks and management.
5. The CCRA and NSRA have different roles within government (i.e. one is for long-term adaptation planning and the other looks at short-term emergency response) and are not currently aligned with one another. To improve resilience planning, incorporating these approaches would prove beneficial, especially as new and evolving multi-hazard risks emerge.

13. Summary and Takeaways

13.1. Summary

This report provides an overview of how disaster risk management and the early warning systems in five European countries are structured with a closer look at five regions / territories that are exposed to multiple hazards and within which actions are taken to tackle the need for MHEWS. We refer to the regions / territories as the demonstrator sites (DEMs) of the HuT project. In this report, the assessment has covered the multi-level disaster risk governance and management framework where the DEMs are embedded. Table 8 provides a high-level overview of the key aspects and elements of the MHEW systems for all five of the DEMs. This table focuses more on the differences at national level although aspects of more local levels of governance are embedded in relevant sections. In table 9 the key strengths, gaps and opportunities for development of inclusive MHEWS of each DEM is outlined, providing a snapshot for each DEM to see areas of strengths and weaknesses, and where there may be potential to strengthen their MHEW, or indeed provide support to other nations.

Taking a wider perspective, this research has demonstrated that within an European context many countries have developed warning systems in vastly different ways and there is no one-size fits all model. Many of these systems have roots based in disaster events that have spurred the development and ongoing evolution of warning systems. Whilst this research has focused on the multi-hazard context, it is clear that many of the DEMs could strengthen their multi-hazard approaches, particularly when it comes to multi-hazard governance structures, including the links between agencies, sharing of data, and collaboration. The DEMS have different governance structures and mechanisms to coordinate decision-making and communication and challenges remain on how to bring both hazard related and institutional silos together to create genuine multi-hazard warning systems. Each DEM provides practical insights into how to achieve this panacea.

The table 8 below provides a high-level snapshot of each DEM's national MHWS and governance structure to enable comparison across DEMs drawn from our research and analysis. The scope of each country's multi-hazard warning system is documented using national-level official information from government websites and services. The categorisation is based on ISC-UNDRR Hazard Information Profiles, which draws on Sendai Framework's comprehensive definition of MHWSs. Different DEMs have a range of hazards covered for warnings, including natural hazards, climate extremes, and geophysical hazards but also biological (e.g. air pollution, pandemics and health alerts), technological, extraterrestrial, and societal (e.g. terrorism alerts).

Table 8: Comparison Summary of DEMS on MHWS

	DEM 2 Val d’Aran, Spain	DEM 3 Lattari, Italy	DEM 6 E Fjords, Iceland	DEM 9 Dorset, UK	DEM 10 Bern, Switzerland
MHWS Scope*	Hydro-meteorological, Climate & Environment, Extraterrestrial Geophysical, Chemical, Biological, Technological, Societal	Hydro-meteorological, Climate & Environment, Geophysical, Biological, Chemical, Industrial	Hydro-meteorological, Climate & Environment, Biological, Geophysical, Technological	Hydro-meteorological, Climate & Environment, Geophysical, Biological, Chemical, Extraterrestrial, Technological, Societal	Hydro-meteorological, Climate & Environment, Geophysical, Technological
MHWS Governance Structure	Decentralised	Decentralised	Centralised	Centralised	Decentralised
MHWS Coordination across authorities and/or scales	Partially, through CP	Between authorities and across scales through Civil Protection	Between authorities through IMO and NCIP partnership	Between authorities through Natural Hazard Partnership	Between authorities and across scales through LAINAT
Type of Warning	Both threshold and impact-based warnings	Both threshold and impact-based warnings	Impact-based warnings	Impact-based warnings	Threshold-based warnings
Warning Channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ES Alert (cell broadcast) - Webpages - Sirens - Apps - Social media - Radio & TV broadcasts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - IT Alert (cell broadcast) - Webpages - Sirens - Broadcast 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Location-based SMS (Cell broadcast) - Webpages - Apps - Sirens - Social media - Radio & TV broadcasts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cell broadcast - Webpages - Apps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Webpages - Apps - Sirens - Radio - Broadcast
Alert system	<p>National level meteorological & hydrological warnings:</p> <p>Colour-coded: Green, Yellow, Orange, Red</p>	<p>Standardised four level alert system</p> <p>Colour-coded: Green, Yellow, Orange, Red</p>	<p>Varied systems</p> <p>IMO colour-coded: Green, Yellow, Orange, Red</p>	<p>Varied systems across agencies</p> <p>MET Office colour-coded: Yellow, Amber or Red</p>	<p>Standardised five level alert system</p> <p>Colour-coded & numbered: 1-5 Green, Yellow, Orange, Red, Dark Red</p>

Accessibility-Languages	Varies websites in 2-5 co-official languages	Websites in 2 languages	Varies-websites & apps in 1-3 languages	Websites & apps only in English	Websites & apps in 5 languages
Multi-sectoral Collaboration	Yes, with scientific community, local and territorial agencies	Yes, with scientific community	Yes, with scientific community	No (everything through agency authorities)	Yes, with private sector
Data System	Data is publicly available on AEMET website; MITECO website (hydrological data), IGN website (seismic & volcanic activity data)	Data is publicly available on CP website	Data is publicly available on IMO website	Data is publicly available on MET Office Climate Data Portal, partially open on BGS website, other data needs special permissions	Data is closed to public, open to authorities through GIN
Public Engagement	Targeted projects and Location specific	National DRR campaigns and Location specific	Targeted projects and Location specific	Targeted projects and Location specific	Targeted projects and Location specific

*This is taken from the national level warning systems published on government webpages and categories are based on [ISC-UNDRR Hazard Information Profiles](#). These are general categories provided by HIP, but it does not necessarily mean cover every hazard within the category.

Val d'Aran, Spain (DEM 2), Lattari, Italy (DEM 3), and Bern, Switzerland (DEM10) operate decentralised warning systems that enable bottom-up approaches and the ability to work across different levels of governance (national, regional, and local). In contrast E Fjords, Iceland (DEM 6) and Dorset in the UK (DEM 9) adopt a more centralised, top-down approach to warnings, whereby bottom-up integration is still needed. However, in both Iceland and the UK, at the central level there is coordination and partnerships in place to enable the co-production of knowledge across different agencies.

Multi-hazard coordination is another component examined, whether a MHWS has multi-agency, multi-sectoral coordination across national, regional, and local scales through mechanisms such as official partnerships or coordination bodies bridging agencies and stakeholders together. Lattari, Italy (DEM 3), Dorset, UK (DEM 9), and Bern, Switzerland (DEM10) boast coordination both across levels of governance through different mechanisms as well as horizontally across agencies.

Communication of warnings is critical and there has been a significant rise in the implementation of cell-broadcast technologies, driven by EU-Alert in 2012 so that all DEMs except DEM10 have cell-broadcast technologies as one method for warning communication and dissemination. It is vital that this is not the only form of communication, as technology does fail as seen in the Germany floods in 2021 resulting in 184 deaths. Redundancy is therefore critical, but cell-broadcasting does at least enable most people in the DEM sites to obtain up to date and immediate information that could be life saving. All DEMs use a range of communication channels

including social media (although not Tik Tok that excludes younger members of society), sirens, and TV and radio.

Whether a warning is communicated or not, is largely irrelevant if the people receiving it do not know what it means, what to do, or are unable to take timely action. To resolve this DEM 6 and DEM 9 use impact-based warnings that enable the receiver of the warning to gain a better insight into what the hazard event will mean for them. The other DEMs use a combination or solely a threshold-based approach. The challenges with using a threshold-based approach are that with more extreme climatic events, some thresholds may not be seen as a concern, but when happening concurrently or as a consequence of another hazard, thresholds may not be exceeded and no warning will be issued, yet the hazard still poses significant risks.

With regards to collaborating with entities outside the government agencies tasked to provide a warning, i.e. the scientific community, the private sector, civil society, all DEMs except DEM 9 have official multi-sectoral partnerships they draw upon for services throughout the warning value chain. However, it is important to note that DEM 10 through the HuT project and BGS partners is currently establishing partnerships with community organisations like the Dorset Coast Forum in Dorset, UK.

The alert systems used across the DEMs typically use a colour coded format, with DEM 6, and DEM 10 adopting fairly standardised warning systems, albeit for different hazards. DEM 6 and DEM 9 have a range of different alert systems and designs and typologies, dependent on the hazard and its historical evolution. It is also little surprise that DEM 9 is the only site to only produce warnings in one language, English, as the other DEMs have at least two or more languages. With cell broadcasting this is an issue that can be resolved by the message appearing in the language the phone is set to.

With regards to data systems, most of the DEMs with the exception of DEM10 have open data systems where data is publicly available or accessible. However, it is important to note that the data shared by government agencies might not be user friendly or in the format that is needed by stakeholders. More efforts are needed to both understand and respond to user needs and data sharing.

Lastly, only DEM3 has national-level campaigns on disaster risk education and mitigation, i.e. simulation exercises that include citizens, regular workshops and awareness campaigns, with also official curriculum in the school system and an extensive volunteer network. The other DEMs all have public engagement activities targeting specific locations and hazards through projects.

13.2. Key Takeaways for DEMs

There are numerous opportunities for DEMs to learn from each other's experiences on developing the MHEWS. An active role from the HuT project in advancing this learning could involve the arrangement of workshops where the DEMs would exchange their experiences and knowledge with sufficient time and facilitation provided. Reporting from such an event would also serve wider audiences.

A key takeaway of this report for the DEMs studied is that several countries and their sub-regions are currently facing an unprecedented situation of having to rapidly develop MHEWS when even the single hazard warnings are not always in place or well developed to effectively address all audiences. The governance and policy support tools, such as the UCP, ERCC, EECC and CEMS remain necessary to advance the MHEWS development. Due to the gaps identified in the case sites, we suggest that even more support is needed to strengthen the local governments' motivation and capacities in engaging with the cross-sectoral multi-level MHEWS management.

Table 9. Summary comparison of the DEMS highlighting strengths and gaps

DEM	Key strengths	Key gaps	Key steps to enhance warnings & collaboration opportunities
DEM 2 Val d’Aran, Spain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Standardised warnings through Cell Broadcast Technology Territorial hazard and risk expertise Specific action plans Cross-sectoral collaboration Development of locally-led warning system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Drought warnings of national rivers basins are not cohesive with the Catalonian system that provides easy-to-reach information for all users A lack of warnings for landslides Inclusivity of the Catalonian warnings level are hindered by limitations in only using Spanish or Catalan languages The cell broadcast alerts do not reach everyone and for tourists, immigrants and language minorities without local social networks, interpretation of what to do in an emergency situation can be difficult Providing warnings via two or three organisations may be challenging for 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fill the gap in landslide warnings (DEM3 and 6) Develop more effective coordination across local, regional, and national levels (DEM 3 and 10) Develop a regional warning system in Val d’Aran due to its unique hazard-scape and geography relative to the rest of Catalonia (DEM 6) Design warnings for local meteorological hazards other than floods, preferably using international standards as used by AEMET and SMC so to increase accessibility and reach of warnings (DEM 9) Support local networks that hold historical and local knowledge on the hazard occurrence and management to build trust and successful collaboration between stakeholders in

		<p>the public to decide which source to use and how to interpret potential inconsistencies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Warnings are focused on first response but development on preparedness is key to enhance warnings • Lack of political and public interest in increasing the effectiveness of warnings 	<p>changing conditions (DEM 3, 9, 10)</p>
<p>DEM 3 Lattari, Italy</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordination and Integration through one body - Civil Protection • Comprehensive coverage of multi-hazard risks • Strong citizen participation and volunteering through exercises and campaigns • Recent law in 2019, Law n. 92 established that risk information and civil protection be taught in national education programs as part of the compulsory 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • While vertical integration between the national civil protection and regional functional centres are strong, integration with downstream actors of municipalities still faces challenges. • Lacks a civilian meteorological service that the entire country uses providing a standardised knowledge base • Lack of harmonisation between municipalities in communicating and disseminating 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • While responsibility first falls to the local authorities, developing standard training to municipalities can highly benefit warnings (DEM 10) • Conduct post-event analysis, evaluations, and reviews to identify lessons learned • While all warning bulletins issued by the regional functional centres are synthesised together and posted on the national civil protection website on a map, it would benefit from being clearer (DEMS 9, 10)

	<p>course of Civil Education</p>	<p>warnings, including channels used and warning design</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited training that is given to downstream levels of the municipalities and mayors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enforce the updating of emergency plans and hazard maps at the municipal scale, as these plans are not validated or verified strictly at the national level by civil protection (DEM 10)
<p>DEM 6 E Fjords, Iceland</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adaptability, local expertise and cross-sectoral collaboration Preparedness on expected and unexpected multi-hazard risks Post-event review and community engagement after disasters Active citizen participation in DRM 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gaps in documentation, regulation and protocols in practices, may result in inequitable knowledge and warnings Information available in languages other than Icelandic Enhancing the effectiveness of warnings on the “last-mile/first-mile”, some may 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Clarify where tourists and foreign residents can obtain information and warnings on bio-geo-physical hazards and what to do when dealing with climate extremes and hazards (DEM3) Establish a network of local observers that are embedded in the DRM system to provide a more harmonised approach and integration of multi-level hazard

		<p>overlook the warnings.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visitors from abroad find it difficult to understand which warnings to follow and how to interpret them • Local activity in emergency situations may contradict official guidelines and warnings that may challenge the formal DRM system. • Further integration of communication between differing scales of decision-making e.g. National Commission of Police with the regional, municipal, and local police departments • Communicate warnings to the public in a timely manner 	<p>monitoring and observation (DEM10)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop Web platforms for national risks and warnings (DEM3, 9, 10) • Develop a data-sharing platform where information about warnings, risk assessments, and actions and response measures is shared. (DEM 10) • Use apps and web pages to reach non-residents, visitors, and tourists, with detailed information on actions and measures to take • Develop information sheets for tourists at hotels and other awareness activities
<p>DEM 9 Dorset, UK</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pioneering of Impact-based warnings for weather and heat warnings • Multi-level Risk Mapping 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Secure and easy data-sharing between stakeholders • Legally mandating multi-hazard, multi-agency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning from DEM3 and DEM10 on multi-scale coordination and bottom-up integration • Learning from DEM 10 on secure and

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong research evidence-based warning systems • Well-developed local networks 	<p>coordination of NHP</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardising terminology • Multi-scale integration and coordination • Expanding scope for multi-sectoral collaboration 	<p>user-friendly data-sharing practices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Draw on lessons from DEM6 on incorporating Scientific Councils
<p>DEM 10 Bern, Switzerland</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Top down and bottom-up integration with local natural hazard advisors • Multi-hazard warning coordination through LAINAT giving a single official voice • Joint Platform for Data sharing: GIN • Multi-stakeholder partnerships • Delineation of roles and responsibilities between Scales • Risk-informed planning and hazard maps • Multilingual web platforms • Post-event Evaluation and analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The level of harmonisation between cantons and municipalities is variable • Narrow hazard focus predominantly on weather and floods that would benefit from addressing other hazards • Lack of engagement with ‘the downstream’ i.e. public users. • It is vital the platforms all share the same exact information and coincide their warnings and alerts to be consistent, clear, and accurate in order to ensure legitimacy and trust in sources and information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop upstream and downstream channels with oversight to ensure that each entity at federal, canton, and municipality scales, carry out their roles and responsibilities • Issue cell broadcasting technologies for warnings • Warning are generally based on a threshold system, consider issuing impact-based warnings to include exposure and vulnerability risks (DEM 6, 9) • Engage the public. e.g volunteer services, public simulation and exercises, open days, and disaster risk education (DEM 3, 6, 9)

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Obtain and incorporate feedback from the public on the effectiveness, quality, and timeliness of warnings and actions by authorities (DEM 9) • Enhance collaboration with universities, research institutes, or scientific communities that could be beneficial (DEM 6)
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In summary key recommendation points specific for each DEM are:

DEM 2 Spain:

1. **Advancing Landslide Warning Systems:** Efforts by ICGC and UPC to develop landslide warnings need legislative recognition for adequate resources. Collaboration with Spain’s ARANTEC and DEM3 (Italy) could help advance these systems, while Iceland’s experience with developing landslide warnings may provide valuable insights.
2. **Enhancing Coordination Across Governance Levels:** Spain’s decentralized civil protection system faces coordination challenges. Learning from DEM3 (Italy) and DEM10 (Switzerland), particularly Switzerland’s supra-coordinating body LAINAT, could improve multi-hazard coordination without political constraints.
3. **Improving Regional and Multi-Hazard Warnings:** Val d’Aran requires a regional warning system tailored to its unique hazards, using stakeholder workshops for inclusivity. Expanding meteorological warnings beyond floods—such as drought warnings—could benefit from DEM9 (UK)’s expertise in multi-hazard impact-based warnings

DEM 3 Italy:

1. **Training for Local Authorities:** Italian partners can learn from Switzerland’s DEM 10 on standardized training for municipalities, as mayors in Italy often lack training in disaster risk reduction (DRR), emergency response, and warning communication, making decision-making challenging during disasters.
2. **Post-Event Evaluations:** Italy can benefit from DEM 9 and DEM 10’s approach to post-event analysis and reviews, as the current system in Italy, heavily focused on liability, discourages thorough assessments and learning from past events.
3. **Improving Warning Communication:** Italy’s national civil protection system could enhance its warning dissemination by adopting Switzerland and Iceland’s methods, such as

centralized national platforms and mobile apps, to provide clearer and more accessible information to the public.

DEM 6 Iceland:

1. **Enhancing Public Awareness and Education:** While Iceland's locals are familiar with natural hazards, tourists and foreign residents lack awareness. Learning from Italy's disaster risk education campaigns, multilingual signage, and video resources could help improve hazard preparedness.
2. **Strengthening Hazard Monitoring and Communication:** Iceland's snow observer system for avalanches is expanding to landslides but could benefit from Switzerland's model of Local Natural Hazard Advisors (LNHAs). Additionally, a national risk web platform, like those in Italy, Switzerland, and the UK, would improve hazard communication and public access to warnings.
3. **Improving Consistency in Risk Communication:** Discrepancies between Iceland's Safe Travel app, IMO, and NCIP websites create confusion. Ensuring consistent messaging across platforms, conducting visitor surveys, and providing hazard information at hotels and for new residents would enhance awareness and preparedness.

DEM 9 UK:

1. **Data Sharing:** Establishing secure and efficient channels for sharing data remains a challenge for the Natural Hazard Partnership (NHP) and other key stakeholders. Stakeholders, including local authorities in Dorset, have highlighted the need for access to critical data and risk information to better understand and deal with natural hazards like landslides.
2. **NHP's Policy Support:** The NHP offers valuable multi-agency collaboration originally driven by Government needs, but it lacks a legal mandate, creating challenges in management, funding, and long-term sustainability. A legal framework with central government support would provide a unifying focal point for risk management and incentivize continued partner contributions to the NHP's efforts.
3. **Terminology Variations:** Different terminologies used for landslide hazards, such as "landslips" or "rockfalls," pose challenges for communication and response. Whilst these terms are referred to by different stakeholders and the media as colloquial language e.g. landslips, and technical failure mechanisms e.g. rockfalls, cliff falls, etc, inconsistent language can cause confusion and hinder effective collaboration. Standardizing terminology is essential for clear communication, risk management, and preparedness.
4. **Coordination Between Local Resilience Forums:** While warnings are issued at the national level, coordination between Local Resilience Forums (LRFs) can be challenging, particularly when responding to multi-hazard events across regions. Increased integration and coordination across scales are needed for more effective hazard response.
5. **Limited Integration of External Expertise and Public Engagement:** There are few formal mechanisms for integrating external expertise, such as from universities, NGOs, and businesses, into decision-making processes. Expanding collaboration with non-government entities at regional and national levels could enhance risk management and preparedness.

DEM 10 Switzerland:

1. **Improving Oversight and Communication Across Governance Levels:** Switzerland's decentralized warning system relies on municipalities, leading to inconsistencies and failures, such as the Neuchatel floods. Strengthening oversight and harmonization across federal, canton, and municipal levels is necessary to ensure timely and effective warnings.
2. **Implementing Cell Broadcasting for Warnings:** Unlike many European countries, Switzerland lacks an SMS-based cell broadcasting system for emergency warnings. Learning from other DEMs can help implement best practices while addressing funding challenges.
3. **Shifting to Impact-Based Warnings:** Switzerland's threshold-based warning system could be improved by incorporating impact-based decision-making, considering contextual factors like season, population, and risk exposure. Lessons from Iceland (DEM 6) and the UK (DEM 9) could aid in this transition.
4. **Enhancing Public Engagement and Feedback:** Public involvement in disaster preparedness, through volunteer services, simulations, and awareness campaigns, can be improved by learning from Italy (DEM 3), Iceland (DEM 6), and the UK (DEM 9). Additionally, Switzerland should integrate public feedback into post-event reviews to strengthen trust and refine warning processes.
5. **Strengthening Collaboration with Research Institutions:** While government-private sector collaboration is strong, partnerships with universities and research institutes remain limited. Adopting Iceland's (DEM 6) model of engaging researchers through scientific councils could enhance innovation and disaster risk management.

14. Conclusions

The research presented in this report highlights the wide diversity and scope of warning systems across the five DEMs investigated. Whilst each warning system is embedded in local DRR activities that are shaped by historical events and social and cultural contexts, there are some common aspects that lead to more effective and enhanced warnings.

► Key factors for building successful MHEWS:

1. Developing effective warnings that consider multiple-hazards, cascading events, and integration across stakeholders.
 - a. This requires governance structures that facilitate cross institutional and cross scale knowledge sharing, integration and decision-making.
 - b. It is vital to generate accurate warnings where possible, and specify the uncertainties involved clearly and embrace the often unknown situations that may emerge. Extreme climatic hazards are posing further challenges by generating crises on scales not recently witnessed and this needs to be accurately conveyed to all stakeholders.
 - c. Preparedness activities are critical to support effective warnings, and lay the foundations for success, however there is also a need to be adaptive and flexible, particularly in the context of a multi-hazard context
 - d. Generating more transparent warnings and data via clear governance structures, open and consistent information and guidance available and accessible to all in a timely manner are critical. This requires working across different languages, different platforms, and being consistent and clear. Having a unified voice of information is critical for credibility to prevent confusion.
 - e. Timely warnings are critical - all too often bureaucratic procedures or lack of clear protocols causes delays in information to the vulnerable communities. Warnings need to be shared so people can have time to process, prepare, and pursue further updates.
2. Adopting public engagement and outreach programmes that empowers local authorities and the public to identify and fulfil their own needs regarding warnings for enhancing preparedness and response behaviours and actions.
 - a. It is vital that key policies are shaped by using public dialogues with scientists, organisations, policy makers and the public. By adopting a first mile approach it empowers those for whom a warning is designed for.
 - b. Several tools and approaches can be used to develop key policy including citizen science, citizen juries / panels, and community, community based warnings.
 - c. It is vital to help the ongoing practice, maintenance, and revisiting of warnings through simulations and drills. Situations, personnel, hazards, and local and national contingencies change over time and a warning system should be updated to reflect these changes. They are not static systems but adapting emergent ones.

- d. Communities have the capacity at a local level to process and manage multiple hazards and risks in a manner that is not possible at a national level. Therefore coordination and communication that crosses the top-down, bottom-up divide is critical using tools such as Integrating Education, Exchange, Engagement across all hazard agencies and the public.
3. Creating and supporting mechanisms to overcome silos and territorialism and instead to encourage idea and action exchange for building trust.
 - a. For a MHWS to work, there needs to be a governance structure that cuts across the various warning organisations that are typically hazard defined. This can be set up as a committee or advisory group, often defined by the civil protection legislation set up in each nation.
 - b. Significant challenges are involved in working across these silos with differing understandings of hazard terminology, appropriate actions, warning capacities, and knowledge that is commonly shaped in each academic and institutional field.
 - c. Training and exercises help to break down social barriers and build up awareness and connections so there is transfer from warning to action.
 - d. It is vital to clarify responsibilities and roles and by simulating an event and addressing conflicting issues, alongside the inclusivity of all people.
 - e. Encourage more active sharing of hazard knowledge, monitoring, and warning facilities to create awareness, between agency staff and the public, to enhance engagement around MHWS. This includes learning from case studies globally and reviewing crises to evaluate how effective the warning process was, and where there are gaps for improvement, without any blame or litigation consequences.

By further integrating warnings as part of DRR activities across Europe it is possible to generate MHWS that build on existing agencies without having to completely change governance structures. In each DEM the perceived risks from multiple hazards are expected to become more complex and severe due to climate change among other factors, and this drives the regions/territories to take action while there are numerous obstacles that hinder the process, including most importantly the lack of monetary resources and political will to develop more effective systems. However, our cases demonstrate alongside previous literature suggests that locally led initiatives with support from professional networks and the research community can gain momentum, unfortunately, from disastrous events, but also from experiences of empowerment and strengthened community.

Working across multiple warning systems

For many of the DEMS it is not just multiple hazards that need to be managed, but also many of the warning systems in place in the five DEMs use a range of warning systems from the Common Alerting Protocol (CAP), to cell-based warnings, to globally integrated warnings (such as for meteorites or drought or famine), to automated warnings for particular hazards such as flooding, to community based warnings. It is critical that all these warning systems work together to reinforce safety, and this requires recognition of both highly formulated and automated warning processes, with highly adaptive localised warning knowledge and processes.

Further to the range of warning systems in place, there are differing scales. There are EU wide warnings in place, such as MeteoAlarm, an Early Warning Dissemination System that visualises, aggregates, and accessibly provides awareness information from 38 European National

Meteorological and Hydrological Services, and Copernicus Emergency Management Service (CEMS) provides information for emergency response and disaster risk management. There is no shortage of data, in fact quite the opposite and AI may be helpful used to cut through large sets of data to aid decision-making processes. However, it is important that it is quality rather than quantity of data, and data by itself does not help to make decisions in times of uncertainty. Currently most EU wide warning services focus more on monitoring, forecasting, and hazard knowledge. Additionally, there are a range of more global scale warning systems in place for volcanic ash and Near Earth Objects (NEO), alongside more regional systems for tsunami that can be part of the suite of warning systems.

What is next for EU wide warnings?

Moving forward it would be advisable to generate an EU wide warnings initiative that unites existing warning bodies and datasets, but also expands to work with all four elements of warnings and within DRR by working with the social science aspects of warnings that often get neglected - the receiving of warnings, believing and trusting the warning, being able to act on the warning, understanding the warning, and acting on the warning. This will also aid multi-hazard warning capacity, alongside integration with key infrastructure and other risks such as conflict, nuclear energy, or air pollution etc.

Warning redundancy is needed to reach as many people as possible, with the caveat that it needs to be consistent. Ultimately building a strong and robust multi-hazard and multi-warning system requires constant communication between the stakeholders. In the future it is foreseeable that more countries will work across national boundaries to pool resources and enhance warnings, particularly for extreme weather and wildfires, this is already being done in Greece.

To achieve this financial investment is needed in warnings, and to help facilitate cross hazard, institutional, and national organisations. Whilst budgets remain tight, warning systems have consistently shown their value for money and remain one of the cost effective DRR actions available. In a world full of ever more complex, unpredictable, interdependent, systemic risks, more investment is needed in the management of these using adaptive tools to establish and communicate the risks so they can be mitigated and vulnerable populations can take action.

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